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D7.4-Results from the expert-based socio-economic assessment of EBA interventions

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
AAL	Average annual losses
BAU	Business-as-usual
BCC	Beach-carrying capacity
BT	Benefit transfer
CBA	Cost-benefit analysis
CCI	Construction cost index
CCLL	Coastal city living lab
CS	Cross-section
CSA	Case study area
CV	Coefficient of variation
DEFRA	Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs
DEM	Digital elevation models
DSAS	Digital Shoreline Analysis System
EBA	Ecosystem-based adaptation
ECP	Extended concentration pathway
EPA	Environment Protection Agency
EU	European Union

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
FTE	Full-time equivalent
GDP	Gross domestic product
GHG	Greenhouse gases
GIS	Geographic information system
GVA	Gross value added
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IRES	Intermittent and ephemeral river streams
NBS	Nature-based solutions
NPV	Net present value
PM	Particulate matter
RCP	Representative concentration pathways
SDR	Social discount rate
SRTP	Social rate of time preference
UK	United Kingdom
WP	Work package

BACKGROUND: ABOUT THE SCORE PROJECT

SCORE is a four-year EU-funded project aiming to increase climate resilience in European coastal cities.

The intensification of extreme weather events, coastal erosion and sea-level rise are major challenges to be urgently addressed by European coastal cities. The science behind these disruptive phenomena is complex, and advancing climate resilience requires progress in data acquisition, forecasting, and understanding of the potential risks and impacts for real-scenario interventions. The Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EBA) supported by smart technologies has potential to increase climate resilience of European coastal cities; however, it is not yet adequately understood and coordinated at European level.

SCORE outlines a co-creation strategy, developed via a network of 10 coastal city 'living labs' (CCLs), to rapidly, equitably and sustainably enhance coastal city climate resilience through EBA measures and sophisticated digital technologies.

The 10 CCLs involved in the project are: Sligo and Dublin, Ireland; Barcelona/Vilanova i la Geltrú, Benidorm and Basque Country, Spain; Oeiras, Portugal; Massa, Italy; Piran, Slovenia; Gdansk, Poland; Samsun, Turkey.

SCORE will establish an integrated coastal zone management framework for strengthening EBA and smart coastal city policies, creating European leadership in coastal city climate change adaptation in line with The Paris Agreement. It will provide innovative platforms to empower stakeholders' deployment of EBA solutions to increase climate resilience, business opportunities and financial sustainability of coastal cities.

The SCORE interdisciplinary team consists of 28 world-leading organisations from academia, local authorities, RPOs, and SMEs encompassing a wide range of skills including environmental science and policy, climate modelling, citizen

and social science, data management, coastal management and engineering, security and technological aspects of smart sensing research.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a deliverable of the SCORE project, funded under the European Union's (EU) Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003534.

The main aim of this document is to present the results of WP7's task 7.4, which focuses on the expert-based socio-economic assessment of adaptation interventions, with a particular emphasis on Ecosystem-based Adaptation (EBA). Specifically, it compares the costs and benefits of EBA measures in the four WP7 frontrunner CCLLs. The first case study compares a floodable park with an alternative river channelisation solution to mitigate flooding in the municipality of Errenteria (Oarsoaldea, Spain). The second case study evaluates intermittent river restoration for flood mitigation in Vilanova i la Geltrú (Spain), through an avoided cost approach. The third case analysis in Piran (Slovenia) assesses the use of historic water cisterns for drought periods versus alternative solutions. A fourth case, conducted in the same CCLL, focuses on the evaluation of the benefits of green spaces for heatwave mitigation. The fifth and final case study examines coastal erosion in Sligo County (Ireland), where it conducts a monetary valuation of the ecosystem services provided by beach and dune areas. Additionally, it presents a general comparison with the costs associated with dune management.

LINKS WITH OTHER PROJECT ACTIVITIES

This task is closely linked to previous WP7 tasks. It builds on **T7.1**, which provided a literature review of socioeconomic assessments of adaptation measures, including cost-benefits analyses (Deliverable¹ 7.1: Riera-Spiegelhalder et al., 2022); **T7.2**, which developed a methodological framework for the socio-economic assessment of adaptation measures to climate change, serving as the main guideline for the current analysis (D7.2: Etxebarria et al. 2022); and **T7.3**, which conducted a multicriteria analysis (MCA) of EBA options in the SCORE CCLLs, ultimately informing the selection of EBA measures for all case studies in **T7.4** (D7.3: Campos Rodrigues et al., 2024).

Moreover, the analysis is connected to **WPs 3** and **6**, particularly for the case studies of Oarsoaldea and Vilanova i la Geltrú, which serve as common frontrunners across the three WPs. The analysis for these CCLLs followed a sequential methodology, building on the results of the hydrological and hydraulic modelling from **WP3** (D3.8: Beden et al. 2024), and the hazard risk assessment conducted in **WP6** (D6.2: Figueiredo and Rangel, 2022; D6.4: Figueiredo et al. 2024). Moreover, for the Sligo case study, the analysis of future shoreline changes was supported by **WP3**. Finally, WP7 benefited from the outcomes of **WP1**, which provided valuable information on the primary climate hazards affecting the CCLLs, as well as from collaboration with **WP2**, particularly through the development of workshops with the CCLLs. These workshops, which were part of **T7.3** (MCA), enhanced WP7's understanding of the specific context of each frontrunner CCLL, thus refining the assessment approach used in **T7.4**. Results from this deliverable and the corresponding work in SCORE will be used for **Task 7.5** (Policy guidelines) and **WP9** (Communication and Dissemination).

It is important to acknowledge the significant contributions of the CCLL's representatives and stakeholders from Oarsoaldea, Vilanova i la Geltrú/Province of Barcelona, Piran, and Sligo, who provided valuable data and insights that

¹ This deliverable refers to other deliverables from SCORE's WPs. To simplify, deliverables will hereafter be labelled as 'D', followed by the number corresponding to the SCORE's WP and the sequential number of the deliverable within that WP.

helped better understand the local context, including the knowledge about past extreme events, the historical evolution of the study areas, among other aspects.

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1.INTRODUCTION

This report presents the results of five case studies conducted across the four WP7 CCLL frontrunners, each investigating different adaptation measures, with a particular emphasis on Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EBA) solutions. Figure 1 shows the locations of the study areas, followed by a summary of each case study.

Figure 1: Location of the study areas

Source: Adapted with minor changes from the original Human Geography Map available in <https://www.arcgis.com/apps/mapviewer/>.

Legend: 1. Errenteria, Oarsoaldea (Spain); 2. Vilanova i la Geltrú (Spain); 3. Piran (Slovenia); 4. Sligo (Ireland).

Floodable Park in Errenteria, Oarsoaldea (Spain)

The first case study led by NAIDER presents the results of evaluating a floodable park implemented in a neighbourhood of Errenteria, located in the *comarca* (or county) of Oarsoaldea (Basque Country, Spain), as compared to an alternative scenario in which concrete walls were constructed to channel the river and mitigate flooding problems in the area. The assessment of the floodable park of the municipality of Errenteria as a flooding mitigation measure is an *ex-post* evaluation, as the park was constructed in 2003. The analysis covers the period from 2003 to 2044, with 2024 serving as the baseline year for the annualisation of costs and benefits, using a Social Rate of Time Preference (SRTTP) of 3%, as referred in D7.2 (Extebarria et al., 2022). The study considers the climate scenarios associated with the Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP) 4.5 and RCP8.5² and estimates the Net Present

² RCPs include "four different 21st century pathways of GHG emissions and atmospheric concentrations, air pollutant emissions and land use (...) a stringent mitigation scenario (RCP2.6), two intermediate scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP6.0) and one scenario with very

Value (NPV) by calculating the implementation and maintenance costs, as well as the benefits, which are expressed as the avoided flood damage resulting from the EBA measure (D6.2: Figueiredo and Rangel, 2022; D6.4: Figueiredo et al. 2024). To test the robustness of the results, a sensitivity analysis is conducted with discount rates of 1% and 5%.

Restoration of an intermittent river in Vilanova i la Geltrú (Spain)

The second case study led by ENT focuses on intermittent river restoration as a strategy for flood mitigation in Vilanova i la Geltrú (Spain). This case study corresponds to an *ex-ante* evaluation of EBA measures in the intermittent river of Torrent de la Piera, comparing the implementation and maintenance costs with the benefits, which are quantified as avoided losses. The starting point of this CBA is the hydraulic and hydrologic flood risk modelling of the intermittent river Torrent de la Piera under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios, and 25 and 100 return periods (D3.8: Beden et al., 2024). The EBA measures analysed include raising the height of the right riverbank through the construction of a levee in the form of an earthen embankment, as well as the widening the riverbed channel in certain river cross-sections. The analysis covers the period from 2024 (Year 0 of the project) to 2065, spanning a 42-year time horizon, which aligns with the Oarsoaldea case study. Another common point is the estimation of Average Annual Losses (AAL) as calculated in D6.2 - "Exposure and Vulnerability Assessment Methodology Report" (Figueiredo and Rangel, 2022). Additionally, the NPV is calculated using a 3% social discount rate, with the robustness of the assessment further validated through sensitivity analysis at 1% and 5% discount rates, as well as by considering an increase in annual maintenance costs.

Restoration of historic water cisterns and the renovation of degraded areas into green spaces in Piran (Slovenia)

These analyses were led by ZRS Koper and Tero. The two organisations defined and shaped two sets of CBAs with special attention to align with the Piran CCLL objectives and the SCORE task for Piran EBA implementation (appointed to ZRS Koper).

Piran has a densely built town centre located on a peninsula at sea level. The buildings are placed closely together and are generally tall. The town is situated between the sea (north, west and south of the town) and the hilly areas (east of the town). The town is typically and traditionally paved with water-permeable cobblestones with minimal inclusion of public pocket parks and private palace gardens. During recent years, the cobblestone pavements have lost part of their permeability, because spaces between the stones have been covered with hard materials to make the surface more resistant and smoother. The beachfront is paved with asphalt concrete and cobblestones, and the shoreline is protected with rocks and boulders. The elevated part of the town, towards the historic Piranese defence walls, contains semi-private gardens and degraded green areas. The buildings in this part of town are smaller and are placed further apart.

Piran's CCLL first executed its MCA, and the prioritised EBAs were taken into the CBA analysis. The study area was defined as the historic town centre (tip of the peninsula) with specific areas defined upon stakeholder interaction and final MCA results, with winter coastal flooding and summer drought/heatwaves being the main hazards, with the latter being more feasible to openly discuss during the SCORE project. To combat these hazards, the proposed EBAs included the renovation of historical water cisterns (or Venetian water wells) to collect the rainwater and store it for the dry season, and the introduction of green spaces in the city (including small parks, but also rain gardens,

high GHG emissions (RCP8.5)" (IPCC, 2014). "RCP2.6: One pathway where radiative forcing peaks at approximately 3 W m^{-2} and then declines to be limited at 2.6 W m^{-2} in 2100 (the corresponding Extended Concentration Pathway, or ECP, has constant emissions after 2100); RCP4.5 and RCP6.0: Two intermediate stabilization pathways in which radiative forcing is limited at approximately 4.5 W m^{-2} and 6.0 W m^{-2} in 2100 (the corresponding ECPs have constant concentrations after 2150); RCP8.5: One high pathway which leads to $>8.5 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ in 2100 (the corresponding ECP has constant emissions after 2100 until 2150 and constant concentrations after 2250)." (IPCC, 2018).

green roofs and green walls). The first CBA assesses the costs and benefits of utilising historic water cisterns for water collection during drought periods, as compared to alternative solutions such as water tanks or water trucks in Piran (Slovenia). The second analysis conducts a CBA on the development of green spaces in the city and their role in mitigating the effects of heatwaves. While it is debatable whether historic water cisterns can be classified as a direct example of an EBA measure—since they do not focus on a specific ecosystem or green area—the fact that they harness natural resources like rainwater to meet the city's freshwater needs and incorporate natural filtration elements such as sand and gravel justifies their inclusion. Furthermore, to the best of our knowledge, these structures have not been analysed from the perspective put forth in this report.

Beach and dunes valuation and management in the context of coastal erosion in Sligo (Ireland)

The final case study, led by ATU with support from ENT, focuses on addressing coastal erosion in the beach and dune areas of Sligo County, Ireland, specifically at the beaches of Enniscrone, Strandhill, and Streedagh. Coastal dune management in Northwest Ireland has historically been employed to mitigate erosion, reduce storm damage, and safeguard coastal infrastructure. However, there is limited data on the effectiveness and economic value of dune management as an adaptation strategy. This case study incorporates shoreline evolution modelling and the mapping of ecological features, followed by a monetary valuation of ecosystem services provided by coastal dunes, such as coastal protection, carbon sequestration, and recreational benefits. The study then provides a general comparison between the benefits associated with these ecosystem services and the costs of dune management, while also outlining potential beach and dune management practices to address coastal erosion.

To **conclude**, the analyses presented in this report were grounded in the (CBA) methodology outlined in D7.2, titled “Methodological framework for the socio-economic assessment of adaptation measures to climate change” (Etxebarria et al. 2022). However, the case studies were given flexibility in adjusting their methodological approaches to suit specific objectives, data limitations, and other context-specific factors. Despite these variations, the case studies shared key similarities such as the influence of the prior T7.3 (Multi-criteria analysis – MCA) on the selection of the adaptation measures for the current task, or the use of 2024 as the baseline year for the analysis. The most similar case studies were Oarsoaldea and Vilanova i la Geltrú (Spain), both of which followed the same methodological approach, including hydraulic and hydrological modelling (from WP3), hazard risk assessment (from WP6), and the avoided losses approach for the estimation of benefits from EBAs. The two case studies conducted for Piran, along with the studies focused on Oarsoaldea and Vilanova i la Geltrú, followed a similar procedure, which included the sequential identification of costs and benefits, followed by their quantification and evaluation using Net Present Value (NPV), and the application of a similar sensitivity analysis. The analysis conducted for Sligo (Ireland) took a different approach, emphasizing the monetary valuation of key ecosystem services provided by coastal dunes in the context of beach erosion, followed by a general comparison with the current costs of dune management.

The remainder of this document is organised as follows. Sections 2-6 present a detailed analysis of each case study, including the main methodological steps and results. Section 7 provides general and specific conclusions for the case studies.

2.FLOODABLE PARK IN ERRETERIA, OARSOALDEA

2.1. Study area and research objectives

Oarsoaldea is a coastal county of the Basque Country (Spain). It is located in the north-east of the province of Gipuzkoa, and is made up by four municipalities: Errenteria, Lezo, Oiartzun and Pasaia (Figure 2). The county has an area of 116.25 km² and 71,759 inhabitants. Being geographically and geologically diverse, the area is notable for the maritime port of Pasaia, which holds considerable significance at the European level. Moreover, it features urban and commercial zones along the coastline, including buildings, roads, and other public and private infrastructures.

Figure 2: Map of Oarsoaldea

Source: Oarsoaldea CCLL.

This CBA focuses on the "Bakea" floodable park, located in the municipality of Errenteria (Figure 3). This park, constructed between 2002 and 2003, covers a total area of 52,766.80 m², including the river, and approximately 41,921.75 m² when excluding the riverbed. This analysis can be considered an *ex-post* evaluation of the "Bakea" park.

Figure 3: CBA case study area: Bakea floodable park

Source: Oarsoaldea CCLL.

The selection of the case study area has been made taking into consideration the following factors:

- **Climatic risks affecting the study area**

As detailed in D1.4 (Laíño Rebollido and Iglesias, 2023) and D.7.2 (Etxebarria et al., 2020), Oarsoaldea is susceptible to natural and climate-related hazards such as coastal floods, inland floods, landslides, coastal storm surges, and coastal erosion. These hazards directly impact both commercial and residential buildings, tourism, cultural heritage, as well as energy and transport networks. When evaluating coastal and land flooding in Oarsoaldea, it is important to recognize that these events are influenced by common factors such as storms with heavy rainfall, intense sea swells, and strong gusts of wind from the sea.

To effectively model and quantify climate risks, a specific study area with 5.8 km² was selected within the total surface of Oarsoaldea, encompassing the four municipalities that make up the region (Figure 4). This area allows for the quantification of the impact on the urban environment, which was considered the main land use typology to analyse and model. Additionally, since the main representative of the CCLL – the Agency of Economic Development of Oarsoaldea – lacks the full competencies (which lie with the municipalities themselves) and the budget to implement EBAs in the short to medium term, an area was chosen to allow for a comprehensive analysis of the potential EBAs to be implemented in the territory. Having selected a study area that encompasses the four municipalities will facilitate future decision making for public and private institutions in Oarsoaldea.

Thus, the final study area encompassed 5.8 km² and included the following key locations:

- The Bay and Port of Pasaia, along with its surrounding areas (hazard: coastal flooding).
- The Oiartzun River basin (hazard: terrestrial flooding).
- The historic centres of the four municipalities of Oarsoaldea (hazards: heat waves and flooding for those areas adjacent to the bay or river).

Figure 4: SCORE study area for the CCLL of Oarsoaldea

Source: D6.2 (Figueiredo and Rangel, 2022).

Given these reasons, the short-term hazard modelling carried out by WP3 (D3.8: Beden et al. 2024) focused on reducing impacts within the urban environment, with fluvial flooding identified as the primary hazard to address. Once the hazard was selected, a preliminary list of potential EBAs suitable for modelling was compiled.

- **Results of the multicriteria analysis (MCA) of EBAs in Oarsoaldea**

As part of task 7.3 (Participatory socio-economic assessment of EBA interventions), an MCA was conducted in Oarsoaldea in February 2023 involving local stakeholders. The main outcome of this analysis was a prioritised list of EBAs that were scored and weighted based on a previously selected criterion. The participatory assessment highlighted open green spaces, including parks and green strips, as the top priority EBAs in Oarsoaldea CCLL (D7.3: Campos Rodrigues et al. 2024). These results were subsequently taken into account when defining the study area for the CBA.

- **Modelling feasibility and expected impact of the EBAs**

Based on the climatic hazard selected and the prioritised EBA types, four EBA actions were considered for the study area. The selected measures had to meet the following criteria: they needed to be compatible with the hydraulic and hydrological modelling conducted by WP3 (D3.8: Beden et al. 2024); demonstrate potential for significant impacts in terms of climate risk reduction and the generation of other socioeconomic and environmental benefits; and to be feasible for implementation in the short to medium term. Based on these criteria, and with the goal of ensuring that the CBA results would be useful for policymakers' decision-making, it was decided to conduct the analysis on the existing Bakea floodable park.

Conducting purely *ex-post* evaluations for projects of this kind can be challenging, primarily because the asset has a long lifespan and is expected to continue providing benefits to society indefinitely, both in terms of flood risk reduction and the provision of ecosystem and social services. Although the park was constructed in 2003 and some benefits have already been realised, many more are anticipated to manifest in the future, particularly as climate change may increase the frequency and intensity of adverse weather events.

Thus, regarding the benefits, the evaluation resembles more of an intermediate analysis. However, in terms of costs it has *ex-post* characteristics, since the initial investment is now considered a "sunk cost" that cannot be recovered. Additionally, reversing the park's development would require significant effort and investment, further reinforcing its *ex-post* evaluation nature.

Conducting an analysis on a measure already in operation allows for more accurate data and estimates, both in terms of investment and maintenance costs, as well as in benefits. This is because the exact characteristics of the area are well known, enabling a more precise and realistic assessment.

From an operational perspective, the analysis also enables an assessment of the suitability of applying this methodology to future measures that are already in place. It will also help to prepare for, and address, the challenges that may arise in obtaining real data. One of the factors that can contribute to discrepancies between *ex-ante* and *interim* or *ex-post* evaluations of the same project is the difference between the projected investment and maintenance costs and those that are ultimately incurred (Boardman et al., 1994). In the case of "Bakea" park, the investment and some maintenance costs can be drawn from previous years, allowing for a more accurate comparison. Therefore, conducting an analysis of this park and comparing it with other *ex-ante* evaluations (such as in the case of Vilanova i la Geltrú) provides valuable insights into this issue and other aspects that may arise when evaluating climate adaptation projects at different stages of their life cycle. This experience will offer valuable lessons

for future evaluations and the implementation of more effective strategies in managing risks and maximizing ecosystem benefits.

2.2. Methodology

Before conducting the evaluation, it is necessary to establish the framework and approach for the *ex-post* analysis. This includes defining the scenarios considered, setting the time horizon and financial parameters, and outlining the methods used to assess both benefits and costs.

2.2.1. Counterfactual scenario

Counterfactuals are used in *ex-post* evaluations to establish what would have happened in the absence of the initiative. This comparison helps to accurately attribute benefits and costs to the initiative rather than to external factors.

The analysis evaluated the societal costs and benefits of the "Bakea" floodable park by comparing it to a counterfactual scenario where the area was developed as an urban zone, similar to the surrounding neighbourhoods. In this hypothetical scenario, the proposed changes would involve removing most of the riparian vegetation and grass, constructing walls to canalize the river, and urbanising the area. The surface would be covered with concrete or similar materials, closely resembling the characteristics of the neighbouring urbanised areas. This scenario is designed to reflect a plausible alternative development that could have occurred, allowing for a realistic comparison of the flood mitigation benefits provided by the park.

2.2.2. Identification of costs and benefits

a) Costs

The "Bakea" floodable park project involved an initial investment, as well as ongoing maintenance costs, to transform the area into a resilient public space capable of mitigating flood risks.

Initial investment

This investment covers several key actions, including the reconfiguration of existing pathways and infrastructure throughout the park, the construction of new access routes to enhance connectivity for residents, and the development of designated floodable zones. Additionally, it includes the removal of old fencing, installation of new perimeter boundaries, and the landscaping and stabilisation of slopes around the park to support ecological resilience. The budget also accounts for the renewal of park amenities, such as seating, lighting, and recreational facilities, along with replanting efforts and soil restoration to reinforce the natural landscape and support biodiversity within the floodable park area.

As the "Bakea" floodable park is an existing measure, data on initial investments have been sourced from the actual budget expenditures provided by the local authority. Specifically, the initial investment includes costs associated with urban development, earthworks, water distribution and sewerage networks, irrigation systems, landscaping, and the installation of sports facilities and urban furniture.

Maintenance costs

Maintenance costs for green areas and parks can vary significantly due to various factors, including climate, seasonal changes, the type of vegetation involved, and specific location requirements (Lee et al., 2010). Maintenance activities

typically include essential tasks like pruning, planting, fertilising and insecticide application, cleaning, irrigation or repairing urban furniture, among others.

These activities highlight the complexity of managing park maintenance, as each task must be carefully scheduled to meet environmental requirements and to optimise resources effectively. Considering the natural complexity of park maintenance, real data has been used to estimate the maintenance cost of “Bakea” park.

The annual maintenance budget for gardens and parks in the municipality of Errenteria was allocated based on the total square meters of green spaces. Data from 2021 was used, as it provided the most accurate information regarding the extent of parks and gardens in the municipality. Using this data, the total budget was divided by the municipality’s total park and garden area to calculate the cost per square meter per year. This €/m² rate was then multiplied by the area of "Bakea" Park to determine its annual maintenance cost.

b) Benefits

Before the project was implemented, the area where "Bakea" Park now stands lacked effective flood management, leaving buildings, railways and residents in Oarsoaldea vulnerable to flood damage. With the creation of the floodable park, this area now provides a natural buffer against flooding, reducing the risk of water damage to surrounding structures and enhancing safety for residents. As a result, "Bakea" Park offers a significant benefit in terms of avoided flood damages, protecting valuable assets and population and minimizing disruptions for the community. To quantify the avoided flood damage in both physical (flood extension and depth) and economic (monetary losses) terms, the analysis first involved the development of hydraulic and hydrological models, followed by a flood risk assessment. Both steps are explained in more detail below.

Hydraulic and hydrological modelling

The hazard scenarios used in estimating avoided losses were developed as part of WP3. The D3.8 (Beden et al., 2024) focuses on the development and application of "last mile" hydraulic models that utilize climatic data derived from hydrological downscaling, sea level, and wave models developed in Task 3.2 and detailed in deliverables D3.3 (Brandini et al., 2022a) and D3.4 (Brandini et al., 2022b). These models operate at an urban scale, leveraging digital terrain models and high-precision spatial data to simulate key hazard scenarios with varying probabilities, as established by statistical tools from Task 3.3. The flood hazard modelling within WP3 generated detailed hazard maps for each CCLL, including Oarsoaldea, across five climate scenarios: historical baseline, RCP4.5 (2015-2065 and 2045-2095), and RCP8.5 (2015-2065 and 2045-2095). In the case of fluvial flooding, two scenarios were assessed—one with and one without “Bakea Park”. The dataset encompasses flood maps across six return periods (5, 25, 50, 100, 200, and 500 years), totalling 60 fluvial and 30 coastal flood hazard maps per CCLL. These maps are structured as raster grids, which delineate flood extents and depths across study areas. For Oarsoaldea, maps have a resolution of 1m x 1m. These datasets were provided in D3.7 (Brandini et al., 2023) and further described in D3.8 (Beden et al., 2024).

Figure 5 provides an illustrative example of the hydrological modelling conducted by WP3. It compares the real and the counterfactual-built up scenarios, highlighting the difference in flood extension.

Figure 5: Illustrative example of real versus counterfactual scenarios

Source: Oarsoaldea CCLL.

Legend: The red areas highlighted in the figure on the right represent the marginal flood extension associated with the counterfactual scenario, as compared to the actual scenario.

Flood risk assessment

To economically value the avoided losses, this CBA integrates insights from the work conducted by WP6, notably in D6.4 (Figueiredo et al. 2024), which provides a comprehensive flood risk assessment for the CCLLs, including Oarsoaldea. This analysis quantifies avoided losses by estimating the potential economic damages to buildings and infrastructure and affected population across various return periods and climate scenarios. Building on the hazard scenarios developed in WP3, the economic valuation of these avoided damages relies on a structured approach that considers the following factors, which is more detailed in D6.2 (Figueiredo and Rangel, 2022) and D6.4 (Figueiredo et al. 2024):

- **Asset exposure and vulnerability data:** Using high-resolution exposure data for assets at risk, such as buildings, roads, and railways, the analysis assigns economic values to each asset class. Vulnerability models, specific to each type of asset, estimate the relationship between flood intensity and potential damage, allowing for a refined calculation of economic losses.
- **Damage functions and replacement costs:** For each asset type, damage functions correlate floodwater depth with estimated physical damage. These functions are combined with the replacement costs of assets to derive potential losses in monetary terms, reflecting the extent of flood damage under both mitigated and unmitigated scenarios.
- **Avoided loss calculation:** By comparing scenarios with and without Bakea Park's flood mitigation function, the analysis identifies the reduction in potential losses attributable to the park. This difference, or "avoided loss", represents the economic benefit provided by the park's flood mitigation capacity.
- **Climate scenario comparison:** To address future uncertainty, the avoided loss calculations are repeated across various climate scenarios and time horizons, illustrating how Bakea Park's mitigation effectiveness may vary under different climate trajectories.

Given the infrequent nature of extreme flood events and the variability in potential damages per event, it is essential to translate flood risk reduction into yearly monetary terms. This is achieved through the calculation of Avoided Annual Losses (AAL), which provides a consistent measure of the economic benefits from flood mitigation efforts over time.

The replacement costs are used to estimate the economic value of avoided damages and are set relative to 2021 values. The AAL calculated in this analysis reflects only direct costs, specifically the expenses required to repair or replace damaged assets. Indirect costs, such as business interruptions or broader economic impacts, were not included in the CBA. This conservative approach ensures that the analysis remains focused on tangible repair and replacement costs, acknowledging that the total risk may be higher if indirect costs were considered.

The analysis utilizes two distinct timeframes for flood risk assessment: the historical baseline, spanning 1956 to 2005, and a future projection from 2015 to 2065. For the interim period of 2005 to 2014, the historical baseline scenario is applied to maintain consistency across the assessment.

Figures 6 and 7 present an example of the monetary results derived from the hazard assessment carried out by WP6, including the analysis with and without the implementation of EBA measure. The results show that the expected AAL are lower when EBA is considered, demonstrating its effectiveness in reducing flood damage.

Figure 6: Annual exceedance probability curves for economic losses caused by fluvial flooding (with and without EBA) in Oarsoaldea

Source: D6.4 (Figueiredo et al., 2024).

Note: The results are expressed in 2021 price terms.

Figure 7: Expected average annual losses (AAL) due to fluvial flooding for each climate scenario and EBA situation

Source: D6.4 (Figueiredo et al., 2024).

Note: The results are expressed in 2021 price terms.

2.2.3. Temporal horizon

Determining a time horizon for infrastructure projects like parks presents a challenge, given the uncertainty surrounding their useful life and the environmental and social services they provide. As highlighted in D7.2 (Etxebarria et al. 2020), projects with long-term societal and environmental impacts benefit from extended time horizons in evaluations. A longer horizon allows such projects to be comparable to traditional infrastructure (O'Mahony, 2021), which often shows marketable short-term returns but may not account for negative externalities. However, while long horizons can be beneficial, excessively extended periods introduce considerable uncertainty, particularly when benefits are derived from probabilistic models that inherently carry risk.

In this context, the temporal scope should ideally align with the reliability of predictive models. For instance, flood hazard models in this project extend to 2065, making a timeframe from 2024 to 2065 appropriate for other *ex-ante* evaluations carried out in the SCORE project. This 42-year period balances long-term foresight with model reliability.

In our case, as we are conducting an *ex-post* evaluation, we have adopted a timeframe from 2003 to 2044, reflecting both historical and projected climate scenarios from 2015 to 2065. Since the historical scenario covers the period from 1956 to 2005, the average values from both the historical and projected (2015-2065) scenarios are used to estimate values for the interim period of 2006-2014, thus ensuring continuity in the data. This approach enables us to use AAL data from both historical and future scenarios, providing a comprehensive assessment that considers both past and foreseeable climate impacts without overextending the model's predictive capacity.

2.2.4. Discount rate

As detailed in D7.2 (Etxebarria et al. 2020), a Social Discount Rate (SDR) has been used to account for the long-term, intergenerational benefits and costs associated with the floodable park. For this evaluation, a discount rate of 3% was selected, consistent with the Social Rate of Time Preference (SRTP) approach. The SRTP considers the trade-offs society is willing to make between present and future consumption, emphasizing the well-being of both current and future generations. This rate is supported by literature, including guidelines from "The Green Book" by HM Treasury, which suggests a rate of 3.5% for the UK, and studies indicating European rates between 3% and 5.5% (Evans & Sezer, 2005). The choice of a 3% rate reflects an alignment with these best practices and ethical considerations, ensuring that the evaluation captures the full scope of benefits and costs over the project's long-term horizon. Moreover, the sensitivity analysis conducted in this CBA will simulate discount rates of 1% and 5% to test the robustness of the results.

2.2.5. Standardisation of monetary values

The monetary value of benefits and costs are set relative to different years. Since the CBA is conducted in 2024, it is necessary to adjust those values to reflect 2024 values. Continuing with the methodology used in D6.2 (Figueiredo and Rangel, 2022), the value update was made by combining the mean of two alternative approaches: 1) by multiplying the original values by the ratio of Spain's GDP per capita for 2023 and for the year to which the original value refers. The ratio of GDPs reflects the change in the price level across the two years; 2) by multiplying the original values by the ratio of Spain's Construction Cost Index (CCI) for 2023 and for the year to which the original value refers. Both GDP per capita and CCI data were obtained from Eurostat³. The year 2023 was selected to reflect the most recent complete year, capturing the finalised price levels incurred in the economy, which could subsequently

³ Main GDP aggregates per capita:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/nama_10_pc_custom_14043808/default/table

CCI data: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/sts_copi_a_custom_14044449/default/table

be applied at the beginning of 2024.⁴ Using constant prices ensures comparability with other investment projects. Additionally, inflation-driven price increases do not necessarily represent a true rise in the value of goods. Instead, they may merely reflect changes in the monetary unit of measurement over time.

2.2.6. Evaluation of costs and benefits

The CBA was conducted based on the estimation of the NPV (Haer et al., 2017). In equation [1], B denotes the accumulated benefits (present value) over the entire period ($T=42$ years), reflecting the reduction in the AAL achieved through adaptation; C represents the total implementation and maintenance costs of the interventions. Equation [2] offers a more detailed breakdown, where M refers to maintenance costs and I_0 to initial investment costs at time $t = 0$.

$$NPV = PV(B) - PV(C) \quad [1]$$

$$NPV = \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{(AAL r_t)}{(1+r)^t} - \left(\sum_{t=1}^T \frac{(M_t)}{(1+r)^t} + I_0 \right) \quad [2]$$

2.3. Results

2.3.1. Initial investment and maintenance costs

A total of 590.1 thousand euros was invested in the construction of 'Bakea' Park

The initial investment for the construction of "Bakea" park totalled €590,118, encompassing a variety of components essential to its development and functionality. A breakdown of this investment reveals a prioritisation of urbanisation and landscaping efforts, along with the necessary infrastructure for park utility and accessibility.

The largest portion of the budget, €241,572 (41% of total investment), was allocated to "urbanisation", underscoring the extensive groundwork required to transform the area into a functional and accessible public space.

"Other Expenses" amount to €94,221, representing 16% of the total budget and reflecting a notable allocation for miscellaneous or auxiliary costs. This category includes essential items such as project management, planning fees, permits, and other logistical expenses critical to successful project execution. The relatively high proportion of this cost category underscores the importance of accounting for unforeseen or indirect costs to ensure smooth implementation. This aspect is particularly important in *ex-post* analysis, where such expenses are more readily identifiable, whereas in *ex-ante* assessments, they may be challenging to accurately predict.

Another important component for the construction of the park is the aesthetic and environmental function, since landscaping received €73,711. Representing 12% of the budget, this investment reflects the commitment to develop green spaces that contribute to the park's flood resilience and recreational appeal. Landscaping not only improves the park's visual appeal but also enhances its ecological role as a floodable area, aiding in water absorption and soil stabilisation.

⁴ Although the baseline year is set to 2024, all financial projections will be based on 2023 price levels, as these were the most current data available at the time the analysis was conducted.

Public lighting and earthworks were allocated similar portions of the budget, each representing 8% of the total investment, with €50,093 and €44,930, respectively. The lighting network enhances safety by ensuring well-lit access during evening hours, while earthworks play a crucial role in shaping the landscape to effectively manage water flow.

An additional €34,257 (6% of total investment) was dedicated to irrigation systems to maintain the park's vegetation. Urban furniture, with an allocation of €24,838 (4%), improves usability and visitor comfort by providing seating, trash receptacles, and signage. Sewage networks, water distribution networks, and sports facilities received smaller allocations, each accounting for 1% of the total investment.

Total annual maintenance costs of 101.7 thousand euros for "Bakea" Park

The maintenance cost for "Bakea" Park is set at €101,696 annually, representing 17% of the park's initial investment. This allocation covers essential upkeep activities necessary to preserve the park's dual role as a floodable area and a recreational space. This level of annual maintenance funding might seem relatively high compared to typical costs associated with other ecosystem-based solutions. However, the park's specific requirements as a multifunctional green space justify this investment, as regular maintenance is necessary for sustaining its environmental functionality and recreational appeal over the long term.

Table 1 summarises the investment and maintenance costs associated with the Bakea Park.

Table 1: Initial investment and maintenance costs of Bakea Park

Concept	Investment	
	Euros	% over total initial investment
Urbanisation	241,572 €	41%
Other expenses	94,221 €	16%
Landscaping	73,711 €	12%
Public lighting	50,093 €	8%
Earthworks	44,930 €	8%
Irrigation systems	34,257 €	6%
Urban furniture	24,838 €	4%
Sewage networks	13,913 €	2%
Water distribution networks	8,190 €	1%
Sports facilities	4,394 €	1%
Total initial investment	590,119 €	100%

Maintenance cost	Euros/year	% of initial investment
	101,696 €	17%

Note: Values are adjusted to reflect 2023 real prices.

2.3.2. Avoided annual losses

The results presented in this section provide an overview of the avoided losses across key infrastructure categories—buildings, roads, and railways—under both historical and projected climate scenarios. Avoided losses are presented for distinct time periods (2003-2005, 2006-2014, and 2015-2044) across moderate (RCP4.5) and severe (RCP8.5) climate conditions.

Avoided infrastructure losses range between approximately 201.9 and 303.2 thousand euros

Summing all infrastructure types, the total avoided AAL is highest in the historical scenario at €303,174. This total avoided AAL decreases over time in projected scenarios, particularly under RCP4.5, where it falls from €252,511

(2006-2014) to €201,848 (2015-2044). Under RCP8.5, the decline is less significant, with values of €266,215 (2006-2014) and €229,257 (2015-2044), reflecting the sustained risk and importance of mitigation in more extreme climate conditions.

For buildings, avoided losses are the highest, with a value of €284,270 in the historical period (2003-2005), decreasing in future scenarios, particularly under RCP4.5, where they drop to €192,687 in the 2015-2044 period, and less sharply under RCP8.5, reaching €215,777 over the same period. For roads, the AAL remains relatively stable, with slight fluctuations: in the historical scenario, it is €11,971, decreasing to €6,575 under RCP4.5 (2015-2044), while slightly increasing to €12,414 under RCP8.5, suggesting greater damages in more severe climate conditions. For railways, the AAL shows a more pronounced decline, starting at €6,933 in the historical period and significantly reducing under RCP4.5 to €2,586 in 2015-2044, and even further to €1,065 under RCP8.5 (Table 2).

Table 2: Avoided average annual losses of Bakea Park

Concept	Category	Historical	RCP 4.5		RCP 8.5	
		2003-2005	2006-2014	2015-2044	2006-2014	2015-2044
Average annual losses (AAL) – without adaptation	Buildings	3,690,039 €	3,731,445 €	3,772,851 €	3,745,502 €	3,800,966 €
	Roads	63,831 €	63,835 €	63,840 €	65,394 €	66,958 €
	Railway	218,957 €	218,778 €	218,599 €	217,983 €	217,009 €
	Total	3,972,827 €	4,014,058 €	4,055,289 €	4,028,880 €	4,084,933 €
Average annual losses (AAL) – with adaptation	Buildings	3,405,769 €	3,492,966 €	3,580,164 €	3,495,479 €	3,585,189 €
	Roads	51,860 €	54,562 €	57,265 €	53,202 €	54,544 €
	Railway	212,024 €	214,018 €	216,013 €	213,984 €	215,944 €
	Total	3,669,653 €	3,761,547 €	3,853,441 €	3,762,665 €	3,855,676 €
Avoided average annual losses (AAL) – with adaptation	Buildings	284,270 €	238,478 €	192,687 €	250,023 €	215,777 €
	Roads	11,971 €	9,273 €	6,575 €	12,193 €	12,414 €
	Railway	6,933 €	4,760 €	2,586 €	3,999 €	1,065 €
	Total	303,174 €	252,511 €	201,848 €	266,215 €	229,257 €

Note: Values are adjusted to reflect 2023 real prices.

2.3.3. Cost-benefit results

Taking into account the avoided average annual losses (AAL) for infrastructure over the analysed period and after discounting the cash flows, Table 3 presents the Net Present Value (NPV) for the implementation of "Bakea" Park as a flood mitigation measure under climate change scenarios RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 for the period 2003-2045.

The total benefits amount to €10,530,385 under RCP4.5 and €11,441,025 under RCP8.5, indicating a substantial economic impact. With an initial investment of €1,130,728 and maintenance costs totalling €4,661,514 over the period of analysis, the project yields positive NPVs of €4,738,143 for RCP4.5 and €5,648,783 for RCP8.5.

Buildings represent the largest share of avoided losses, with €9,987,573 and €10,754,718 for RCP4.5 and RCP8.5, respectively. These results highlight the role of the park in protecting the built environment. Avoided losses for roads (€369,441 under RCP4.5 and €563,457 under RCP8.5) and railways (€173,371 under RCP4.5 and €122,851 under RCP8.5) are comparatively smaller but still contribute to the overall positive impact. The higher NPV under the RCP8.5 scenario reflects the increased benefits of flood mitigation in more severe climate conditions, supporting the value of "Bakea" Park as an effective long-term adaptation measure.

Table 3: Estimated NPV for the Bakea Park

Concept		RCP4.5	RCP8.5
Costs (present value)	Initial investment		-1,130,728 €
	Total maintenance costs		-4,661,514 €
	Total		-5,792,242 €
Benefits (in total avoided losses; present value)	Buildings	9,987,573 €	10,754,718 €
	Roads	369,441 €	563,457 €
	Railway	173,371 €	122,851 €
	Total	10,530,385 €	11,441,025 €
NPV		4,738,143 €	5,648,783 €

Note: Values are adjusted to reflect 2023 real prices.

2.3.4. Sensitivity analysis

Table 4 summarises the NPV for the "Bakea" Park under different discount rates (1%, 3%, and 5%) and climate change scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5), along with the Coefficient of Variation (CV) to assess variability across discount rates.

The sensitivity analysis, conducted with varying discount rates, yields consistently positive NPVs for the implementation of "Bakea" Park. Under RCP4.5, the NPVs range from approximately €4,432,446 to €5,304,860, while for RCP8.5, the values range from €5,354,483 to €6,247,937. These results demonstrate the robustness of the project's economic viability across different discount rate assumptions and climate scenarios. The relatively low CVs in both scenarios (6–7%) indicate that the project's economic performance is robust across different discount rates, with slightly higher NPVs observed under RCP8.5 due to greater flood risks and corresponding benefits of mitigation.

Table 4: Sensitivity analysis using different discount rates

Climate change scenarios	NPV			Coefficient of variation (CV; %)
	1%	3%	5%	
RCP 4.5	4,432,446 €	4,738,143 €	5,304,860 €	7%
RCP 8.5	5,354,483 €	5,648,783 €	6,247,937 €	6%

Note: Values are adjusted to reflect 2023 real prices.

3. RESTORATION OF AN INTERMITTENT RIVER IN VILANOVA I LA GELTRÚ

3.1. Study area and research objectives

Intermittent and ephemeral river streams (IRES), as their designation suggests, do not maintain a continuous flow of water, in contrast to perennial rivers (Datry et al., 2018; Gutiérrez-Jurado et al., 2019). Nevertheless, IRES play an important role in delivering a range of ecosystem services, including the provision of resources (e.g., food, water), regulation and maintenance (e.g., carbon sequestration, flood protection), and cultural services (e.g., aesthetic value, recreational opportunities) (Datry et al., 2018; Jorda-Capdevila et al., 2021).

With climate change and the likely increase in extreme precipitation (Lee et al., 2023), the frequency and severity of riverine floods are expected to rise, leading to significant damage. In some urban areas, rapid development has reduced floodplain spaces near IRES, limiting their capacity to act as flood buffers. Consequently, IRES are becoming more constrained by surrounding residential, commercial, and industrial areas, further restricting options for flood adaptation.

This CBA focuses on an urban intermittent river named Torrent de la Piera, in the city of Vilanova i la Geltrú (Barcelona, Spain). Vilanova i la Geltrú is a coastal city of the Mediterranean basin, south to Barcelona. The municipality has an extension of 33.99 km² and a population of 68,768 inhabitants (Idescat, 2024). The city is intersected by three intermittent rivers: Torrent de la Pastera and Torrent de la Piera in the northwest, and Torrent de Sant Joan in the southeast. Due to its hydrological structure and proximity to the sea, Vilanova i la Geltrú is highly vulnerable to flooding. The Torrent de la Piera does not maintain a consistent flow throughout the year, remaining dry for much of the time. This stream is connected to the sea at its east end, and Torrent de la Terrosa and Santa Magdalena in the north. Moreover, it is located within an urban area, in between a residential area and a road known as 'Ronda Europa'. This road is one of the main connections between the east and the north end of the city, with an underpass section beneath the railway. This study focuses on a 2.85 km stretch of the stream, which has an elevation profile ranging, from north to south, from 22 to 0 meters. For the purpose of the analysis, the study area was divided into six subsections (with corresponding river cross-sections), primarily separated by road intersections. Figures 8 and 9 illustrate the study area.

Figure 8: Map of the study area in Vilanova i la Geltrú

Source: Adapted with changes from Mapchart.net and Visor SigPac: <https://siapac.mapama.gob.es/feqa/visor/>.

Legend: The map in the right corresponds to the municipality of Vilanova i la Geltrú. The black line traces the segment of the 'Torrent de la Piera' that is considered in the analysis.

Figure 9: Study area segmentation in Vilanova i la Geltrú

Source: Own elaboration using a satellite image from Google Earth.

Legend: 'CS' refers to cross-sections, which are marked along the segment of the Torrent de la Piera analysed in this study (indicated by the blue dashed line).

During past periods of intense rainfall, the water has risen over the stream's right bank (oriented north-south), spilling into adjacent areas such as road and sidewalk. These flooding episodes interrupt traffic and pedestrian movements, impeding the connection between north and east ends of the city (see an example of a flooding event in Figure 10). Climate change could lead to a higher frequency and severity of these effects. To address this issue, a combination of two EBA measures is proposed in some sections of the stream: i) Raising the elevation of the right riverbank by constructing a levee in the form of an earthen embankment; and ii) Widening the riverbed channel. The implementation of the second measure also involves riverbed reprofiling (or adjustments in the riverbed elevation), while preserving the gradual descent from the top to the bottom of the stream.

The previous measures correspond to modifications in the channel morphology, primarily aimed at increasing flood conveyance capacity, and are designed following nature-based engineering requirements. Its selection was inspired by a Multicriteria Analysis (MCA) workshop celebrated in Vilanova i la Geltrú, in March 2023 (for more information see "D7.3 - Results from the participatory socio-economic assessment of EBA interventions"; Campos Rodrigues et al., 2024). In this session, local and regional stakeholders were invited to prioritise EBA measures to alleviate flooding episodes in the lower part of Torrent de la Piera, which was identified as the critical area. This section is smaller in size than the one considered in the CBA, measuring approximately 240 meters.

Figure 10: Flooding episode at Ronda Europa near the underpass section beneath the railway (Vilanova i la Geltrú, June 2018)

Source: Aigües de Vilanova i la Geltrú.

To summarise, this study conducts an *ex-ante* CBA with two main objectives: i) Identify potential combinations of EBA measures and assess their effectiveness in mitigating inland flooding under various climate change scenarios; and ii) Analyse the costs and benefits associated with the different combinations tested, particularly by comparing implementation and maintenance costs with the potential reduction in average annual losses (AAL) from flooding.

3.2. Methodology

The following subsections present the main methodological elements of the *ex-ante* analysis conducted for the CCLL of Vilanova i la Geltrú. This includes the adaptation scenarios, identification of benefits and costs, temporal horizon, discount rates, standardisation of economic values, and the approach taken for the evaluation of costs and benefits.

3.2.1. Adaptation scenarios

The CBA focuses on comparing the following scenarios:

- **Business-as-usual (BAU):** no intervention, and consideration of climate change scenarios RCP4.5 and RCP8.5.
- **Adaptation scenario 1:** widening the riverbed and raising the height of the right riverbank with a levee at specific river cross-sections, while considering the RCP4.5 climate scenario.
- **Adaptation scenario 2:** widening the riverbed and raising the height of the right riverbank with a levee at specific river cross-sections, while considering the RCP8.5 climate scenario.

3.2.2. Identification of costs and benefits

a) Costs

The interventions were carried out across three sections of Torrent de la Piera, specifically in some cross-sections of zones 2, 3 and 5 previously presented in Figure 9. The implementation of the adaptation measures involves both initial investments and maintenance costs, which are outlined below.

Initial investment

The analysis examined various types of investment costs associated with the selected measures, focusing particularly on the actions presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Actions considered in the implementation of the adaptation measures in Torrent de la Pera

	Intervention #1: Riverbed widening combined with the construction of a river levee (zone 2)	Intervention #2: Riverbed widening (zone 3)	Intervention #3: Construction of a river levee (zone 5)
Land clearing	■	■	■
Excavation for riverbed widening	■	■	□
Loading, transport, and disposal of non-usable extracted material	■	■	□
Loading and transportation of extractable material from intervention No2 to No3	□	□	■
Dispersal of the extracted material for river levee construction	■	□	■
Land resurfacing for river levee development	■	□	■
Land resurfacing for riverbank consolidation	□	■	□
Riverbank consolidation with geotechnique (live slope grid)	■	■	■
Riverbank/levee greening (geofibre and vegetation)	■	■	■

Maintenance costs

In this study, annual maintenance costs are assumed to be 1% of the initial investment. Nevertheless, the sensitivity analysis will also explore a 2% rate to assess variations. These values are consistent with those implemented in Amadio et al. (2022) and Bockarjova et al. (2022), the latter specifically for blue nature-based solutions (NBS).

b) Benefits

Following the same procedure developed in the Oarsoaldea case study, this CBA relied on the prior development of hydraulic and hydrological models by WP3, followed by a flood risk assessment by WP6, to estimate the avoided flood damage resulting from the implementation of EBA measures. The avoided losses were considered the primary benefit of the adaptation interventions.

Hydraulic and hydrological modelling

The estimation of the flood risk in the study area for the BAU and adaptation scenarios was based on the work developed by WP3 on regional and local projections. Using the 1D and 2D hydraulic software model HEC-RAS (USACE, 2018) it was simulated the flood propagation related to a land river discharge and the effect of storm surge from the sea (Beden et al., 2024). All methodological details, related to the boundary conditions, modelling details, including Digital Elevation Models (DEM) resolution and base flow data are described in D3.8 – “User document for the short-term hazard modelling” (Beden et al., 2024).

The historical period 1956-2005 was considered as the baseline year. Flooding simulations with and without EBA interventions were run for different return periods (5, 25, 50, 100, 200, and 500 years) and climate scenarios (RCP4.5, RCP8.5) for the periods 2015-2065 and 2045-2095. For the purpose of the CBA, the selected future period was 2015-2065, to minimise uncertainty regarding long-term scenarios and the effectiveness of EBA measures. To test and model the proposed interventions, flooding simulations were conducted and analysed for the six subsections of the study area. This procedure facilitated the identification of the most critical areas and the selection of the most effective solutions to reduce flood depth and extent, while ensuring that interventions were applied selectively throughout the study area. Table 6 presents the description of the EBA measures ultimately selected, while Figure

11 displays an example of flooding simulations, particularly for RCP4.5 and return periods of 25 and 100 years, both with and without adaptation. The results indicate a significant reduction in the extent of flooding with adaptation.

Table 6: Selected EBA interventions within the study area of Vilanova i la Geltrú

Specifications	Illustrative example
Measure No1: Riverbed widening along with the increase in the height of the right riverbank by constructing a levee in the form of an earthen embankment	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Zone 2 (intervention in cross-sections 45-38; no intervention in CS 46). - Covered length of 360 m. - Riverbed widening of 2 meters in the right bank. This action also involves riverbed reprofiling, while preserving the gradual descent from top to the bottom of the stream. - 2-meter rise on the right bank, with a slope of 63.43° and 3.5 meters wide. - When determining the necessary volume for riverbank heightening, a shrinkage factor of 25% percent was considered. This means that the volume of soil obtained from the extracted area corresponds to 125% of the new riverbank volume. This factor accounts for compaction and other losses (Golder Associates and Associated Engineering, 2003). 	<div style="text-align: center;"> <p><i>Transversal view</i></p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p><i>Frontal view of the riverbank</i></p> </div> <div style="margin-top: 10px;"> <p>1) Riverbed widened by 2 meters to the right (soil volume removed: ~3,778 m³).</p> <p>2) Right riverbank heightening by 2 meters (required volume of soil extraction: ~2,250 m³).</p> <p>Areas:</p> <p>A: 720 m²</p> <p>B: 792 m²</p> <p>C: 540 m²</p> </div>
Measure No2: Riverbed widening	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Zone 3 (intervention in cross-sections 36-32; no intervention in CS 37 and 31-28). - Covered length of 190 m. - Riverbed widening of 2 meters in the left riverbank. This action also involves riverbed reprofiling, while preserving the gradual descent from top to the bottom of the stream. 	<div style="text-align: center;"> <p><i>Transversal view</i></p> </div> <div style="margin-top: 10px;"> <p>1) Riverbed widened by 2 meters to the right (soil volume removed: ~3,495 m³).</p> </div>
Measure No3: Raising the elevation of the right riverbank by constructing a levee in the form of an earthen embankment	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Zone 5 (intervention in cross-sections 19-13; no intervention in CS17 as it is located below the railway bridge). - Covered length of 250 m. - 2-meter rise on the right bank, with a slope of 63.43° and 3.5 meters wide. - The volume of soil obtained from the extracted area corresponds to 125% of the new riverbank volume (shrinking factor of 25%) (Golder Associates and Associated Engineering, 2003). 	<div style="text-align: center;"> <p><i>Transversal view</i></p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p><i>Frontal view of the riverbank</i></p> </div> <div style="margin-top: 10px;"> <p>1) Right riverbank heightening by 2 meters (required volume of soil extraction: ~1,563 m³).</p> <p>Areas:</p> <p>A: 550 m²</p> <p>B: 375 m²</p> </div>

Figure 11: Hazard maps for river flood, return periods 25 and 100 years, with and without EBA implementation and scenarios RCP4.5 and RCP8.5

Source: Beden et al. 2024.

Flood risk assessment

The estimation of the hazard risk was undertaken by combining three components: i) the probability of occurrence of negative consequences and economic losses because of the combination of hazard (flood scenarios); ii) exposure (geographical location of people, buildings, roads and railway); and iii) vulnerability (combination of flood intensities, physical impacts, and economic losses). A complete explanation of the methodology can be found in D6.2 – “The Exposure and Vulnerability Assessment Methodology Report” (Figueiredo and Rangel, 2022). The combination of these three components (hazard, exposure, and vulnerability) made it possible to estimate Average Annual Losses (AAL) for each hazard scenario and type of exposed elements.

Gridded maps on a 100m x 100m resolution showed aggregate loss metrics at urban scale. For a return period of 100 years, and RCP8.5 in the period 2045-2095, it was estimated the spatial distribution of population, and the average annual losses, due to a fluvial flood (D6.4: Figueiredo et al., 2024). From this, fluvial flood risk curves were derived with and without the implementation of the measures described in Table 6. These curves present the annual probability of exceedance, and the economic loss expressed in millions of Euros (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Annual exceedance probability curves for economic losses caused by fluvial flooding (with and without EBA) in Vilanova i la Geltrú

Source: D6.4 (Figueiredo et al., 2024).

Note: The results are expressed in 2021 price terms.

It was then possible to calculate AAL, understood as the sum of all damage cost for each return period. The total AAL was based on a log linear approach to calculate the integral of the exceedance probability curve of the damages for each return period (Olsen et al., 2015; Haer et al., 2017). Figure 13 presents the AAL for the climate change scenarios RCP 4.5 and 8.5, covering various periods, with and without adaptation. The results indicate a significant reduction in AAL with the implementation of EBA measures for all combinations.

Figure 13: Expected average annual losses (AAL) due to fluvial flooding for each climate scenario and EBA situation in Vilanova i la Geltrú

Source: D6.4 (Figueiredo et al., 2024).

Note: The results are expressed in 2021 price terms.

3.2.3. Temporal horizon

The Spanish government, building on European Commission’s proposal for economic analysis of investment projects, recommends considering 30-year time horizon for environmental and water projects (CEDEX, 2019). Environmental projects usually consider long time horizons (OECD, 2018). However, due to the high variability of flooding returns periods predicted by models and water body assessments, a 42-year time horizon was selected under RCP4.5 and

RCP8.5 climate scenarios. This time frame covers projections from the projects' Year 0 (2024) to 2065. The choice of this time horizon is also supported by the available projections from the previous methodological steps, including hydraulic and hydrological modelling, as well as the hazard risk assessment.

3.2.4. Discount rate

To account for the uncertainties of the proposed measures, a broad range of discount rates were proposed. The discount rate shows the opportunity costs of public investments with long time horizons. The selected rate for baseline calculations was 3% (Bockarjova et al. 2022, CEDEX 2019, Borrego-Marin and Berbel, 2019). To test the robustness of the assessment, 1% and 5% rates were considered for the sensitivity analysis (CEDEX 2019, Bockarjova et al. 2022).

3.2.5. Standardisation of monetary values

Since year 0 of the analysis is set to 2024, and the intervention is planned to start at the beginning of this year, it was necessary to adjust the benefit values (i.e., avoided losses) from the original reference year of 2021 to the end of 2023⁴. Similar to the Oarsoaldea case study, which followed the procedure from WP6 in D6.2 (Figueiredo and Rangel, 2022), this adjustment was made by applying the average ratios of Spain's GDP per capita and CCI, based on Eurostat data⁵.

3.2.6. Evaluation of costs and benefits

The CBA was calculated in terms of NPV to estimate future cashflows in the present time. It followed the approach described in Haer et al. (2017). In equation [1], B stands for the benefits (present value) accumulated during the whole period ($T=42$ years), whereas C represents the sum of the implementation and maintenance costs of the interventions (present value). Equation [2] provides a more detailed formulation, where AAL_r refers to the benefits in terms of the reduction in average annual losses with adaptation in comparison with the BAU scenario. M represents maintenance costs, and I_0 the initial investment costs of the measure at $t = 0$. The discount rate is indicated as r .

$$NPV = PV(B) - PV(C) \quad [1]$$

$$NPV = \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{(AAL_r)_t}{(1+r)^t} - \left(\sum_{t=1}^T \frac{(M_t)}{(1+r)^t} + I_0 \right) \quad [2]$$

3.3. Results

3.3.1. Costs

The cost of implementing EbA measures in Torrent de la Piera was estimated to range between 495.4 and 779.2 thousand euros

⁵ Main GDP aggregates per capita:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/nama_10_pc_custom_14043808/default/table

CCI data: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/sts_copi_a_custom_14044449/default/table.

Table 7 presents the implementation costs considered for the three types of intervention. This information was derived from the consultation of scientific and technical literature. The total estimated cost for the three interventions ranged from €495,354.51 to €779,189.46. The largest portion of the budget is allocated to riverbank consolidation using the geotechnique of a live slope grid. The analysis evaluated two options for this technique: applying it to 50% and 100% of the riverbank area adjacent to the stream. The 100% coverage represents the highest level of consolidation aimed at ensuring optimal protection of the riverbank.

Table 7: Implementation costs of EBA interventions in Torrent de la Piera (2024)

Interventions	Specific actions	Unitary costs	Total costs estimates
1. Riverbed widening along with the increase in the height of the right riverbank by constructing a river levee in the form of an earthen embankment (zone 2)	1. Land clearing	0.3 €/m ² (a)	3,502.44 €
	2. Excavation for riverbed widening	8.91 €/m ³ (b)	33,661.09 €
	3. Dispersal of the extracted material in the previous action for the development of the river levee	3.44 €/m ³ (c)	7,740.00 €
	4. Loading, transportation, and disposal of non-usable extracted material	4.68 €/m ³ (b)	7,150.57 €
	5. Land resurfacing for the development of the river levee	1.67 €/m ² (c)	4,749.48 €
	6. Riverbank consolidation with geotechnique (live slope grid) considering two options: 50% and 100% coverage of the riverbank area adjacent to the stream	117.55 €/m ² (d)	88,867.80 € - 177,735.60 € *
	7. Riverbank greening - construction and placement of a live fascine at the bottom of the riverbank in shallow trenches placed parallel to the flow of the stream	47.58 €/m (d)	17,128.80 €
	8. River levee greening – geofibre made from coconut	6.85 €/m ² (d)	19,481.40 €
	9. River levee greening – vegetation (sowing of a mix of native low-maintenance herbaceous seeds)	1.71 €/m ² (d)	4,863.24 €
	Total	-	187,144.82 € - 276,012.62 € *
2. Riverbed widening (zone 3)	1. Land clearing	0.3 €/m ² (a)	915.50 €
	2. Excavation for riverbed widening, with a portion of the material to be reused in Intervention No. 3 and the remainder to be sent for disposal	8.91 €/m ³ (b)	31,136.11 €
	3. Loading, transportation, and disposal of non-usable extracted material	4.68 €/m ³ (c)	9,041.82 €
	4. Land resurfacing for riverbank consolidation	1.67 €/m ² (c)	2,788.71 €
	5. Riverbank consolidation with geotechnique (live slope grid) considering two options: 50% and 100% coverage of the riverbank area adjacent to the stream	117.55 €/m ² (d)	98,147.41 € - 196,294.81 € *
	6. Riverbank greening – geofibre made from coconut	6.85 €/m ² (d)	11,438.70 €

Interventions	Specific actions	Unitary costs	Total costs estimates
	7. Riverbank greening - construction and placement of a live fascine at the bottom of the riverbank in shallow trenches placed parallel to the flow of the stream	47.58 €/m ^(d)	9,040.20 €
	8. Riverbank greening – vegetation (sowing of a mix of native low-maintenance herbaceous seeds)	1.71 €/m ² (d)	2,855.50 €
	Total	-	165,363.96 € - 263,511.36 € *
3. Raising the elevation of the right riverbank by constructing a river levee in the form of an earthen embankment (zone 5)	1. Land clearing	0.3 €/m ² (a)	488.30 €
	2. Loading and transportation of extractable material from intervention No2	1.25 €/m ³ (c)	1,953.13 €
	2. Dispersal of the extracted material in intervention No 2 for the development of the river levee	3.44 €/m ³ (c)	5,375.00 €
	3. Land resurfacing for the development of the river levee	1.67 €/m ² (c)	4,295.73 €
	4. Riverbank consolidation with geoengineering technique (live slope grid) considering two options: 50% and 100% coverage of the riverbank area adjacent to the stream	117.55 €/m ² (d)	96,819.74 € - 193,639.47 € *
	5. Riverbank greening - construction and placement of a live fascine at the bottom of the riverbank in shallow trenches placed parallel to the flow of the stream	47.58 €/m ^(d)	11,895.00 €
	6. River levee greening – geofibre made from coconut	6.85 €/m ² (d)	17,620.22 €
	7. River levee greening – vegetation (sowing of a mix of native low-maintenance herbaceous seeds)	1.71 €/m ² (d)	4,398.62 €
	Total	-	142,845.73 € - 239,665.47 € *
TOTAL		-	495,354.51 € - 779,189.46 € *

Sources: ^(a) Servei de manteniment de les lleres dels torrents del municipi de Vilanova i la Geltrú (in English: “The service for the maintenance of the banks of the streams in the municipality of Vilanova i la Geltrú). In: <https://contractaciopublica.cat/ca/detall-publicacio/71ef2cb5-5537-4e64-a175-c700ea064ff7/200046097> (accessed in July 2024); ^(b) ITEQ (<https://itec.cat/>; accessed in July 2024); ^(c) Naturalea (2020); ^(d) Löchner Prats (2019).

Notes: * The lower and upper values within the range correspond to the options of considering 50% and 100% coverage of the riverbank area adjacent to the stream by a live slope grid, respectively. Values are adjusted to reflect 2023 real prices.

3.3.2. Avoided annual losses

This section presents a summary of the results concerning the avoided annual losses across the categories—buildings, roads, and railways—for the period 2024-2065 and climate change scenarios RCP4.5 and RCP8.5.

Avoided annual losses estimated to range between approximately 3.4 and 3.8 million euros for RCP4.5 and RCP8.5, respectively

The results from the WP6 analysis of AAL (D6.4: Figueiredo et al. 2024), as shown in Table 8 indicate that adaptation led to a reduction in AAL across all infrastructure categories. Nevertheless, buildings were particularly favoured by

the implementation of EbA measures, exceeding 3 million euros in avoided AAL in both scenarios. In comparison, the avoided losses for the railway network are estimated at around 237 and 280 thousand euros for RCP4.5 and RCP8.5, respectively. Moreover, the avoided losses for roads are approximately 8.5 and 9.3 thousand euros for the respective scenarios.

Table 8: Avoided average annual losses with the EBA implementation in Torrent de la Piera (2024-2065)

Concept	Category	RCP4.5		RCP8.5	
		Euros	% over total	Euros	% over total
Average annual losses (AAL) – without adaptation	Buildings	3,580,015 €	88.3%	4,499,023 €	89.2%
	Roads	13,476 €	0.3%	16,109 €	0.3%
	Railway	463,086 €	11.4%	530,174 €	10.5%
	Total	4,056,576 €	100%	5,045,306 €	100%
Average annual losses (AAL) – with adaptation	Buildings	393,668 €	63.03%	988,939 €	79.4%
	Roads	4,965 €	0.8%	6,833 €	0.5%
	Railway	225,947 €	36.2%	250,505 €	20.1%
	Total	624,580 €	100%	1,246,277 €	100%
Avoided average annual losses (AAL) – with adaptation	Buildings	3,186,347 €	92.8%	3,510,085 €	92.4%
	Roads	8,511 €	0.2%	9,276 €	0.2%
	Railway	237,139 €	6.9%	279,669 €	7.4%
	Total	3,431,997 €	100%	3,799,030 €	100%

Source: Own elaboration based on D6.4 (Figueiredo et al., 2024).

Note: Values are adjusted to reflect 2023 real prices.

3.3.3. Cost-benefit results

Table 9 provides a summary of the key results regarding the costs, benefits and the Net Present Value (NPV) of implementing EBA measures, under the climate change scenarios RCP 4.5 and 8.5. The analysis covers the period from 2024 to 2065, and considers a discount rate of 3% and annual maintenance costs corresponding to 1% of the initial investment. The results show a positive NPV ranging from approximately 79.4 to 88.3 million euros, indicating a clear preference for adaptation compared to the BAU scenario.

Table 9: Estimated NPV for the EBA implementation in Torrent de la Piera (2024-2065)

Concept		RCP4.5	RCP8.5
Adaptation option A: Live slope grid on 50% of the riverbank			
Costs (present value)	Initial investment		495,355 €
	Total maintenance costs		115,974 €
	Total		611,329 €
Benefits	Buildings	74,600,027 €	82,179,506 €

Concept		RCP4.5	RCP8.5
(in total avoided losses; present value)	Roads	199,252 €	217,171 €
	Railway	5,551,992 €	6,547,723 €
	Total	80,351,271 €	88,944,400 €
NPV		79,739,942 €	88,333,071 €
Adaptation option B: Live slope grid on 100% of the riverbank			
Costs (present value)	Initial investment	779,189€	
	Total maintenance costs	182,427 €	
	Total	961,616 €	
Benefits (in total avoided losses; present value)	Buildings	74,600,027 €	82,179,506 €
	Roads	199,252 €	217,171 €
	Railway	5,551,992 €	6,547,723 €
	Total	80,351,271 €	88,944,400 €
NPV		79,389,655 €	87,982,784 €

Note: Values are adjusted to reflect 2023 real prices.

3.3.4. Sensitivity analysis

The sensitivity analysis, which incorporates various discount rates and annual maintenance costs, reveals positive NPVs for the adaptation scenarios, ranging from approximately 59 to 115.5 million euros. The CV of 27%, calculated from all estimates across both climate change scenarios suggests a moderate level of variability in the NPV. This outcome is primarily driven by changes in the discount rate.

Table 10: NPV for various adaptation scenarios and discount rates (2024-2065)

Concept	RCP4.5		RCP8.5		
	Annual maintenance costs*		Annual maintenance costs*		
	1%	2%	1%	2%	
Adaptation option A: Live slope grid on 50% of the riverbank					
Discount rate	1%	114,309,514 €	114,143,572 €	126,605,014 €	126,439,071 €
	3%	79,739,942 €	79,623,968 €	88,333,071 €	88,217,097 €
	5%	58,773,185 €	58,687,516 €	65,120,792 €	65,035,124 €
Coefficient of variation (CV; %)	27.17%		27.16%		
Adaptation option B: Live slope grid on 100% of the riverbank					
Discount rate	1%	113,930,596 €	113,669,570 €	126,226,095 €	125,965,069 €
	3%	79,389,655 €	79,207,228 €	87,982,784 €	87,800,357 €
	5%	58,440,262 €	58,305,506 €	64,787,870 €	64,653,114 €
Coefficient of variation (CV; %)	27.26%		27.24%		

Notes: Values are adjusted to reflect 2023 real prices; * Annual maintenance costs correspond to different percentages over the initial investment cost.

4. RESTORATION OF HISTORIC WATER CISTERNS IN PIRAN

4.1. Study area and research objectives

The role of water reuse in the EU has primarily been approached from the perspective of applying circular economy principles within the water sector. The ultimate aim is to reduce both consumption and the pressure placed on natural resources (including energy), while enhancing the recycling and reuse of water to the greatest extent possible (European Commission, 2012). The circular water economy is defined by Chen et al. (2021) as a business model that enables sustainable production and consumption through the reuse of water and resource recovery. The Action Plan for the Circular Economy also calls for action on water reuse in the context of droughts and water scarcity (European Commission, 2015). Another key piece of legislation is the EU Regulation 2020/741 of the European Parliament and of the Council, which focuses on water reuse for irrigation.⁶ This regulation aims to strengthen the market for technologies and services related to water recycling and to promote the development of water reuse projects across the EU (Berbel et al., 2023). It encourages the reuse of water resources as part of sustainable management, reducing pressure on freshwater supplies, and preserving traditional water collection technologies to help minimise environmental impacts and promote sustainability. The increased expected water shortages with climate change, particularly in Southern Europe, justify the need to promote alternatives to conventional sources (rainfall, surface or groundwater) for irrigation (La Jeunesse et al., 2016).

In accordance with the above-mentioned principles, this study focuses on the restoration and repurposing of historic underground cisterns in urban areas, which were designed to collect rainwater from rooftops for non-potable uses, such as washing roads, watering gardens, and firefighting. The reactivation of these cisterns aims to reduce pressures on municipal water systems, increase water storage capacity, and enhance public awareness of water conservation and cultural heritage. The restored cisterns are expected to provide vital water resources during drought periods, contributing to the resilience of local communities.

The objective of the respective CBA is to evaluate the feasibility and potential benefits of restoring historic water cisterns and their impact on the local community of Piran. One of the characteristic features of Piran's historical infrastructure is the network of water cisterns, ingeniously designed to address the ongoing challenges associated with water scarcity. These cisterns, which were once an integral part of water management systems, were originally designed to collect and store rainwater, providing valuable resources for drinking and other uses during periods of water scarcity. In a region with limited natural water resources and seasonal fluctuations in rainfall, the residents of Piran relied on these underground cisterns to collect and store rainwater, ensuring a consistent supply of drinking water, particularly during the dry summer months. This is especially important for Piran, which practically has no natural water sources other than rainwater.

Beyond their functional significance, the cisterns today stand as tangible examples of historical ingenuity in managing natural resources, reflecting the community's adaptation to environmental constraints. Cisterns such as those at 1st of May Square, the Lighthouse on Punta, and the Old Kindergarten Parish represent valuable cultural monuments and sustainable water management solutions that remain relevant in contemporary discussions on climate resilience and water conservation.

⁶ Regulation (EU) 2020/741 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 May 2020 on minimum requirements for water reuse (Text with EEA relevance. In: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2020/741/oj/eng>.

In this context, exploring the potential for renovating and repurposing these cisterns is of particular importance. Investigating the possibility of revitalising these historic structures would help the town not only to preserve its cultural heritage but also to address current water management challenges, such as reducing the risk of water scarcity during the peak tourist season and minimising dependence on external water supplies. The presence of these cisterns provides a unique opportunity to combine historical preservation with practical and sustainable solutions for the future, especially since currently 100% of water for Piran is imported from other regions, and even in the best-case scenario of cistern re-activation, the town would remain mostly dependent on this exogenous water.

The specific purpose of the CBA regarding water cistern restoration is to estimate the costs and benefits of restoring historic water cisterns, which were originally built underground throughout the town to collect rainwater from rooftops and provide drinking water. The selection of the climate change hazard, study area, and research objectives was informed by the results of the MCA previously conducted in Piran (D7.3: Campos Rodrigues et al. 2024).

This CBA focuses on the restoration of the following 3 cisterns:

- **1st of May Square Cistern**

The 1st of May Square in Piran is one of the central and most well-known areas of the town, with significant historical and cultural interest. In this area, one of the important historical water cisterns is located, originally constructed to collect and store rainwater from the rooftops of surrounding buildings. This cistern, with an area of 670m², is situated within a short distance from the road, facilitating access for water transport if necessary. It continues to be an important part of Piran's historical infrastructure, offering both cultural as well as functional value to the town.

- **Lighthouse on Punta Cistern**

The Lighthouse of Punta area in Piran is known for its stunning views of the Adriatic Sea and its historical significance. In this area, one of the historical water cisterns is located, originally built to collect rainwater and provide drinking water to the town. This cistern has an area of 60 m² and is situated close to the road, facilitating access for potential water transport. Although it is no longer in use today, this cistern remains an important part of Piran's historical heritage and the region's natural resource management.

- **Old Kindergarten Parish Cistern**

The Old Kindergarten Parish area in Piran is a historic site with significant cultural heritage. Here lies one of the town's historical water cisterns, which was used for collecting rainwater and ensuring a drinking water supply. The cistern's surface spans 130 m² and is located close to the road, providing easy access for potential water transport. Although it is no longer in use today, this cistern remains an important part of Piran's historical infrastructure and traditional water management.

Figures 14 and 15 and Table 11 present additional information about these cisterns.

Figure 14: Cisterns analysed in the CBA focused on the renovation of historic wells in Piran

1st of May Square cistern

Lighthouse Punta cistern

Old Kindergarten Parish cistern

Source: Piran CCLL.

Figure 15: Map with the location of the 3 cisterns in the town of Piran

Source: Piran CCLL.

Table 11: Summary of the key characteristics of the cisterns

Basic information	Cistern		
	1 st of May Square	Old Kindergarten Parish	Lighthouse Punta
1. Current status	In-use	Not in use	Restored in 2023 but not in use
2. Capacity (m ³)	390	40	20
3. Existence of sand filters	Yes	Yes	No
4. Surface area (m ²)	670	130	60
5. Proximity of the cistern to the road in meters (if needed for water carrier vehicles; in meters)	8	8	3
6. Distribution of water (pipes, mobile tank, hoses, etc.)	Currently no such infrastructure is in place	Currently no such infrastructure is in place	Currently no such infrastructure is in place
7. Method of pumping (pumps, buckets, mechanical or by hand)	Bucket, gas powered pump	Bucket	Bucket
8. Permeable or impermeable pavement	Permeable	Permeable	Impermeable

Source: Piran CCLL.

4.2. Methodology

4.2.1. Identification of costs and benefits

a) Costs

The restoration and operation of historical cisterns entail several cost categories, including the initial implementation and the ongoing maintenance and operational expenses. These cost categories are presented as follows:

- **Direct implementation costs**

Initially, the costs related to the restoration of the cisterns include the pre-treatment of water before storage. If there are mechanical parts in the infrastructure, such as pumps, additional electricity costs are required. Furthermore, monitoring and analysis of water quality are essential for its safe use, and this includes expenses for water sampling, field measurements, laboratory analysis, and the preparation of reports that will provide critical data for water usage.

- **Maintenance and operational costs**

The ongoing operation of the restored cisterns requires regular maintenance, including costs for part replacement or repairs to the wells. Additionally, there are costs for water treatment, such as chlorination, to ensure water quality, particularly if there are concerns about the safety of the water being used. Another significant expense is the detection and elimination of illegal discharges or pollution that may affect the cisterns, which requires specialised staff and equipment.

- **Testing and design costs**

Furthermore, before the restoration, tests are necessary to assess the feasibility of each cistern and the need for interventions. Feasibility analyses include technical and economic evaluations for restoring the infrastructure and integrating new components into the existing system. Consulting services related to the design, permitting, and supervision of the restoration are essential to ensure the quality and legality of the project.

- **Promotional costs**

Promotional costs encompass all expenses related to advertising, marketing, and communication efforts aimed at raising awareness of the historical cistern restoration project and its significance for the local community and tourism. These costs are essential for ensuring the project's visibility, engaging local communities, and attracting tourists, all of which contribute to the funding and overall success of the project. A well-designed promotional strategy goes beyond showcasing the tangible benefits of the project; it also focuses on educating the public about the importance of cultural heritage and the sustainable management of water resources.

The cost estimates used in the CBA for all above cost categories are based on desk research and consultation of online sources, as well as on information obtained through personal interviews and through public and private documentation sourced from companies offering water treatment and water management solutions, such as TEMAK, Adtec, AcquaSource, and E-Chemicals. Specific references on sources of this information can be found in the respective section of this study.

b) Benefits

The restoration and reuse of historical public cisterns for non-potable uses offer significant benefits both for the environment, as well as for the local community. The goal of this initiative is to save water and energy, as well as to

enhance the sustainability of local water resources, while simultaneously improving the quality of life for citizens and protecting the environment. The benefits included in the analysis are outlined as follows:

- **Water and energy savings**

Using water from the restored cisterns for applications such as garden irrigation, street washing, and firefighting, contributes to the full utilisation of the region's natural resources, and possibly reduces the need for water from the public supply network, especially during drought periods, which coincide with the peak of the tourist season. Also noteworthy is the increased need for water in urban and peri-urban agriculture in those summer months, as there are several terraces that locals use for hobby farming, as well as some semi-professional farmers. In this way, the project enhances local autonomy and water resource management. Furthermore, saving water leads to a reduced need for pumping and transporting water from distant sources, resulting in significant energy savings. This process improves the efficiency of infrastructure and contributes to the protection of the region's natural resources.

- **Reduction of surface runoff and erosion control**

Using rainwater for the irrigation of public and private gardens, as well as for street washing, helps reduce surface runoff and alleviates the burden on the relatively inefficient drainage system of Piran, minimizing the risk of flooding during heavy rainfall (Panagos et al., 2023). Additionally, the proper use of water for irrigating green spaces contributes to controlling soil erosion and maintaining soil stability (Boardman et al., 2006; Bezak et al., 2023).

- **Economic benefits from water reuse**

Using the water for non-potable applications, such as irrigation and street washing, reduces the expenses associated with potable water consumption from the public supply network, offering significant economic savings (Lopez et al., 2024). Local authorities and citizens benefit from lower costs related to using potable water for non-potable needs, while also promoting sustainability in local water resource management. In addition, the money saved can be reinvested in other infrastructure improvement initiatives or environmental protection programs (Berbel et al., 2023).

- **Income from increased tourist traffic**

The renovation of the cisterns enhances the cultural appeal of Piran, attracting more tourists interested in cultural heritage. As unique historical landmarks, the cisterns offer a deeper connection to the city's past and add value to the visitors' experience. Increased interest in cultural heritage and sustainable tourism development, such as tours of renovated historical landmarks, promotes sustainable growth and strengthens Piran's popularity as a tourist destination.

The estimation of water benefits is based on calculations of the water savings obtained from the specific cisterns, and relate to their capacity, surface area used to collect the water, the rainfall in Piran, as well as the cost of water and water transport to the area. Furthermore, the avoided costs of flooding are included as potential benefits. Finally, a corresponding increase in the number of tourists visiting Piran and in touristic revenues is assumed.

4.2.2. Temporal horizon

A period of 42 years was chosen to maintain consistency with the other case studies presented in this report and facilitate potential comparability. This period is deemed appropriate for the current CBA, as it spans a sufficiently long period of time to account for the project's benefits, without extending too long in the future for which no

realistic climate change or policy prioritisation scenarios can be developed. Therefore, the base year is 2024 (investment year), and the CBA extends to 2065 (41 more years).

4.2.3. Discount rate

The base discount rate that was used in the CBA was 3%, with the sensitivity analysis also considering 1% and 5% rates. This selection aligns with the rates applied in the previous CBAs.

4.2.4. Evaluation of costs and benefits

The Net Present Value (NPV) was calculated to assess the long-term financial viability of the project over a 42-year period. The analysis considers projected revenues and costs, discounted to present value using an appropriate discount rate. The NPV formula applied is presented below, where R represents revenues, C costs, r the discount rate, and t the year in the evaluation period. A positive NPV indicates that the project is expected to generate net benefits over time, supporting its feasibility and sustainability.

$$NPV = \sum \left(\frac{R_t - C_t}{(1 + r)^t} \right) \quad [1]$$

4.3. Results

The CBA for the restoration of the three historical reservoirs provides a comprehensive examination of both the costs and the benefits associated with the project. This analysis not only focuses on direct benefits, such as water savings and energy savings, but also examines the significant indirect benefits arising from the increase in tourism, which plays a critical role in the financial sustainability and success of the project.

The analysis considers two possible scenarios: the first scenario includes tourism benefits, and the second scenario excludes them, in order to better understand the impact of the project and its value to the local economy and environment. Below is a detailed breakdown of the project's costs and benefits, highlighting how the inclusion of tourism income can significantly enhance the sustainability of the investment.

4.3.1. Costs

In total, the estimated present value cost for the restoration and long-term sustainability of the three reservoirs ranges from 539,751 euros to 630,673 euros.

The first category of expenses includes the **Direct Implementation Costs (A1)**. These are the initial costs related to the restoration of the reservoirs and the necessary preparations for water storage and reuse. These costs cover the pre-treatment of water to ensure its quality, potential electricity expenses when mechanical systems such as pumps are required, and costs for water quality testing and monitoring, which are essential for ensuring the safety of the stored water. The total amount for these expenses is **€158,872**. These expenses are crucial for the success of the project, as proper treatment and monitoring of the water are necessary to avoid contamination and to meet quality requirements. The difference in pre-treatment costs for the 1st of May Square cistern compared to the other two cisterns is due to its more deteriorated condition. It requires more restoration and treatment work before recharging, such as cleaning, pollutant removal, and infrastructure reinforcement, which demand additional resources, technology, and time to restore the functionality of the cistern. The difference in the other cost categories is due to its larger size.

Maintenance and Operational Costs (A2) are the ongoing expenses required to keep the reservoirs in good condition in the future. These costs include replacing worn-out parts, chlorinating the water to maintain its quality, and the necessary work for maintaining the infrastructure. Additionally, they cover the detection and elimination of illegal discharges that may damage the system. The total cost for maintenance and operation is **€272,766**. This category of expenses ensures the long-term sustainability of the project, keeping it fully operational and efficient.

Testing and Design Costs (A3) include the preliminary assessments required before restoration. These tests evaluate the feasibility of the reservoirs and determine the necessary interventions and design measures. Feasibility analyses, which include technical and financial evaluations, are necessary to guide the restoration process. Consultancy services for design, licensing, and project supervision are additional expenses, totalling **€108,112**.

Finally, **Promotional Costs (A4)** play a critical role in promoting the project both locally and internationally. The project's promotion helps attract funding and inform the public about the cultural and environmental value of the reservoirs. These costs include expenses for advertising, media campaigns, and public relations to increase the visibility of the project. The total cost for promotional expenses is **€90,922**. The difference in promotion costs for the three cisterns is mainly due to their location. The 1st of May Square cistern has higher promotion costs due to its strategic position, which requires more resources and promotional efforts to attract visitors and promote it as a tourist spot. On the other hand, the other two cisterns are located in already touristically developed neighbourhoods of Piran, where the tourism infrastructure and recognition are already stronger, reducing the need for such high promotion costs.

The **total estimated cost** for the restoration and sustainability of the three reservoirs ranges between **€539,751** and **€630,673 in present values**, depending on whether promotional expenses related to tourism are included (Scenario B) or excluded (Scenario A). These amounts reflect both the initial investment for restoration as well as the ongoing maintenance and operational costs required to keep the reservoirs functional and efficient.

Table 12 displays the costs associated with the three cisterns in present values, and Figure 16 depicts the percentage breakdown of these costs across the various categories in scenario A, which is presented alone as it includes all cost categories. Maintenance costs account for the largest portion, followed by direct implementation costs.

Table 12: Estimation of the present value of costs for the restoration of the cisterns under scenarios A and B

Costs	Cistern			Total
	1st of May Square	Old Kindergarten Parish	Lighthouse Punta	
A1. Direct implementation costs				
Pre-treatment costs (additional treatment prior to recharge)	19,988 €	1,553 €	1,553 €	23,095 €
Possible electricity (if mechanical parts)	34,096 €	17,048 €	17,048 €	68,191 €
Water quality testing and monitoring (including collection, in situ measurements, preparation, laboratory analysis, evaluation of the results, report)	22,885 €	22,496 €	22,205 €	67,586 €
Total A1	76,968 €	41,098 €	40,806 €	158,872 €
A2. Maintenance and operational costs				
Maintenance costs (e.g., parts replacement, size of cistern rehabilitation, repairs)	22,730 €	13,638 €	13,638 €	50,007 €
Post-treatment costs (e.g., chlorination)	52,280 €	34,096 €	34,096 €	120,472 €
Detection and elimination of illegal discharges	9,092 €	6,819 €	6,819 €	22,730 €
Labor for maintenance and pollution prevention	34,096 €	22,730 €	22,730 €	79,557 €
Total A2	118,199 €	77,284 €	77,284 €	272,766 €
A3. Testing and design				

Costs	Cistern			Total
	1st of May Square	Old Kindergarten Parish	Lighthouse Punta	
Testing costs (Leak testing of cisterns, Checking of leak detection of roofs, Soil permeability testing, Control of the water transport system)	22,730 €	22,730 €	22,730 €	68,191 €
Feasibility analyses (e.g. Visual inspection, investigate opportunities for artificial recharge of groundwater in the wider region, Possible methods/techniques to implement circular economy, Alternative Methods to apply rainwater harvesting, technical report)	11,365 €	11,365 €	11,365 €	34,096 €
Consulting services for the design, permitting, and supervision of the reconstruction	2,913 €	1,456 €	1,456 €	5,825 €
Total A3	37,008 €	35,552 €	35,552 €	108,112 €
A4. Promotional expenses				
Marketing & Advertising	72,738 €	9,092 €	9,092 €	90,922 €
Total A4	72,738 €	9,092 €	9,092 €	90,922 €
Total costs (Scenario A - with A4)	304,913 €	163,025 €	162,734 €	630,673 €
Total costs (Scenario B - without A4)	232,175 €	153,933 €	153,642 €	539,751 €

Figure 16: Cost categories allocation associated with the adaptation scenario A (%)

4.3.2. Benefits

The benefits derived from restoring the three water cisterns were estimated at 2.3 million euros

The present value of the **Direct Benefits (B1)** of the project is significant and contributes both to environmental sustainability as well as to cost savings. Direct benefits include **water savings** (€35,394), **energy savings** (€2,124), **reduction of runoff** (€84,272), and **erosion control** (€50,563). These environmental benefits provide immediate financial gains, while simultaneously enhancing the resilience of the local community against issues such as water scarcity, floods, and soil erosion. The total amount of these direct benefits is **€172,354**.

The **Indirect Benefits (B2)** include **groundwater recharge** (€607), **revenue from water reuse** (€10,113), and **reduced stormwater management costs** (€16,854), all in present values. Groundwater recharge improves water security, while water reuse reduces dependence on municipal water systems, providing further economic benefits. Still, the most significant **Indirect Benefit (B2)** comes from the increase in **tourism**. The restoration of

the reservoirs and their promotion as cultural monuments is expected to attract a significant number of visitors, both from the local and international tourism markets. As historical and cultural points of interest, the reservoirs have the potential to boost tourism revenue. The expected increase in tourism revenue is estimated at **€1,057,133**, a sum that significantly enhances the overall economic value of the project. The restoration of these reservoirs **offers an opportunity to combine environmental sustainability with cultural tourism**, contributing to the local economy while preserving valuable heritage. The total indirect benefits amount to **€1,084,707**, enhancing the sustainability of the project.

The present value of the **total benefits** – including direct and indirect benefits – ranges from **€199,928** to **€1,257,061**, corresponding to scenarios B and A. The substantial disparity between these estimates derives from the significant revenue generated through tourism in scenario B, highlighting the importance of tourism income for the local economy and the sustainability of the project.

Table 13 outlines the estimated benefits from the restoration of the cisterns in present values, while Figure 17 illustrates the distribution of these benefits across different categories in scenario A.

Table 13: Estimation of the present value of benefits obtained from restoration of the cisterns under scenarios A and B

Benefits	Cistern			Total
	1st of May Square	Old Kindergarden Parish	Lighthouse Punta	
B1. Direct benefits				
Water savings	27,575 €	5,350 €	2,469 €	35,394 €
Energy savings	1,654 €	321 €	148 €	2,124 €
Reduction in surface runoff	65,654 €	12,739 €	5,879 €	84,272 €
Erosion control	39,392 €	7,643 €	3,528 €	50,563 €
Total B1	134,276 €	26,053 €	12,025 €	172,354 €
B2. Indirect benefits				
Groundwater recharge	473 €	92 €	42 €	607 €
Revenue from water reuse	7,878 €	1,529 €	706 €	10,113 €
Reduced stormwater management costs	13,131 €	2,548 €	1,176 €	16,854 €
Income from increased tourist traffic	634,280 €	211,427 €	211,427 €	1,057,133 €
Total B2	655,762 €	215,595 €	213,350 €	1,084,707 €
Total benefits (Scenario A – with Income from increased tourist traffic)	790,037 €	241,648 €	225,375 €	1,257,061 €
Total benefits (Scenario B – without Income from increased tourist traffic)	155,758 €	30,222 €	13,948 €	199,928 €

Figure 17: Benefits categories allocation associated with the adaptation scenario A (%)

4.3.3. Cost-benefit results

Table 14 presents the results of the cost-benefit analysis, expressed as Net Present Value (NPV). **Scenario A shows a positive NPV of €626,388**, indicating that the project is desirable. The total benefits (€1,257,061) significantly exceed the costs (€630,673), with direct benefits such as water savings, energy savings, and runoff reduction contributing to a substantial return. Moreover, indirect benefits, such as increased tourism income (€1,057,133), add considerable value to the project, further improving its financial outlook. This positive NPV suggests that the investments in the cisterns will not only pay off in terms of immediate operational savings but will also generate long-term economic and social benefits. The project's successful integration of water resource management and its ability to drive tourism revenue underscores its overall viability and potential for contributing to sustainable development.

The **results for Scenario B indicate a negative NPV of - €339,823** due to the cisterns small size and high restoration and maintenance costs. The total cost of the project (€539,751) far exceeds the expected benefits (€199,928), showing a poor return on investment. The key reasons for the negative performance are as follows:

- **High Fixed Costs:** Pre-treatment costs (€23,095), water quality testing (€67,586), and post-treatment costs (€120,472) are high and cannot be efficiently distributed due to the small scale of the cisterns, leading to disproportionate expenses.
- **Limited Direct Benefits:** The benefits, such as water savings (€35,394) and runoff reduction (€84,272), are too small to offset the high costs. The small capacity of the cisterns limits the amount of water that can be collected and used, making the project less efficient.
- **Small Scale:** The small volume of the cisterns reduces the return on investment, as fixed costs are spread over a limited amount of stored or treated water. Larger cisterns would distribute the same restoration costs across a greater volume, improving the cost-benefit ratio and potentially resulting in a positive NPV.
- Furthermore, **operational costs for maintenance and monitoring are high, while the benefits from water reuse and runoff reduction do not sufficiently cover these expenses**, contributing to the negative NPV and the project's lack of economic viability at this scale.

Table 14: Estimated NPV for the restoration of the cisterns under scenarios A and B

Concept	Scenario A	Scenario B
Costs (present value)	630,673 €	539,751 €
Benefits (present value)	1,257,061 €	199,928 €
NPV	626,388 €	-339,823 €

In conclusion, from the cost-benefit analysis, it is found that there is no benefit in rehabilitating the cisterns/wells without the benefit of tourism development. This is related to the limited water storage capacity of the wells due to their shallow depth and diameter, the permeability of the soil, and the general condition of the wells. In addition, the small storage capacity of the cistern/wells limits their contribution to flood control from stormwater. As a result, the water savings are limited and therefore the economic benefits are also limited.

It is also essential to highlight that the cost analysis incorporates a comparative evaluation of the currently existing alternative practice for water provision, specifically the transportation of restored water via tanker trucks. This comparison allows for a comprehensive assessment of the economic viability and sustainability of utilising water resources through the restoration of water cisterns.

Within the framework of the suggested project, the restoration of cisterns enables the utilisation of rainwater, which requires only an initial investment in pumping infrastructure and a distribution network composed of plastic piping. The capital expenditure associated with water pumps is modest, with costs ranging from approximately 200 to 350 euros per unit, as indicated by market sources⁷. Additionally, the cost of a 50-meter flexible hose is estimated at 50 euros. The operational energy consumption of the pumping system is minimal, making it an economically and environmentally favourable solution for non-potable water applications. As previously mentioned, the harvested water can be efficiently repurposed for urban maintenance activities such as street cleaning, as well as for landscape and garden irrigation.

Conversely, the alternative scenario of transporting water from external sources via tanker trucks is associated with significantly higher recurrent costs. The transportation expenses depend on multiple factors, including seasonal variations, the required volume of water, and the distance from the water source. Typically, the cost per delivery per truck ranges from 100 to 150 euros, which accumulates over time and represents a substantial financial burden, particularly for continuous or large-scale water usage. Additionally, the environmental impact of tanker truck transportation—such as fuel consumption and carbon emissions—should also be considered when evaluating the overall sustainability of this method.

By comparing these two approaches, it becomes evident that the restoration and use of rainwater from cisterns present a more cost-effective and sustainable alternative to conventional water transportation methods, particularly in contexts where water conservation and efficient resource management are priorities.

4.3.4. Sensitivity analysis

Table 15 presents the results of the NPV for scenarios A and B under different discount rates (1%, 3%, 5%). In Scenario A, the NPV is positive at all rates, indicating that the project is desirable. However, it decreases as the discount rate increases, from €946,521 at 1% to €435,437 at 5%. In Scenario B, the NPV is negative across all discount rates, signifying that the costs exceed the benefits. Furthermore, the coefficient of variation (CV), with absolute

⁷ <https://www.allwater.gr/en/water-pumps-pressure-systems/>.

percentages ranging from 26.2% to 31.5%, indicates a moderate sensitivity of the results to changes in the discount rates.

Table 15: Estimated NPV from the sensitivity analysis

Discount Rate	Net Present Value (NPV)	
	Scenario A	Scenario B
1%	946,521 €	-481,783 €
3%	626,388 €	-339,823 €
5%	435,437 €	-254,396 €
Coefficient of variation (CV; %)	31.5%	(-)26.2%*

*Note: * The CV result is negative because the mean is negative. However, for clarity, it is important to focus on the magnitude of the absolute value.*

5. RENOVATION OF DEGRADED AREAS INTO GREEN SPACES IN PIRAN

5.1. Study area and research objectives

Open access (i.e., accessible to all) green spaces and pocket parks play a crucial role in enhancing urban environments and improving the quality of life for city dwellers. These areas provide numerous benefits to communities, ranging from environmental advantages to social and health improvements.

For these reasons, the European Union (EU) has demonstrated a strong commitment to promoting urban green spaces and pocket parks through various policy initiatives and strategies. The EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030⁸, adopted in May 2020, marks a significant milestone in this effort by explicitly including urban biodiversity targets (European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, 2021). This strategy calls for cities with over 20,000 inhabitants to develop Urban Greening Plans to create biodiverse and accessible urban forests, parks, and gardens. The European Commission has already established an EU Urban Greening Platform⁹ under a new “Green City Accord”¹⁰ with cities and mayors to support this initiative (European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, 2021; EUROPARC Federation, n.d.). The strategy builds upon earlier efforts, such as the 2013 Green Infrastructure Strategy, which promotes the deployment of green infrastructure in urban and rural areas across the EU (European Commission, 2013). Additionally, through projects like UrbanGreeningPlans¹¹, the LIFE Program provides financial support for urban greening initiatives, enabling local policymakers and green space managers to design and implement innovative mechanisms for increasing biodiversity in urban areas. These policies collectively emphasise the value of urban green spaces for biodiversity conservation, climate change mitigation, and citizens’ physical and mental well-being (European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, 2021; EUROPARC Federation, n.d.; European Commission, 2013).

The SCORE project aims to enhance climate resilience in European coastal cities by focusing on the development of EBA solutions. The promotion of open access green spaces and pocket parks in urban areas can contribute to this goal by supporting water management, alleviating heat waves, improving air quality and capturing carbon. Moreover, these multifunctional spaces offer a range of other benefits, such as the preservation of cultural heritage, provision of habitats for various species, and human health benefits.

Open green spaces and pocket parks in coastal cities can serve multiple functions within the SCORE project’s framework, such as:

1. *Climate resilience and water management:*

Green spaces act as natural water retention areas, helping to manage stormwater runoff and reduce the risk of urban flooding (Department for Communities and Local Government, 2015). This aligns with SCORE’s objective of improving water management in coastal cities. By incorporating permeable surfaces and vegetation, these areas can:

- Absorb excess rainwater, reducing pressure on urban drainage systems.
- Filter pollutants from runoff, improving water quality.

⁸ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/biodiversity-strategy-2030_en.

⁹ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/urban-environment/urban-nature-platform_en.

¹⁰ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/urban-environment/green-city-accord_en.

¹¹ <https://www.europarc.org/greening-plans/>.

- Recharge groundwater, contributing to sustainable water resource management.

2. *Enhancing urban biodiversity:*

Coastal ecosystems are particularly vulnerable to climate change. Urban green spaces can serve as habitats for local flora and fauna, supporting biodiversity conservation efforts (Lee et al., 2015). This aspect complements SCORE's aim of preserving natural and cultural heritage in coastal areas.

3. *Mitigating Urban Heat Island effect:*

Green spaces help reduce ambient temperatures in urban areas, which is crucial for coastal cities facing increased heat stress due to climate change (Bajwoluk & Langer, 2023). This cooling effect contributes to SCORE's goal of enhancing climate resilience.

4. *Social and cultural benefits:*

Pocket parks and open green spaces can be designed to showcase local heritage, including water management traditions. This aligns with SCORE's emphasis on preserving cultural heritage while addressing modern challenges. These areas can:

- Serve as educational spaces about local history and sustainable water management.
- Provide community gathering spaces, fostering social cohesion.
- Improve the quality of life for residents, contributing to the overall resilience of coastal communities.

5. *Integration with water cistern restoration:*

The restoration of historic water cisterns can be complemented by the creation of pocket parks above or near these structures. This integration can:

- Increase public awareness of traditional water management techniques.
- Provide green spaces that benefit from the restored cisterns for irrigation.
- Create multifunctional urban areas that combine heritage preservation, water management, and public recreation.

By integrating open green spaces and pocket parks into the SCORE project's strategies, coastal cities can enhance their climate resilience, preserve cultural heritage, and improve urban liveability. These green areas serve as multifunctional solutions that address various challenges faced by coastal communities in the context of climate change.

In this frame, the objective of a CBA for green spaces and pocket parks is to evaluate the economic feasibility and potential benefits of implementing these urban features in Piran, Slovenia. This analysis aims to quantify and compare the costs of creating and maintaining such spaces against the various benefits they provide to society. A comprehensive CBA for green spaces and pocket parks typically considers the following aspects:

1. **Economic benefits:**

- **Property value increase:** Green spaces often lead to higher property values in surrounding areas, potentially increasing tax revenues (McCosh, 2024).
- **Tourism and business attraction:** Well-designed parks can attract visitors and businesses, stimulating local economies (McCosh, 2024).

- **Healthcare cost savings:** By promoting physical activity and improving mental health, parks can reduce healthcare expenditures (García de Jalón et al., 2020; Wilson & Xiao, 2023).

2. Environmental benefits:

- **Air quality improvement:** Vegetation in parks absorbs pollutants, potentially saving on health-related costs (Wilson & Xiao, 2023; Stanfel, 2024).
- **Stormwater management:** Green spaces can reduce the burden on urban drainage systems, saving on infrastructure costs (McCosh, 2024; Stanfel, 2024).
- **Urban Heat Island mitigation:** Parks help cool urban areas, potentially reducing energy costs for cooling (Stanfel, 2024).

3. Social benefits:

- **Community cohesion:** Parks provide spaces for social interaction, potentially reducing costs associated with social isolation (García de Jalón et al., 2020).
- **Recreational value:** Parks' amenity and recreational value contribute to overall societal well-being (García de Jalón et al., 2020).

4. Costs:

- **Land acquisition:** This is especially relevant in urban areas where space comes at a premium.
- **Development and construction:** Initial costs of creating the green space or pocket park.
- **Maintenance and operations:** Ongoing costs for upkeep and management.

A CBA aims to express these benefits and costs in monetary terms wherever possible, allowing for a direct comparison. By conducting a thorough CBA, policymakers and urban planners can make informed decisions about investing in green spaces and pocket parks, justifying expenditures based on the expected returns to society. This analysis can be particularly valuable in securing funding and support for urban greening initiatives (García de Jalón et al., 2020; McCosh, 2024).

In addition to the numerous benefits, the Municipality of Piran, Slovenia, is a significant tourist destination, underscoring the need for urban green spaces and pocket parks. Furthermore, this is the first indication that a relevant CBA will likely yield positive results.

In the context of the SCORE project, four separate CBAs were conducted for urban green spaces and pocket parks in Piran – one for each prospective site in which an urban green space or pocket park may be developed or restored from existing degraded areas, along with a combined CBA for all the sites. Subsequently, sensitivity analyses have been conducted to assess the robustness of the findings.

The analysis focuses on the following four sites (Table 16):

Table 16: The four prospective sites to become urban green spaces/pocket parks

No.	Name	Total estimated open area (m ²)	Accessibility	Ownership	Parcel (No.)	Publicly owned area (m ²)	Privately owned area (m ²)
1	Kindergarten	2,012.90	Public area with restrictions	Municipal	903/2; 903/3	2,012.90	0.00

No.	Name	Total estimated open area (m ²)	Accessibility	Ownership	Parcel (No.)	Publicly owned area (m ²)	Privately owned area (m ²)
2	Dog Park	442.70*	Public area	Mixed (public and private)	From 603 to 608	278.20	240.30
3	Maritime Museum	270.00	Public area	Municipal	1184	270.00	0.00
4	Olive Trees (close to the football pitch)	8,818.00	Inaccessible (fenced off)	Municipal	5/1	8,818.00	0.00

Note: * The Total estimated open area is smaller than the total of public and private area because: a) part of this area is a flat rooftop, which cannot be considered usable in our context, as any calculations would need to include green roof expenses, which drastically changes the proposed project; and b) part of this area is currently fenced off, because the private owner cannot utilize this space but refuses to let the public access it.

The analysis of costs and benefits for these sites is based on the assumption that they will be open to visitors, Piran citizens and tourists alike, and not restricted by their current use or by any other use restrictions. The overall approach focuses on understanding the impact of open green spaces in the city, and in the city's economy.

Figure 18 presents a satellite image of the area where the study sites are located.

Figure 18: Satellite image of the study sites' locations

Source: Google Earth.

Legend: 1. Kindergarten (45.52720436° N, 13.5706308° E); 2. Dog Park (45.5301348° N, 13.5662559° E); 3. Maritime Museum (45.5278042° N, 13.5680815° E); 4. Olive Trees (close to the football pitch) (45.5283406° N, 13.5715893° E).

The **Kindergarten site** could be transformed into a learning garden for children, incorporating small-scale EBA elements into the landscape (e.g., higher trees that provide shade, or a designated rain garden to retain water that could be directed towards the available cistern), enhancing its aesthetic and functional (with the addition of playground equipment) values. The area features three terraces, each around 4-5 m high, separated by a wall. The

landscape mainly includes shrubs and grasses. A cistern that collects water is also present, but would require a pumping system to address the elevation differences in order to be efficiently using the collected water for irrigation.

The **Dog Park** is an underutilised piece of land characterised by its mixed ownership and natural vegetation. A portion of the privately owned area, covering 51 m², remains an overgrown patch that is fenced off, while the rest is open and not enclosed. Adjacent to this lies a 14.6 m² strip of public land, part of parcel no. 425, which is surrounded by the Dog park. The area features a variety of trees, including pine, fruit, and olive trees (with sparse density), and is situated at an elevation of 12-14 meters above sea level. In general, the site, despite the availability of trees, appears degraded, and not well-maintained. What is proposed is to enhance the area by increasing its biodiversity towards achieving higher visitation by humans within the limitations of still functioning as a dog park.

The **Maritime Museum study site** corresponds to a very small area located between Sergej Mašera Maritime Museum and the Art Hotel. It is ideally situated to create a pocket park that could enhance the surroundings of the cultural and hospitality landmarks. Its size and location make it suitable for subtle landscaping improvements or small-scale green installations.

The **Olive Trees area** coexists with some unclassified land uses (e.g., smaller trees and bushes). A decade ago, the Municipality funded landscape architecture proposals for a public park on this lot, highlighting its potential as a recreational space that balances natural and cultural elements, objectives which are also considered for this CBA.

In Figure 19, the locations of all the areas are presented.

Figure 19: Map representation of the study sites' locations

Source: Kralj, E., Kumer, P., & Meulenberg, C. J. W. (2023).

5.2. Methodology

5.2.1. Adaptation scenarios

The adaptation scenarios for the implementation of green spaces and pocket parks in Piran are designed to enhance urban resilience, environmental sustainability, and community well-being. These scenarios consider various approaches to transforming degraded urban areas into functional green spaces that provide ecological, economic, and social benefits. The state of the open green spaces that are examined is considered open lands without existing equipment, greenery, etc. The general assumptions considered for the adaptation scenarios are presented in the following subsection. Further, specific assumptions are presented in Annex 1.

5.2.2. Identification of costs and benefits

The **Green Infrastructure Valuation Toolkit (GI-Val)**, developed by the Mersey Forest (The Mersey Forest et al., 2010), was primarily used for the estimation of the costs and benefits of the CBA. The GI-Val stands out as one of the most comprehensive and user-friendly tools for conducting CBAs of urban green spaces and open parks. This Excel-based toolkit offers a robust framework for assessing the value of green assets or proposed green investments across multiple dimensions.

GI-Val's strength lies in its ability to quantify a wide range of benefits provided by green infrastructure. The toolkit evaluates 11 key benefits, including climate change mitigation, health improvements, and property value enhancement (Allison et al., 2021). This multifaceted approach allows for a more holistic assessment of green spaces, capturing both tangible and intangible benefits that other tools might overlook.

One of GI-Val's distinguishing features is its flexibility in expressing benefits. It provides monetary valuations where possible, quantitative assessments for metrics like job creation or visitor numbers, and qualitative evaluations through case studies and research references (Allison et al., 2021). This versatility makes it particularly suitable for urban planning contexts, where decision-makers often need to consider a diverse array of factors.

GI-Val also allows for:

- A quick comparison of multiple project alternatives.
- Identification of key benefit areas that warrant further investigation.
- Initial stakeholder engagement by demonstrating potential project impacts.

GI-Val provides valuable insights for decision-making about whether to proceed with more detailed planning and analysis. The toolkit assesses the value of green assets or proposed green investments across 11 key benefit categories, while also comparing it with the costs of green infrastructure projects. The benefit categories are the following (The Mersey Forest et al., 2011):

1. Climate change adaptation and mitigation.
2. Flood alleviation and water management.
3. Place and communities.
4. Health and wellbeing.
5. Land and property values.
6. Investment.

7. Labour productivity.
8. Tourism.
9. Recreation and leisure.
10. Biodiversity.
11. Land management.

For each category, the tool considers various costs and benefits, such as (The Mersey Forest et al., 2010; Ecosystems Knowledge Network, n.d.; Allison et al., 2021):

1. Costs:

- Initial investment for creating or improving green infrastructure.
- Ongoing maintenance and management expenses.
- Potential opportunity costs of land (The Mersey Forest et al., 2010; Ecosystems Knowledge Network, n.d.; Allison et al., 2021).

2. Benefits:

- Monetary values derived from economic valuation techniques.
- Quantitative measures such as job creation or visitor numbers.
- Qualitative assessments through case studies or research (The Mersey Forest et al., 2010; Ecosystems Knowledge Network, n.d.; Allison et al., 2021).

The tool allows users to input project-specific data and utilises additional information from key published studies and sources, including the United Kingdom's (UK) Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA), Natural England (government adviser for the natural environment in England), and Forest Research (primary institution in Great Britain focused on forestry and tree research). This approach enables a comprehensive assessment of both direct economic impacts and broader societal and environmental benefits. For example, in the "Land and property values" category, the tool can estimate the potential increase in property values resulting from nearby green spaces. In the "Health and wellbeing" category, it can quantify potential healthcare cost savings due to improved air quality and increased physical activity opportunities. It is important to note that while GI-Val provides a broad value-for-money assessment, it is not intended to replace more rigorous formal project appraisal techniques. The toolkit is designed as an initial, indicative appraisal tool to help stakeholders make informed decisions about green infrastructure investments and to build a case for such investments across a broad range of partners. By considering this wide array of costs and benefits across multiple categories, GI-Val offers a holistic approach to valuing green infrastructure, helping to bridge the gap between the evidence required to increase investment in green spaces and what is practically available (The Mersey Forest et al., 2010; Ecosystems Knowledge Network, n.d.; Allison et al., 2021).

It has to be mentioned that the GI-Val tool contains many libraries and tools to calculate the values which are not possible to be mentioned here due to space limitations. Herein, the main assumptions will be mentioned together with assumptions per category, but the reader who would like to fully understand the process, should download the GI-Val toolkit (The Mersey Forest et al., 2010) and GI-Val toolkit User Manual (The Mersey Forest et al., 2011) and read the present deliverable in parallel.

General assumptions

The main assumptions made were as follows:

- Where default values made sense, they were adopted.
- The state of the examined open green spaces was considered as open lands without existing equipment, greenery, etc.
- All open spaces will be covered by evergreen trees based on the toolkit's default value.
- All the initial calculations with the GI-Val were made in British pounds (£) to avoid mistakes, as this toolkit is set to use this currency. Nevertheless, the final results are presented in Euros (€), using a conversion rate of 1 £ = 1.20 €, valid as of November 30, 2024 (Wise, 2024).

The specific assumptions made for project data, the benefits per category, and the costs are presented in Annex 1. Context inputs are not mentioned in this deliverable as these are only informative and do not affect the values.

The above assumptions led to the results presented in section 5.3. On one hand, costs are presented in terms of capital costs, management and maintenance costs, and aggregate costs, reflecting the gross-value added (GVA) to Piran's economy in present terms. On the other hand, benefits are shown in present terms for the 11 previously mentioned benefit categories, indicating the corresponding GVA, Land and property value, and Other economic value. These three figures should not be added together, as they represent different kinds of value for different stakeholder groups. Only the GVA should be used combined with the total investment to reach a positive or negative NPV value for Piran's economy as a whole. Nevertheless, the other values can be considered qualitatively, as a municipality should also be interested in the well-being of its inhabitants in terms of both economic benefit and liveability.

In order to have an easily comprehensible deliverable, the summaries of the costs and benefits are presented per park.

5.2.3. Temporal horizon

A period of 42 years was used, again in accordance with the other SCORE CBAs, in order to produce comparable results. This period is deemed appropriate for the current CBA, as it spans a sufficiently long period of time to account for the project's benefits, without extending too far into the future, where developing realistic climate change or policy prioritisation scenarios becomes more challenging. Therefore, the base year is 2024 (investment year or year 0), and the CBA extends to 2065 (41 more years).

5.2.4. Discount rate

The base discount rate that was used in the CBA is 3%, in accordance with the discount rate used in all SCORE CBAs. Moreover, the sensitivity analysis applied rates of 1% and 5% to test the robustness of results.

5.3. Results

5.3.1. Kindergarten Park

The summary of the GI-Val toolkit for the Kindergarten Park, using a discount rate of 3% and a time period of 42 years, is provided below.

a) Costs

The total costs for the Kindergarten Park over the entire analysis period amounted to 1.9 million euros in present value (Table 17).

Table 17: Estimation of costs for the Kindergarten Park over a 42-year period with a 3% discount rate

No.	Costs groups	Costs subgroups	Gross value added (GVA)
1	1. Capital costs	1.1 Trees	24,155 €
		1.2 Equipment	21,000 €
		1.3 Construction	157,007 €
		1.4 Labor	72,000 €
		1.5 Studies and surveys	13,708 €
		1.6 Overheads and miscellaneous	28,787 €
		Sub-total	316,657 €
2	2. Management and maintenance costs	2.1 Horticultural maintenance	35,912 €
		2.2 Labor	1,389,011 €
		2.3 Utilities	89,707 €
		2.4 Equipment replacement	50,641 €
		2.5 Cleaning	46,011 €
	Sub-total	1,611,282 €	
Total present value of investments			1,927,938 €

b) Benefits

The Kindergarten Park's estimated benefits in present terms were approximately 3.7 million euros in GVA, 2.2 million euros in land and property value, and 1.1 million euros in other economic values (Table 18). The top three contributors to the GVA were Tourism (58% of the total GVA), Land Management (39%), and Labour Productivity (3%). The benefit groups of Health & Well-being, and Recreation & leisure had the highest share of the total of the category "Other economic value" with 65% and 35%, respectively. It should be noted here that the benefits of the category "Places and communities" both in the GVA as well as in the "Other economic value" are indirect and not monetary benefits. These benefits relate to the expected work of volunteers, as well as to an increase in the number of local households with a view of green space. These benefits are therefore considered in the estimation of the GVA and of the "Other economic value" of the project, but are not considered in the calculation of the Net Present Value for the GVA, which relates only to monetary benefits. More information on this can be found in the explanation of the use of the GI-Val tool in Annex 1.

Table 18: Estimation of benefits for the Kindergarten Park over a 42-year period with a 3% discount rate

No.	Benefits groups	Gross value added (GVA)	Land and property value	Other economic value
1	Climate Change Adaptation & Mitigation	0.00 €	n.a.	2,347 €
2	Water management & Flood Alleviation	64.54 €	n.a.	n.a.
3	Place & communities	125,011 €	n.a.	26,753 €

No.	Benefits groups	Gross value added (GVA)	Land and property value	Other economic value
4	Health & Well-being	19,918 €	n.a.	1,098,466 €
5	Land & Property Values	n.a.	2,233,250 €	n.a.
6	Investment	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
7	Labour Productivity	96,993 €	n.a.	n.a.
8	Tourism	2,094,409 €	n.a.	n.a.
9	Recreation & leisure	n.a.	n.a.	587,872 €
10	Biodiversity	n.a.	n.a.	0.17 €
11	Land management	1,404,744 €	n.a.	n.a.
Total economic present value of benefits		3,741,138 €	2,233,250 €	1,127,567 €

Notes: "n.a." stands for "not available"; for a complete overview of how the benefits were estimated, see Table A 1 in Annex 1; the value of recreation and leisure benefits has not been included in the total of the category "other economic value" to avoid a possible risk of double counting with the health and well-being values, due to reduced mortality from increased walking and cycling. More detailed information on this can be found in the GI-Val tool explanation in Annex 1.

As previously mentioned, the three figures – GVA, Land and property value, and Other economic value – should not be added together, as they represent different kinds of value for different stakeholder groups.

The comparison of costs and benefits, based on the application of equation (1), indicates that the **Kindergarten Park's NPV for a temporal period of 42 years and 3% discount rate will amount to 1.8 million euros**. The positive NPV indicates that the investment should be realised, even without counting the benefits of the "Land and property value" and the "Other economic value" benefits groups.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \textit{Kindergarten park NVP} && (1) \\
 & = -\textit{Total present value of investment} \\
 & + \textit{Total economic present value of GVA benefits} \\
 & = -1,927,938.19 \text{ €} + 3,741,138.06 \text{ €} = 1,813,199.87 \text{ €} \Rightarrow \\
 & \textit{Kindergarten park NVP} > 0
 \end{aligned}$$

Finally, it is worth noting **other benefits of the Kindergarten park project that are not expressed in monetary terms**, but can still be quantified as below:

- A 0.22 °C reduction in surface temperature due to the mitigation of the urban heat island effect.
- 66,100 kg of CO₂-equivalent sequestered.
- 46,700 lt of water will be diverted from sewers per year.
- 18.5 more households will have a view of green space.
- 12 new volunteers for several activities (e.g., planting flowers and trees, maintaining cleanliness, organising community events, creating art projects, repairing amenities, supporting wildlife, leading education programs, etc.).
- 0.03 lives will be saved per year.
- 0.01 tonnes of PM2.5 will be removed each year.
- Between 16 and 87 workdays lost will be avoided each year.

- Regarding tourism attraction, it is estimated that the project will bring 4,520 new visitors and create four Full-Time Equivalent (FTE) jobs per year.
- Regarding recreation, the project is expected to serve 43,800 local users and create two FTE jobs per year.

5.3.2. Dog Park

The following is a summary of the GI-Val toolkit for the Dog Park, applying a discount rate of 3% over a 42-year period.

a) Costs

The total costs for the Dog Park over the entire analysis period amounted to 824,148 euros in present value (Table 19).

Table 19: Estimation of costs for the Dog Park over a 42-year period with a 3% discount rate

No.	Costs groups	Costs subgroups	Gross value added (GVA)
1	Capital costs	1.1 Trees	5,312 €
		1.2 Equipment	1,200 €
		1.3 Construction	34,531 €
		1.4 Labor	36,000 €
		1.5 Studies and surveys	3,852 €
		1.6 Overheads and miscellaneous	8,090 €
	Sub-total		88,985 €
2	Management and maintenance costs	2.1 Horticultural maintenance	7,900 €
		2.2 Labor	694,505 €
		2.3 Utilities	19,736 €
		2.4 Equipment replacement	2,894 €
		2.5 Cleaning	10,128 €
	Sub-total		735,163 €
Total present value of investments			824,148 €

b) Benefits

The Dog Park's estimated benefits in present terms were about 1.5 million euros in GVA, 2.2 million euros in land and property value, and 1.1 million euros in other economic values (Table 20). The top contributors to the GVA were Tourism and Land management, both categories representing 48% of the total GVA. Regarding the category "Other economic value", the top contributors for the total value were Health & Well-being (87 %) and Recreation & leisure (13%). As discussed above, more detailed information on the methodology for the estimation of benefits can be found in the GI-Val tool explanation in Annex 1.

Table 20: Estimation of benefits for the Dog Park over a 42-year period with a 3% discount rate

No.	Benefits groups	Gross value added (GVA)	Land and property value	Other economic value
1	Climate Change Adaptation & Mitigation	0.00 €	n.a.	516 €
2	Water management & Flood Alleviation	15 €	n.a.	n.a.

No.	Benefits groups	Gross value added (GVA)	Land and property value	Other economic value
3	Place & communities	31,253 €	n.a.	17,203 €
4	Health & Well-being	4,380 €	n.a.	1,043,430 €
5	Land & Property Values	n.a.	2,162,127 €	n.a.
6	Investment	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
7	Labour Productivity	64,500 €	n.a.	n.a.
8	Tourism	698,141 €	n.a.	n.a.
9	Recreation & leisure	n.a.	n.a.	154,885 €
10	Biodiversity	n.a.	n.a.	0.04 €
11	Land management	702,372 €	n.a.	n.a.
Total economic present value of benefits		1,500,661 €	2,162,127 €	1,061,149 €

Notes: "n.a." stands for "not available"; for a complete overview of how the benefits were estimated, see Table A 1 in Annex 1; the value of recreation and leisure benefits has not been included in the total of the category "other economic value" because of the risk of double counting. As discussed above, more detailed information on the methodology for the estimation of benefits can be found in the GI-Val tool explanation in Annex 1.

The comparison of the costs and benefits was made through the application of the following equation, where only the benefits associated with the GVA were computed. The results show that the **Dog Park's NPV for a period of 42 years and a 3% discount rate amounts to 675.5 thousand euros**, indicating that the investment should be realised, even without counting the benefits of the "Land and property value" and the "Other economic value" benefits groups.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Dog Park NVP} &= -\text{Total present value of investment} && (2) \\
 &+ \text{Total economic present value of GVA benefits} \\
 &= -824,148.30 \text{ €} + 1,500,660.99 \text{ €} = 676,512.69 \text{ €} \Rightarrow
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Dog Park NVP} > 0$$

In terms of **other benefits not quantified in monetary terms**, the Dog Park's project is estimated to contribute to:

- A 0.05 °C surface temperature reduction with the mitigation of the urban heat island effect.
- A total of 14,500 kg/CO₂-equivalent sequestered.
- 10,300 lt of water diverted from sewers per year.
- 11.9 more households will have a view of green space.
- Three new volunteers for several actions (e.g., planting flowers and trees, maintaining cleanliness, organising community events, creating art projects, repairing amenities, supporting wildlife, leading education programs, etc.).
- 0.02 lives will be saved per year.
- Between 11 and 58 workdays lost will be avoided each year.
- Regarding tourism attraction, it is estimated that the project will bring 1,510 new visitors and create one FTE job per year.

- Regarding recreation, it is estimated that the project will serve 29,200 local users and create one FTE job per year.

5.3.3. Maritime Museum Park

The summary of the GI-Val toolkit for the Maritime Museum Park, considering a discount rate of 3% and a temporal period of 42 years, is presented in the following pages.

a) Costs

The total costs for the Maritime Museum Park amounted to 790.7 thousand euros in present value (Table 21).

Table 21: Estimation of costs for the Maritime Museum Park over a 42-year period with a 3% discount rate

No.	Costs groups	Costs subgroups	Gross value added (GVA)
1	Capital costs	1.1 Trees	3,240 €
		1.2 Equipment	600 €
		1.3 Construction	21,060 €
		1.4 Labor	36,000 €
		1.5 Studies and surveys	3,045 €
		1.6 Overheads and miscellaneous	6,395 €
	Sub-total		70,340 €
2	Management and maintenance costs	2.1 Horticultural maintenance	4,804 €
		2.2 Labor	694,505 €
		2.3 Utilities	12,038 €
		2.4 Equipment replacement	2,894 €
		2.5 Cleaning	6,164 €
	Sub-total		720,405 €
Total present value of investments			790,744 €

b) Benefits

Regarding the Maritime Museum Park's estimated benefits in present terms were about 1 million euros in GVA, 2.2 million euros in land and property value, and 1.1 million euros in other economic values (Table 22). The top contributors to the GVA were Land management (73% of the total GVA), and Tourism (24%). Regarding the category "Other economic value", the top contributors for the total value were Health & Well-being (84 %) and Recreation & leisure (16%). As discussed above, more detailed information on the methodology for the estimation of benefits can be found in the GI-Val tool explanation in Annex 1.

Table 22: Estimation of benefits for the Maritime Museum Park over a 42-year period with a 3% discount rate

No.	Benefits groups	Gross value added (GVA)	Land and property value	Other economic value
1	Climate Change Adaptation & Mitigation	0.00 €	n.a.	315 €
2	Water management & Flood Alleviation	9 €	n.a.	n.a.
3	Place & communities	31,253 €	n.a.	8,725 €

No.	Benefits groups	Gross value added (GVA)	Land and property value	Other economic value
4	Health & Well-being	2,672 €	n.a.	1,043,321 €
5	Land & Property Values	n.a.	2,162,127 €	n.a.
6	Investment	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
7	Labour Productivity	32,493 €	n.a.	n.a.
8	Tourism	232,709 €	n.a.	n.a.
9	Recreation & leisure	n.a.	n.a.	195,957 €
10	Biodiversity	n.a.	n.a.	0.02 €
11	Land management	702,372 €	n.a.	n.a.
Total present value of benefits		1,001,507 €	2,162,127 €	1,052,361 €

Notes: "n.a." stands for "not available"; for a complete overview of how the benefits were estimated, see Table A 1 in Annex 1; the value of recreation and leisure benefits has not been included in the total of the category "other economic value" because of the risk of double counting. As discussed above, more detailed information on the methodology for the estimation of benefits can be found in the GI-Val tool explanation in Annex 1.

The costs and benefits were compared using the following equation, which considers only the benefits associated with the GVA. The results show that the **Maritime Museum Park's NPV for a temporal period of 42 years and a 3% discount rate amounts to about 210.8 thousand euros**; therefore, the investment should be realised, even without counting the benefits of the "Land and property value" and the "Other economic value" benefits groups.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \textit{Maritime Museum park NVP} && (3) \\
 & = -\textit{Total present value of investment} \\
 & + \textit{Total economic present value of GVA benefits} \\
 & = -790,744.20 \text{ €} + 1,001,506.86 \text{ €} = 210,762.66 \text{ €} \Rightarrow
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\textit{Maritime Museum park NVP} > 0$$

Finally, there are **other benefits associated with the Maritime Museum Park that are not quantified in monetary terms**, notably:

- A 0.03 °C surface temperature reduction with the mitigation of the urban heat island effect.
- A total of 8,860 kg/CO₂-equivalent sequestered.
- 6,250 lt of water diverted from sewers per year.
- 6.03 more households will have a view of green space.
- Three new volunteers (e.g., planting flowers and trees, maintaining cleanliness, organising community events, creating art projects, repairing amenities, supporting wildlife, leading education programs, etc.).
- 0.02 lives will be saved per year.
- Between five and 29 workdays lost will be avoided each year.
- Regarding tourism attraction, it is estimated that the project will bring 503 new visitors, whereas no FTE job was estimated to be created per year.
- Regarding recreation, it is estimated that the project will serve 14,600 local users and create one FTE job per year.

5.3.4. Olive Trees Park

The summary of the GI-Val toolkit for the Olive Trees Park, considering a discount rate of 3% and a temporal period of 42 years, is presented as follows.

a) Costs

The total costs for the Olive Trees Park over the entire analysis period amounted to 4.2 million euros in present value (Table 23).

Table 23: Estimation of costs for the Olive Trees Park over a 42-year period with a 3% discount rate

No.	Costs groups	Costs subgroups	Gross value added (GVA)
1	Capital costs	1.1 Trees	105,816 €
		1.2 Equipment	49,200 €
		1.3 Construction	687,804 €
		1.4 Labor	216,000 €
		1.5 Studies and surveys	52,941 €
		1.6 Overheads and miscellaneous	111,176 €
		Sub-total	1,222,937 €
2	Management and maintenance costs	2.1 Horticultural maintenance	157,305 €
		2.2 Labor	2,083,516 €
		2.3 Utilities	392,974 €
		2.4 Equipment replacement	118,645 €
		2.5 Cleaning	201,580 €
		Sub-total	2,954,021 €
Total present value of investments			4,176,958 €

a) Benefits

The Olive Trees Park's estimated benefits in present terms were about 7.3 million euros in GVA, 2.5 million euros in land and property value, and 1.3 million euros in other economic values (Table 24). The top contributors to the GVA were Tourism (67% over the total GVA) and Land management (30%). With respect to the category "Other economic value", the top contributors for the total value were Health & Well-being (60 %) and Recreation & leisure (39%). As discussed above, more detailed information on the methodology for the estimation of benefits can be found in the GI-Val tool explanation in Annex 1.

Table 24: Estimation of benefits for the Olive Trees Park over a 42-year period with a 3% discount rate

No.	Benefits groups	GVA value	Land and property value	Other economic value
1	Climate Change Adaptation & Mitigation	0.00 €	n.a.	10,306 €
2	Water management & Flood Alleviation	292 €	n.a.	n.a.
3	Place & communities	292,939 €	n.a.	47,452 €
4	Health & Well-being	90,872 €	n.a.	1,206,305 €
5	Land & Property Values	n.a.	2,517,741 €	n.a.

No.	Benefits groups	GVA value	Land and property value	Other economic value
6	Investment	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
7	Labour Productivity	129,000 €	n.a.	n.a.
8	Tourism	4,654,228 €	n.a.	n.a.
9	Recreation & leisure	n.a.	n.a.	783,829 €
10	Biodiversity	n.a.	n.a.	0.75 €
11	Land management	2,107,116 €	n.a.	n.a.
Total economic present value of benefits		7,274,447 €	2,517,741 €	1,264,064 €

Notes: "n.a." stands for "not available"; for a complete overview of how the benefits were estimated, see Table A 1 in Annex 1; the value of recreation and leisure benefits has not been included in the total of the category "other economic value" because of the risk of double counting. As discussed above, more detailed information on the methodology for the estimation of benefits can be found in the GI-Val tool explanation in Annex 1.

The costs and benefits were compared using the following equation, focusing solely on the benefits related to the GVA. The results show that the **Olive Trees Park's NPV for a period of 42 years and a 3% discount rate amounts to approximately 3.1 million euros**. The positive NPV shows that the investment should be realised, even without including the benefits from the "Land and property value" and "Other economic value" groups.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Olive Trees park NVP} && (4) \\
 & = -\text{Total present value of investment} \\
 & + \text{Total economic present value of GVA benefits} \\
 & = -4,176,958.08 \text{ €} + 7,274,446.66 \text{ €} = 3,097,488.58 \text{ €} \Rightarrow \\
 & \text{Olive Trees park NVP} > 0
 \end{aligned}$$

In terms of **other benefits not quantified in monetary terms**, the Olive Trees Park's project is estimated to contribute to:

- A 0.96 °C surface temperature reduction with the mitigation of the urban heat island effect.
- A total of 289,000 kg/CO₂-equivalent sequestered.
- 206,000 lt of water diverted from sewers per year.
- 31.5 more households will have a view of green space.
- 27 new volunteers (e.g., planting flowers and trees, maintaining cleanliness, organising community events, creating art projects, repairing amenities, supporting wildlife, leading education programs, etc.).
- 0.03 lives will be saved per year.
- 0.01 tonnes of NO₂, 0.02 tonnes of O₃, and 0.03 tonnes of PM_{2.5} will be removed each year.
- Between 22 and 115 workdays lost will be avoided each year.
- Regarding tourism attraction, it is estimated that the project will bring 10,100 new visitors and create eight FTE jobs per year. Regarding recreation, it is estimated that the project will serve 58,400 local users and create three FTE jobs per year.

5.3.5. Sensitivity analysis

In this section, the results of a sensitive analysis will be performed for the following scenarios:

1. For a discount rate of 1% instead of 3%.
2. For discount rate of 5% instead of 3%.
3. For a disaster event, that means a complete reconstruction of the parks in year 21.
4. The initial scenario of a 3% discount without a disaster will also be presented for comparison.

Table 25 presents the NPV results for the four scenarios. As previously mentioned, the computation of benefits was made by including only the GVA, excluding the benefits of “Land and property value” and the “Other economic value”. With those added, the results would be even more beneficial.

The results indicate that the construction of the parks seems to be resilient to any type of scenario. Both in the case of a discount rate of 1% and 5%, the NPVs are positive, and the parks should be constructed. This is also the case for the disaster scenario. Even in case there is a disaster, and the parks need to be completely reconstructed from scratch during these 42 years, the NPVs are positive, and the decision should be to be reconstructed. Finally, the coefficient of variation (CV), with percentages ranging from 28.7% to 37.6%, indicates a moderate sensitivity of the results to changes in the scenarios.

Table 25: Four scenarios for the sensitivity analysis

Kindergarten Park				
Scenario	Costs (present value)	Benefits (present value)	NPV	Coefficient of variation (CV; %)
1. DR of 1%	-2,577,396 €	5,291,365 €	2,713,970 €	28.7%
2. DR of 5%	-1,529,996 €	2,795,087 €	1,265,091 €	
3. Complete reconstruction of the parks in year 21 following a disaster event	-2,108,523 €	3,741,138 €	1,632,615 €	
4. Initial scenario (3% DR with no disaster)	-1,927,938 €	3,741,138 €	1,813,200 €	
Dog Park				

Scenario	Costs (present value)	Benefits (present value)	NPV	Coefficient of variation (CV; %)
1. DR of 1%	-1,120,470 €	2,127,213 €	1,006,744 €	32.9%
2. DR of 5%	-642,583 €	1,118,672 €	476,089 €	
3. Complete reconstruction of the parks in year 21 following a disaster event	-874,895 €	1,500,661 €	625,766 €	
4. Initial scenario (3% DR with no disaster)	-824,148 €	1,500,661 €	676,513 €	
Maritime Museum Park				
Scenario	Costs (present value)	Benefits (present value)	NPV	Coefficient of variation (CV; %)
1. DR of 1%	-1,081,117 €	1,425,790 €	344,673 €	37.6%
2. DR of 5%	-612,824 €	743,437 €	130,613 €	
3. Complete reconstruction of the parks in year 21 following a disaster event	-830,858 €	1,001,507 €	170,649 €	
4. Initial scenario (3% DR with no disaster)	-790,744 €	1,001,507 €	210,763 €	
Olive Trees Park				
Scenario	Costs (present value)	Benefits (present value)	NPV	Coefficient of variation (CV; %)
1. DR of 1%	-5,367,632 €	10,263,272 €	4,895,640 €	35.8%
2. DR of 5%	-3,447,396 €	5,448,824 €	2,001,428 €	
3. Complete reconstruction of the parks in year 21 following a disaster event	-4,874,382 €	7,274,447 €	2,400,065 €	
4. Initial scenario (3% DR with no disaster)	-4,176,958 €	7,274,447 €	3,097,489 €	

6. BEACH AND DUNES VALUATION AND MANAGEMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF COASTAL EROSION IN SLIGO

6.1. Study area and research objectives

More than 24% of the world's sandy beaches are experiencing net erosion higher than 0.5 m/year due to sea level rise, creating socioeconomic vulnerability (Pais-Barbosa et al., 2023). This is also the case of Ireland's coastal areas, which are undergoing increased rates of erosion due to rising sea levels, storm surge frequencies, reduced sediment delivery to the coast, and degradation from human activities (Roebeling et al., 2013). This problem has been a cause of increasing concern to local municipalities, farmers, landowners and residents in coastal areas across Ireland, especially Sligo County, as has been indicated through numerous reports (SCC, 2024).

Coastal habitats, such as beaches and dunes, offer vital ecosystem services, including coastal protection, support for recreational activities, carbon sequestration, water quality enhancement, and biodiversity conservation. A recent EPA study valued Irish coastal ecosystems at 2.57 billion euros per year and highlighted the important role of dunes in controlling coastal erosion and protecting low lying coastal areas from flooding in Ireland (EPA, 2018). However, according to projections from Paprotny et al. (2018), by 2100, the annual loss of ecosystem services due to coastal erosion in Ireland could amount to the equivalent of 0.3% of the country's 2018 GDP.

This case study examines the coastal area of County Sligo, with a particular focus on three beaches: Strandhill, Streedagh, and Enniscrone (Figure 20; Figure 21). According the 2022 Census, Sligo's County had a population of 70,198 people, with the town serving as its urban centre with 20,608 residents.¹² The total area of the county is 1,837 km², and the coastline is 180 km long (SCC, 2024). Beaches play a key role in supporting recreational activities and generating tourism revenue for the county. The top recreational activities include surfing, swimming, dog-walking, camping and caravan-parking (SCC, 2024). The total beach area is approximately 176.7 hectares (ha) at Strandhill, 407.4 ha at Streedagh, and 146.7 ha at Enniscrone (Table 26). Strandhill has the largest dune area, but all three sites feature highly dynamic dune systems, dominated by vegetation such as marram grass. The study sites were selected based on growing concerns about erosion from residents, the presence of existing sand dunes and ongoing dune management, a knowledge gap due to the lack of monitoring, stakeholder relationships through the CCLL, and the availability of baseline data.

¹² <https://www.cso.ie/en/csolatestnews/pressreleases/2023pressreleases/pressstatementcensusofpopulation2022-summaryresultssligo/>;
<https://www.cso.ie/en/csolatestnews/pressreleases/2023pressreleases/pressstatementcensus2022resultsprofile1-populationdistributionandmovementssligo/>.

Figure 20: Map of study sites in Sligo County (Ireland)

Source: Own elaboration based on Google Earth data.

Figure 21: Images of the beach sites

Enniscrone

Strandhill

Streedagh

Source: <https://www.discoverireland.ie/>.

Table 26: Estimated areas for the beach sites

Beach site	Total beach area (2024; m ²) ^a	Dune area (2004-2006; m ²) ^b	% of dune area over the total
Strandhill	1,767,215	1,140,183	64.5%
Streedagh	4,073,600	1,043,050	25.6%
Enniscrone	1,467,222	423,352	28.9%

Sources: ^a Due to the lack of available data, estimates were made using Google Earth by tracing beach boundaries and measuring the area based on 2024 satellite images. ^b Data corresponding to 2004-2006 surveys from the National Parks & Wildlife Service: <https://www.npws.ie/maps-and-data/habitat-and-species-data/article-17/2019/habitats/dunes-habitats>.

Note: Although the area estimates are from different years, the percentage of dune area relative to the total is included in the table to provide an indication of the potential dunes' relative size.

This study explores the concept of EBA within the context of beach and dunes management as a strategy to mitigate and prevent coastal erosion in County Sligo. Under this approach, measures such as fencing or (re-)vegetation can help protect the beach and surrounding coastal areas from erosion and inundation. A natural sandy shoreline is a resilient and adaptive structure, responsive to changes in forcing conditions, which helps minimise the impact of hydrodynamic events (Hanley et al., 2014). The same study argues that grey infrastructure solutions can be detrimental to the integrity of coastal sandy habitats, as they can harm the local biodiversity and ecology, alter the beach morphology and, in some cases, exacerbate erosion. Accordingly, the main objectives

of this analysis were to conduct a monetary valuation of important ecosystem services provided by the beaches and dunes—coastal protection, carbon sequestration, and recreational support—within the context of shoreline evolution, incorporating the effect of sea level rise. These ecosystem services were selected based on stakeholder discussions with coastal communities during a participatory MCA conducted prior to this research (Tiwari et al., 2024), site-specificities, available literature, and are rooted in the principles of co-creation in the CCLL. This study aims to improve existing knowledge about beach and dunes management’s role in addressing coastal erosion; to identify and discuss better management practices; to contribute towards the engagement of local stakeholders in coastal management activities; and to inform policymakers, promoting the uptake of EBA in local planning.

The main methodological components of this study include:

1. Ecological mapping of the three beach sites to characterise the types of dunes, management strategies, climate change and other anthropogenic-based impacts, and the ecosystem services provided.
2. Estimation of shoreline evolution projections from 2024 to 2044.
3. Performing a Benefit Transfer (BT) approach to monetarily value the benefits associated with the study areas, which include the ecosystem services of coastal protection, carbon sequestration and support of recreational activities, and subsequently establishing a general comparison with the costs of sand dune management.
4. Outline potential beach and dune management practices to counteract coastal erosion.

6.2. Methodology

This section describes the main methodological steps concerning the ecological mapping of beaches, shoreline evolution modelling, and monetary valuation of ecosystem services.

6.2.1. Ecological mapping of beaches

This methodological step involved working with local ecologists to characterise the sand dunes on the three sites in Sligo, including conducting various field visits between November 2023 to February 2024. This action involved collecting data on the impact of human activities and climate change on the beach and dunes, noting any pre-existing EBA or grey infrastructure, documenting cultural or socioeconomic features of significance, and identifying unique natural features such as rivers and rocky shores, among other aspects. Key features were mapped at each beach site, including areas of highest human activity and recreational value, regions most affected by erosion and climate change, various dune types, and the morphological and ecological characteristics of the beaches. Existing GIS data from local authorities' reports were also utilised, along with data collected during site visits.

6.2.2. Shoreline evolution modelling

This activity involved developing models to study erosion/accretion per beach transect and season on three study sites in Sligo County. Data from Landsat 5, 6 and 7 (1999-2017; with 30-50 metres resolution) and Sentinel 2 (2018 onwards; with 10 metres resolution) was used for future projections, in order to estimate the area of land lost due to erosion. The Digital Shoreline Analysis System (DSAS) technique and the Kalman filter were applied for the analysis of shorelines, to detect the area that will be lost/gained between 2024 and 2044.

This modelling process presented several challenges: (i) Data gaps, due to difficulty in integrating data from heterogenous sources. Common obstacles in data standardisation include inaccessible or insufficient local data, and the quality of the validation process (Brenner et al., 2010); (ii) Due to weather conditions like cloud cover, there were

data gaps that reduced the quality of the information; (iii) Difficulties in projecting sand dunes changes over time, due to limited understanding of dune-trends, and the limited timeframe of available historical data. These challenges were somewhat mitigated through validation of results through site-visits.

6.2.3. Monetary valuation of ecosystem services

Monetary valuation methods can be applied to analyse the extent to which ecosystem services contribute to societal wellbeing, and the willingness of individuals and groups to pay for these services (Koetse et al., 2015). Ecosystem service valuation helps compare natural capital with physical and human capital, monitor the quantity and quality of natural resources over time, assess their contribution to societal welfare, and support project evaluations to ensure its sustainability (Liu et al., 2010).

In the present study, a benefit transfer (BT) – or environmental value transfer – approach was used for the monetary valuation of three ecosystem services associated with the study areas. BT involves adapting existing studies that provide monetary estimates of ecosystem services to new policy contexts with limited data. Techniques commonly used in BT include: a) extrapolating benefit-estimates from one site to another; b) transferring economic functions of benefits between sites; c) conducting meta-analysis, including finding independent studies related to the topic; and d) preference calibration, which combines existing benefit-estimates (Roebeling et al., 2013). This case study uses a unit value transfer approach, applying the findings from other studies to the study areas in Sligo. Tables A2-A4 in the Appendix section list the studies consulted for the analysis. More information on the implementation of the methodological approach for each ecosystem service, along with the corresponding results, is provided in Section 6.3.3.

6.3. Results

6.3.1. Ecological mapping of beaches

Dune systems are in a constant state of change and maintaining this natural dynamism is essential to ensure the health of the dune system and its ability to offer coastal protection (NPWS, 2015). In Ireland, there are nine sand dune habitats listed under the EU Habitat Directive¹³, including dynamic areas at the front and stabilised parts at the back of dune systems. All dune habitats occur as a mosaic of evolving vegetation communities, that are inextricably linked and should be regarded as a single geomorphological unit (NPWS, 2015). The following pages provide a detailed characterisation of the three beach sites.

a) Strandhill: Embryonic Shifting Dunes, Marram Dunes, Fixed Dunes, Dunes with Creeping Willow, Dune Slacks

Strandhill is the busiest beach in Sligo County, attracting a high number of visitors. This is due to its proximity to Sligo town, and the presence of recreational infrastructure such as cafes and restaurants. The embryonic dunes have disappeared on this beach, exposing the dune system to heavy erosion. The main causes of this erosion are pressure from human activities on the ground, climate change, and the presence of a rock armour.

While the area near the car park is experiencing significant dune erosion due to human pressures, the fixed dunes farther from the car park remain relatively undisturbed by human activity and are protected by marram grass and other vegetation. The section north of the carpark is experiencing accelerated loss of large, fixed dunes along the foreshore due to the placement of the rock armour. This structure has helped protect human infrastructure but has

¹³ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/nature-and-biodiversity/habitats-directive_en.

also contributed to increased erosion in certain areas of the beach and caused a general sinking of the sand bed, further exacerbating the effects of sea level rise.

The low fixed dunes are lost due to the incursion of the sea and rocks, driven in with force from the energy of the open ocean. Several parts of the beach have been impacted by wave activity, also causing dune erosion. The dunes in front of houses and the caravan park are increasingly degraded. Storms have also caused much degradation and are changing the way the estuary functions. The community-owned local golf club owns most of the beach and dunes and has transformed a large area of land for golf use, contributing significantly to the local economy. The dunes provide crucial protection to the golf course. However, a substantial portion of the fixed dunes on this site has historically been lost to the sea. These details are illustrated in Figure 22.

Figure 22: Ecological map of Strandhill Beach

Source: Own elaboration based on data from the National Parks & Wildlife Service (<https://www.npws.ie/>) and field surveys.

b) Streedagh: Embryonic shifting dunes, Marram dunes, Fixed dunes, Humid dunes

Streedagh is the most rural of the selected sites and features a parking lot near the lagoon, at the entrance to the beach. This area is also the most vulnerable, primarily due to human impact. Near the car park, there are semi-eroded farmlands with some marram grass.

The dunes are extensively exposed to, and beaten up by, storms, which are expected to become more frequent with climate change. A narrow driveway built on the beach, used by landowners and the local council to access the dunes, constitutes a human pressure on the area. Another reason for erosion is the significant wind and wave impact on this beach, which has caused the fixed dunes to deteriorate. There is limited presence of embryonic dunes, with stones underneath. Stones wash up on the beach due to natural processes, and storms can pull out stones from underneath dunes, disturbing the sand. The embryonic dunes at the end of the beach are protected by small patches of marram grass and will eventually develop into marram dunes. However, they are unlikely to become fixed dunes due to the influence of strong currents. Human activity such as grazing of cows and camping fire rigs has also impacted the dunes.

Certain parts of the dune system are better protected by offshore rocks, particularly towards the northern end of the beach. Additionally, landowners have placed straw bales as an EBA measure to protect the dunes from erosion. However, this has unintentionally introduced invasive plant species, such as dandelion, white clover, and red fescue. One concern is that if the roots of these plants grow too deep, they can turn the sand into soil. Figure 23 presents the map of Streedagh.

Figure 23: Ecological map of Streedagh Beach

Source: Own elaboration based on data from the National Parks & Wildlife Service (<https://www.npws.ie/>) and field surveys.

c) Enniscrone: Marram dunes, Fixed dunes

Enniscrone has the healthiest dune system across the three beach sites. This is possibly due to the orientation of the beach, which refracts the waves, reducing the beach's exposure to direct open waves. The dune system begins near the car park, which contains fixed dunes. Whilst one side of the car park has a rock armour that provides coastal protection, the other side has a small stream and a caravan park protected by coastal dunes. The dune system consists of fixed dunes that are rich in biodiversity in certain areas, but some sections have suffered significant erosion from storm blowouts and have been partially affected by human activities, such as the construction of firepits and camping.

One of the most important impacts of climate change is the increase in wind pressure. Although a medium level of wind pressure is necessary for bringing sand and nutrients to keep the dunes healthy, too much pressure can cause erosion. There are certain areas where the dunes are in the process of becoming fixed dunes from embryonic dunes, also known as semi-fixed dunes, and these are increasingly exposed to wind pressures.

In several sections, the dune system is compact with no shingles or cobbles. There is a pedestrian path that crosses the fixed dunes, containing wooden fencing as part of dune management strategies. Towards the end of the beach, there are windmills, and big dune hills containing intensive fencing work. Moreover, a significant part of the fixed dune area consists of the local golf course, where the land has been converted, creating a clear distinction between managed and unmanaged dunes. This impacts biodiversity, as different types of species are attracted to different types of dunes. Enniscrone beach also has patches of dune grassland and moss. These details are illustrated in Figure 24.

Figure 24: Ecological map of Enniscrone Beach

Source: Own elaboration based on data from the National Parks & Wildlife Service (<https://www.npws.ie/>) and field surveys.

6.3.2. Shoreline erosion and future scenarios

Our study estimated the erosion on beaches, which are subject to climate change impacts (e.g., sea level rise, storm damage, erosion, etc.) and intensive human activities, contributing to shoreline retreat and beach area loss. This study focused on shoreline erosion in general, rather than specifically addressing dune erosion. However, different methodologies can estimate dune erosion based on shoreline recession. For example, studies have calculated dune erosion by analysing shoreline recession during 100-year storm events using shore slopes (Enriquez et al., 2019). Therefore, future research could apply the results presented below to estimate dune erosion at these sites as well.

Results presented in Table 27 and **Error! Reference source not found.** show future projections of erosion of 547,412 m² at Strandhill, 318,566 m² at Streedagh, and accretion of 85,354 m² at Enniscrone, between 2024 and 2044. This indicates that Enniscrone has the healthiest dune system, with effective succession from embryonic to semi-fixed to fixed dunes, creating a resilient shoreline which may cope better with coastal erosion in the future. In contrast, Strandhill and Streedagh beaches—particularly Strandhill, which is associated with the largest relative loss compared to 2024—are likely to experience widespread erosion along much of their lengths, emphasizing the urgent need for beach and dune erosion prevention.

Table 27: Projected historical and future area change at the study sites

Beach site	Future area change (m ² ; 2024-2044)	% change relative to the total area from 2024	Annual average change in area (m ² ; 2024-2044)*
Strandhill	-547,412	-31%	-27,370.6
Streedagh	-318,566	-7.8%	-15,928.3
Enniscrone	+173,027	+11.8%	8,651.4

Note: * The projections estimate the area for specific points in time, particularly for the years 2024 and 2044. However, for the purpose of monetary valuation in the following sections, a constant annual average area change was assumed. The year 2024 serves as the base year, with changes in area considered only for the subsequent years.

Figure 25: Projected Shoreline Evolution at the study sites

Source: Own elaboration using Google Earth data and results from shoreline projections.

6.3.3. Economic valuation of ecosystem services

This section presents the monetary valuation of coastal protection, carbon sequestration, and recreation, based on the projected future changes in area at the study sites discussed earlier.

a) Coastal protection

Defining coastal protection: Coastal protection is a particularly valuable ecosystem service provided by sandy ecosystems, especially in the face of storms, floods, and sea level rise. Measuring the coastal protective properties of shorelines involves understanding the relationship between the beach morphology, the dunes' shapes and sizes, and wave attenuation, especially for addressing coastal hazards (Barbier et al., 2011).

Protection against coastal erosion comprises two components. One on hand, the sand-mass that acts as a barrier against waves and water and, on the other, its maintenance through additional sand, enabling the capacity of dunes and other sandy areas to cope with sea level rise. The monetary valuation of the former component involves calculating infrastructural damage costs through erosion, whereas the latter can be calculated through the replacement costs of dune nourishment, with annual sand accumulation acting as a metric for quantifying coastal protection (Van der Biest et al., 2017). Certain types of vegetation require a particular amount of sand deposit each year, or soil may develop whilst marram grass degenerates (Van der Biest et al., 2017). Coastal protection can be valued by multiplying the surface area covered by dynamic dunes (which accumulate fresh sand along the shoreline) with the annual sedimentation rate (Van der Biest et al., 2017). Alternatively, Toimil et al. (2023) suggest an approach based on the avoided damage cost method, which acknowledges that erosion protection is dependent on the shoreline response to coastal dynamics, involving modelling. Additionally, Jimenez et al. (2017) defined the optimum beach-width as an indicator of coastal protection, being a vital criterion in dissipating storm-

energy during the return period. Considering the Catalan coast, optimum beaches were defined in the previous study as those wider than the expected storm-induced erosion, with return periods of 25-50 years.

Value of dune nourishment: Our study adopts an approach inspired by Van der Biest et al. (2017), using the cost of dune nourishment as a proxy to estimate the future costs needed to maintain or restore coastal protection. To this end, we apply the value of 8 euros/m²/year, which reflects the estimated average dune maintenance costs across various countries, covering expenses for sand, labor, and vegetation. This value was then adjusted using the Consumer Price Index in Ireland, bringing it to 9.76 euros/m² at the 2024 price level.

Considering future projections (2024-2044), the losses in coastal protection value for Strandhill and Streedagh beaches amount to approximately 5.3 and 3.1 million euros respectively, in 2024 monetary levels. With a 3% discount rate, these values adjust to about 4 and 2.3 million euros respectively. In contrast, Enniscrone beach is projected to see an increase of 1.7 million euros in coastal protection value between 2024 and 2044, based on 2024 monetary terms. With a 3% discount rate, this value adjusts to 1.3 million euros (Table 28).

Table 28: Monetary valuation of coastal protection at the study sites (2024-2044)

Beach site	Value change	
	Nominal future value estimate (2024 price levels)	Present value estimate (2024) at 3% discount rate*
Strandhill	-5,342,741 €	-3,974,325 €
Streedagh	-3,109,204 €	-2,312,855 €
Enniscrone	+1,688,743 €	+1,256,212 €

*Note: * These estimates were made based on the annual average change in area assumed for the study sites (Table 27).*

b) Valuation of carbon sequestration

Defining carbon sequestration: In Ireland, coastal sand dunes have a total land area of about 12,013 hectares and absorb approximately 2.1 tonnes of carbon per hectare per year (Jones et al., 2008; EPA, 2018). Carbon stock refers to carbon stored in the biosphere, while carbon sequestration is the rate of capture and long-term storage of atmospheric carbon dioxide (Drius et al., 2016). Our study uses estimates of carbon sequestration, quantified through empirical field measurements in different parts of Europe. Van der Biest et al. (2017) determined carbon sequestration by measuring the total amount of carbon stored in the upper first meter of the soil, considering the soil profile characteristics and land use type. Annual sequestration was calculated by dividing the stored carbon by a period of 100 years. The values obtained from this study, based on Belgian field measurements, compare relatively well with the estimates in Beaumont et al. (2014), who analysed mean sequestration rates in the upper 15 cm of the soil over 160 years in coastal dunes in the United Kingdom. Similarly, Drius et al. (2016) collected soil samples with a 15 cm-deep core and 5 cm diameter from the Italian Adriatic coastal dunes, estimating long term carbon sequestration (1954-2006.) The estimates from these three studies have informed benefit transfer in our research.

Monetary value from carbon sequestration: The benefits from carbon storage are valued monetarily based on literature on the socioeconomic costs of carbon and European guidelines on carbon pricing (Van der Biest et al., 2017). The benefits are related to avoided damages from climate change, which involves assumptions, but can be quantified as the marginal benefits of meeting greenhouse gas reduction targets (Van der Biest et al., 2017). Beaumont et al. (2014) estimated the average monetary value from carbon sequestration from dunes at 25-55 euros per hectare per year in the UK. Drius et al. (2014) reported a range of values for carbon sequestration in dunes: 30-

60 euros tonne/ha for mobile dunes, 25-65 euros tonne/ha for semi-fixed dunes, and 30-72 euros tonne/ha for fixed dunes, assuming the cost of carbon per tonne at 73 euros. These values align with those from Beaumont et al. (2014), though Drius et al. (2014) focused on dune categories similar to those in our study. Van der Biest et al. (2017) estimated the monetary value of carbon sequestration from embryonic dunes (dynamic) along shoreline at 150 euros per hectare/year, and dunes with grass and moss (fixed) at 220 euros per hectare/year. Based on the estimates from the previous studies, our research applies an average carbon sequestration value for coastal dunes ranging from €45 to €180 per hectare per year, taking into account socioeconomic conditions, carbon sequestration rates, and dune categories. When accounting for inflation, the average value of carbon sequestration corresponds to 142 euros/ha/year (2024). This value will be applied to the changes in dune areas from the three study sites, whether losses or gains, observed between 2004 and 2024. By doing so, we can estimate the corresponding changes in the carbon sequestration value over this period.

Results from benefit transfer: The potential change in carbon sequestration value resulting from future dune area changes (i.e., loss or gain) between 2024 and 2044 is calculated using 2024 monetary values and a 3% discount rate. Results shown in Table 29 reveal minor losses at Strandhill and Streedagh, along with gains in Enniscrone.

Table 29: Monetary valuation of carbon sequestration at the study sites (2024-2044)

Beach site	Dune area change (m ²)*	Value change	
		Nominal future value estimate (2024 price levels)	Present value estimate (2024) at 3% discount rate**
Strandhill	-353,080.74	-5,013.75 €	-3,729.59
Streedagh	-81,552.90	-1,158.05 €	-861.44
Enniscrone	50,004.80	+710.07 €	+528.20

*Note: * The change in dune area was assumed to correspond to 64.5%, 25.6%, and 28.9% of the total beach area change for Strandhill, Streedagh, and Enniscrone, respectively. These percentages represent the proportion of dunes relative to the total beach area, as shown in Table 26; ** These estimates were based on the annual average change in area assumed for the study sites (Table 27).*

c) Valuation of recreation

Ireland's beach areas hold significant recreational value. A cross-country survey conducted in Ireland in 2018 found that 73% of the respondents visited the coastline at least once, and 38% visited the coastline more than ten times during a one-year period (EPA, 2018). Another study estimated that revenue from activities such as camping, surfing, lodging at Strandhill beach could reach 11.5 million euros over the next 100-years, a value at risk of being lost due to erosion (Calder, 2023).

Determining recreational value: This case study examines recreation solely from a welfare perspective, excluding potential revenue generated from recreation and tourism. To assess this value, it utilizes the concept of consumer surplus, which reflects the value that visitors place on their trip to the beach. In the Maharees and Castlegregory communities (County Kerry, Ireland) during summer 2019, a consumer surplus value of 3.09 euros per person per beach visit was estimated, comparing favourably with the values of Mediterranean destinations (Carr, 2020). Moreover, Hynes et al. (2022) estimated the consumer surplus from the Galway Bay Coastal Walk (Ireland) at 11.9 euros per trip. When exploring studies globally, Van der Biest et al. (2017) estimated the consumer surplus at 4.5 euros per visit to Belgian beaches. Based on the average of these estimates, the overall consumer surplus for visiting the beach in our case study is 8.3 euros per person per visit. When adjusted to 2024 price levels, this value increases

to 10.5 euros per person per visit. This figure represents the total value of the beach trip, without accounting for specific recreational activities.

Estimated number of visitors: Specific data on visitors is not available for the study sites. Therefore, two methods were used to estimate this information, based on two types of visitation indicators:

- (i) The **actual annual number of visitors** was estimated by consulting various reports on beach visitation throughout Ireland. Data from Failte Ireland (2019) for the period between 2015 and 2019 show that the average number of visitors in Sligo County beaches was 300 per day in July, across two of the three study sites – Strandhill and Enniscrone – along with the beaches of Mullaghmore and Rosses Point. For the same month, the average daily visitations across 75 coastal tourist sites in Ireland was 194. These figures were assumed to remain valid for 2024. For our analysis, July was selected as the reference month, as it had the most comprehensive data available, providing the most accurate representation. The previously defined figures of 300 and 194 visitors were used as an approximation to the maximum and minimum values for daily visits in July, respectively. In addition to the previous sources, studies on the distribution of visitor percentages throughout the year in North-West Ireland were used to estimate the number of visitors per day and per month, using the July figures as a reference. (EUROSTAT, 2024). Figure 26 presents the results of this extrapolation, showing an approximation of the estimated monthly maximum and minimum number of visitors per beach in Sligo. The total estimated annual visitors per beach ranged from 36,358 to 56,382. While the results specifically represent Sligo County, they could be applicable as a reference for studies across Ireland, as they are based on beach visitation estimates nationwide.

Figure 26: Estimated monthly visitors per beach in Sligo County (2024)

Source: Own elaboration based on data from Failte Ireland (2019) and EUROSTAT (2024).

It is important to note that, due to data limitations, estimating the distribution of visitors across the different study sites is challenging. Assuming an equal distribution of visitors may not accurately reflect actual visitation patterns. For instance, Strandhill Beach attracts a larger number of tourists due to its proximity to Sligo town and its range of recreational amenities, followed by Enniscrone, and then Streedagh, the most rural site. Therefore, to estimate site-specific tourist numbers, the number of

visitors in 2024 was assumed to be directly proportional to the populations of the three coastal towns. Based on this ratio, the estimated annual visitor numbers ranged from 72,660 to 112,650 for Strandhill, 43,596 to 67,590 for Enniscrone, and 21,798 to 33,795 for Streedagh.

To **estimate potential changes in visitor numbers due to climate change**, particularly coastal erosion and subsequent beach area loss, our analysis adopted the approach used by Van der Biest et al. (2017), where is assumed an annual 4% change in visitor numbers for every 10% change in beach area. Based on this assumption, the previous visitation figures, and the projected shoreline changes, Enniscrone beach could have an 11.8% increase in beach area by 2044, resulting in 4.72% increase in visitor numbers (gain of 2,058 to 3,190 visitors by 2044). Streedagh beach could have an 7.8% loss of beach area by 2044, resulting in 3.1% lesser visitors (loss of 680 to 1,054 visitors by 2044). Strandhill beach area could be reduced by 31% between 2024 and 2044, resulting in 12.4% less visitors (less 9,010 to 13,969 visitors by 2044).

- (ii) Another method has been used to **estimate the potential number of visitors at any given time, based on beach area and the beach carrying capacity (BCC)**. Lopez-Doriga et al. (2019) define BCC as the number of visitors that can be accommodated within a given beach area with no negative social consequences or impacts on resources, i.e., the minimum sustainable area per user. In the context of Catalan beaches (Spain), the authors estimated the BCC to range from 4 to 12 m² per user. Zacarias et al. (2011) estimated that the physico-ecological carrying capacity in Praia de Faro in Southern Portugal should be between 1,385 and 2,628 visitors/day, assuming the optimum area available per user to be between 5 to 10 m². This value range was also estimated in Rodella et al. (2019) for the ideal area occupied per tourists in Italian beaches of Romagna and Sardinia. Based on the average of the previous data, the BCC calculated for our study is rounded to 8 m² per user.

Using a BCC of 8 m² per user and the total beach area, the estimated number of visitors at any given time in 2024 is approximately 220,902 for Strandhill, 509,200 for Streedagh, and 183,403 for Enniscrone. Based on projected area changes from 2024 to 2044, these figures are expected to adjust to 152,475, 469,379, and 205,031 for each respective beach by 2044.

The previous two methods present an approximate number of visitors to the beach sites, which is then multiplied by recreational consumer surplus to estimate the ecosystem service value associated with recreation.

Recreational value: Table 30 presents the results for both categories of estimated visitors, including data on the number of visitors and their corresponding recreational welfare value. In the first method, which estimates the actual number of visitors, the total change in recreational value between 2024 and 2044 shows the largest loss in Strandhill (-109,104€) and the greatest gain in Enniscrone (+24,918€). In the second method, which estimates the potential number of visitors at any given time, Strandhill and Streedagh experienced losses of 543,461€ and 311,029€, respectively, while Enniscrone saw a gain of 168,923€.

Table 30: Monetary valuation of recreation in Sligo County (2024-2044)

Year	Indicator	Beach sites		
		Strandhill	Streedagh	Enniscrone
Method 1: Estimation of the actual number of visitors				
2024	Annual No. of visitors	72,660 - 112,650	21,798 - 33,795	43,596 - 67,590

Year	Indicator	Beach sites		
		Strandhill	Streedagh	Enniscrone
Method 1: Estimation of the actual number of visitors				
	Annual recreational value	762,930€ - 1,182,825€	228,879€ - 354,848€	457,758€ - 709,695€
2044	Annual No. of visitors	63,650 – 98,681	21,118 – 32,741	45,654 – 70,780
	Annual recreational value (2024 price level)	668,327€ - 1,036,155€	221,738€ - 343,776€	479,364€ - 743,193€
2024-2044	Total change in recreational value (DR of 3%; present value in 2024)	-70,373€ to -109,104€	-5,312€ to -8,236€	+16,072€ to +24,918€
Method 2: Estimation of the potential number of visitors at any given time				
2024	Potential No. visitors at any given time	220,902	509,200	183,403
	Recreational value	2,319,471€	5,346,600€	1925732
2044	Potential No. visitors at any given time	152,475	469,379	205,031
	Annual recreational value (2024 price level)	1,600,988€	4,928,480€	2,152,826€
2024-2044	Total change in recreational value (DR of 3%; present value in 2024)	-543,461€	-311,029€	+168,923€

6.3.4. Analysis of costs and benefits

Costs of dune management in Sligo: Data procured from the Sligo County Council on price of sand dune management (i.e., installing new fencing or repositioning/repairing/extending existing fencing) indicated that between 2020-2022, the average cost was between 20-32 euros/linear metre in Strandhill and Enniscrone beaches. No such work was carried out in Streedagh. The cost of installing new fencing (120-150 metres in length) was typically between 4,800-5,000 euros and the cost of repairing and extending new fencing (30-40 metres in length), was typically between 600-800 euros. A local report on dune management costs in Rosses Point (Sligo County) estimated the costs between 10-200 euros/linear metre for dune re-profiling, including fencing, planting grass, and other repair costs, especially after storm events (SCC, 2016). Based on this, the cost of dune management comes up to 1.05 euros/m² in 2016, and 1.23 euros/m² in 2024 (adjusted for inflation). Additionally, based on scientific literature, Spurgeon (1999) found that costs of sand dune rehabilitation in Tramore, Ireland was 1.53 euros/m², including replanting marram grass, fencing, sand-trapping, etc. This value corresponds to 2.45 euros/m² when adjusted for 2024 price levels. The average of both these costs is 1.80 euros/m², which will be used in this study. Whilst calculating costs includes factoring in project coordination costs; planning and design costs (e.g., economic appraisal, environmental licenses, data collection, etc.); capital construction costs (e.g., contract payments, supervision, etc.); land or property costs; operation/maintenance costs (e.g., monitoring, replacement and repairs, etc.) (DEFRA, 2015); our data on costs is scarce due to limited monitoring in Sligo.

Comparison of benefits and costs: Assessing the benefits and costs enables a systematic evaluation, and whilst the quality and quantity of this data in Europe has improved, it is still limited (EEA, 2023). Our study did not explicitly model the effects of different beach and dune management options on shoreline preservation and their associated benefits. However, our estimates provide valuable insight into the potential benefits of coastal management. The current aggregate value of ecosystem services was estimated at 10.24€ per square meter (2024 values), which includes the combined values for coastal protection (9.76€/m²), carbon sequestration (0.142€/m²/year), and recreation (0.34€/m²/year, based on the average values estimated for the three beach sites). In comparison, the average cost of dune management in Ireland, as indicated above, is 1.8€ per square meter.

Although not comprehensive, the analysis suggests that the monetary benefits of dune management are nearly six times greater than the associated management costs (Figure 27). Moreover, it is noteworthy that sand dunes provide other ecosystem services like biodiversity conservation, water quality improvement, and more, which have not been included in this study, and could affect the comparison between costs and benefits.

Figure 27: Comparison between ecosystem services values and dune management costs

6.3.5. Dune and beach management recommendations

The threat of flooding and storm generally affects the whole coastline. In contrast, coastal erosion is site-specific and acts on short-and long-term spatiotemporal scales (Debaine and Robin, 2012). Although several traditional protection measures are available to coastal engineers, including revetments, groynes, breakwaters, etc., the best protection against coastal hazards is the quality of the dune system (Debaine and Robin, 2012). A sandy shoreline can adapt in response to climate change, to maintain stability and minimise hydrodynamic effects. For example, sandy beaches respond to wave energy by flattening their profile, which leads to greater transport of sediments offshore, helping bigger waves break easily and reducing the pressure of wave-energy on the shoreline (Hanley et al., 2014). With extremely energetic waves, sediment can be mobilised from beach-dunes, acting as emergency sediment supply and enhancing wave-dissipation (Hanley et al., 2014). Onshore winds can transfer this sediment back to the dunes, creating a dynamic-linked system where tides, waves, current and weather control the sediment, creating a healthy dune system (Hanley et al., 2014). To assess the quality of dunes, it is pertinent to assess its ability to reduce flood risk, shoreline retreat and aeolian erosion. Eroded shores generate narrow embryonic dunes, which are more susceptible to coastal hazards (Dang et al., 2021), and fixing dunes can stabilise the dune system. One of the ways to fix dunes is through marram grass, a fast-growing plant that has deep roots which provide a high amount of nitrogen that improves soil quality for the agricultural development and the nutrient regulation (Dang et al., 2021).

Different dune systems can offer different levels of protection against different coastal hazards, based on how they are managed. Managing dunes requires an understanding of the physical and ecological processes on site and in the wider environment; the risks to humans and natural environment; the effectiveness and consequences of management decisions; and the short-and-long term objectives of the sites (Debaine and Robin, 2012). This includes practices such as sand accumulation; formation of geomorphic features; native vegetation that aids dune formation; sediment accumulation along fence lines to trap wind-blown sand; and building foredune ridges to increase sediment volume (Johnston et al., 2023). These practices can aid the recovery of coastal dunes with minimal human

intervention, following the removal of key stressors (like beach driving, mechanic grooming, dog-walking, invasive species, human activity, raking, irrigation, etc.). Potential dune and beach management practices are presented as follows.

a) Dune management practices

Vegetation: Fernandez-Montblanc et al. (2020) found that vegetation enhances dune stability and reduces erosion in the Adriatic region. While initially, fencing can help trap sand, in the long run studies suggest that natural recovery through native vegetation is the best strategy (Fernandez-Montblanc et al., 2020). The characteristics of sand accretion are often species-dependant, and physical site characteristics, such as salt spray and moisture, can also influence plant zonation on coastal dunes (Johnston et al., 2023). While the ability of dunes to attenuate waves depends on dune geomorphology and sand supply, the presence of vegetation is pivotal as it aids deposition of sand (Hanley et al., 2014). However, it is important to only use native species, as non-native species of vegetation can change dune morphology. Dynamic vegetation like marram grass has great capacity to withstand sand burial, at up to a meter per year (Van der Biest et al., 2017). When sand is deposited, marram shoots rapidly grow through it and the new sediment is held with the roots. In comparison, woody vegetation is more prone to erosion as stems are less flexible and not able to lie flat during high winds (Feagin et al., 2014).

Fencing: Sand fences work by reducing wind speed, enabling the accumulation of sand deposits, and supporting dune species. The spatial arrangement of fencing must create maximum topographic complexity in a restricted area, and be based on rigorous modelling, optimal design and experience (Hanley et al., 2014). On shores with steeply inclined seabeds, fencing may be ineffective due to reduced aeolian transport of sand. The position of fencing has important implications for the dune structure. For example, fencing in the foredune can prevent deposition of sand in the dune behind it, reducing vertical dune-growth (Itzkin et al., 2020). It is important to make fencing decisions contextualised in local knowledge, as dunes fenced ineffectively can erode quicker and may not recover (Itzkin et al., 2020). The orientation of the fencing could affect the dune system. Parallel fencing encourages natural dune morphology compared to angled fences (Grafals-Soto and Nordstrom, 2009). If fencing is placed seaward of the crest of the dune, it must be installed at a 45 degree or greater angle to the shoreline. Each section of fencing must not be longer than ten feet, and sections must be spaced at least seven feet apart on a diagonal alignment, ideally facing the wind direction (Grafals-Soto and Nordstrom, 2009). Sturdy drift fencing is a popular technique, wherein the components are nailed together, and the fence is constructed in a zigzag pattern. Mendelssohn et al. (1991) observed that a straight fence with perpendicular sides spurs the most sand accumulation during the first year; during the second year the zigzag and straight fences accumulate more sand in comparison. The configuration of dune-fencing should be selected based on its short term or long-term objectives.

Sand trapping: Lawlor and Jackson (2022) conducted a study in Maghera (County Donegal) to explore the effects of sand-trapping on the dune system. They found that despite sand trapping, erosion occurred in foredunes over a ten-year period due to storm damage and limited maintenance of the dune site. However, the back dunes still indicated growth, and the dune system remained relatively intact. This intervention was more successful and less expensive than grey infrastructure, that could have been counterproductive due to the risk of destabilisation of sediments. The sand trap worked by harnessing the wind-blown dynamics to accelerate the build of foredunes.

Soil inversion: Bird et al. (2020) argue that substantial dune fixation has resulted in loss of mobile dunes, and removing certain types and amounts of vegetation can improve dune dynamics through reactivation of sand. Fixed dunes are generally the most frequently restored dune type (54%), followed by semi-fixed and mobile dunes. However, the most frequently used restoration mechanism is revegetation (42%), while less than 5% projects focused on vegetation removal (Bird et al., 2020). Evidence suggests that soil processes in fixed dunes can change the soil irreversibly, and removal of vegetation and topsoil in dune slacks and inner dunes might not

have any significant effect. To tackle this, top-soil inversion and ploughing can be effective methods for restoration of inland dunes, as they can lower surface-soil fertility and create a nutrient-poor space of revegetation (Bird et al., 2020).

b) Beach management practices

Beach geomorphology: Sand accretion in dunes varies depending on wind direction, lag surface, effects of perimeter fencing, sediment flux, and aeolian transport (Johnston et al., 2023). A lag surface forms with the wind-driven removal of fine sand and retention of coarser grained sand and pebbles, which can lead to sand accretion. Hanley et al. (2014) found that the ability of dunes to withstand storm damage depends on dune morphology, sediment supply, accumulation, and stabilisation. When sediment delivery rates are high, the foredunes become wider as sand deposits are spread out. In contrast, when sand supply is minimal, dunes become taller as sediment is accumulated over a small area. During negative sand supply, beach erosion creates short narrow dunes that can be easily washed over by waves. In Ireland, beach nourishment has significantly impacted dunes, but cautious consideration of the grain size of sand is important for the technique to be successful.

Beach nourishment: Dynamic dune systems can lose the frontal dunes due to erosion. Parts of the mobilised sand will be blown into the inner dunes, turning them into dynamic systems and allowing the dunes to migrate inland (Van der Biest et al., 2017), and beach nourishment can aid with this. In case of lack of space (such as, due to houses, golf course, etc.), measures like beach nourishment help reactivate the dunes, but dune geomorphology must be considered (Hanley et al., 2014). Aerts (2018) suggest the use of hybrid retention structures such as groins to help capture sand and sustain beach nourishment.

Beach width: Dune stability depends on the complex interaction between the surf zone, the beach and the foredunes. Foredune belts are typically larger on dissipative beaches than on intermediate beaches (Fernandez-Montblanc et al., 2020). Wide beaches enable increased aeolian transport, simultaneously increasing the dissipative morphodynamics and dune height. Additionally, increase in beach width extends the distance between dunes and the sea, enhancing wave energy dissipation during storm events (Fernandez-Montblanc et al., 2020). The dunes' morphological response can often drive shoreline retreat more than sea level rise impact, but remains unaccounted for. Johnston et al. (2023) found that the width of the beach and the surf zone along the beach affect the stability of the dune system.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The following subsections present an overview of the developed study and specific insights derived from the five case studies.

7.1. Overview

This deliverable presented the findings of WP7 Task 7.4, which focused on the socio-economic assessment of adaptation interventions, with particular emphasis on Ecosystem-based Adaptation (EBA). The analysis primarily examined the costs and benefits of EBA measures across four WP7 frontrunner CCLs. The case studies included flood mitigation through floodable parks in Errenteria (Oarsoaldea, Spain), and intermittent river restoration (e.g., embankments, riverbed widening) in Vilanova i la Geltrú (Spain); drought management through the restoration of historic water cisterns, and heatwave mitigation through open-access green spaces in Piran (Slovenia); and, finally, the monetary valuation and management of beaches and dunes in the context of coastal erosion in Sligo County (Ireland). The analyses were dependent on the results of previous SCORE tasks, including task 7.3 within WP7, other WPs, and interactions with stakeholders. The case studies were inspired in the CBA methodology but were allowed flexibility, meaning that some case studies performed partial-CBA analysis or, in the case of Sligo, a non-comprehensive comparison between the monetary values of ecosystem services – coastal protection, carbon sequestration, and recreation – with dune management costs.

Overall, the analyses demonstrated that the assessed measures could be viable options for addressing local climate adaptation challenges, not only in terms of hazard risk reduction and economic efficiency but also due to the additional complementary benefits they offer. By incorporating nature-based elements, these measures have the potential to deliver ecosystem services that are less evident in traditional grey infrastructure. The following sections present detailed insights for each case study, including main findings, limitations and opportunities for improvement.

7.2. Detailed insights

7.2.1. Floodable Park in Errenteria, Oarsoaldea

The experience of “Bakea” floodable park in Oarsoaldea stands out as an example of how nature-based adaptation measures can be cost-effective for reducing flood risks compared to “grey” infrastructure alternatives while providing broader socio-environmental benefits. The ex-post cost–benefit analysis (CBA) reveals that the investment yields a positive net present value (NPV) under conservative discount rates, reinforcing its viability from a financial standpoint. By converting a formerly urbanizable riverine area into a floodable park, the measure has reduced expected average annual losses (AAL) from flood —particularly building and infrastructure losses—while also providing ecological, social, and recreational benefits that typically remain unaccounted in traditional “grey” infrastructure assessments. Rather than rigidly canalizing the river and urbanizing the adjacent area, creating this floodable space has enabled greater resilience to extreme hydrological events, diminishing potential damage to nearby buildings and assets.

From an economic standpoint, and in light of a comparative vision of “grey” infrastructure composed of concrete walls and similar defences, the “Bakea” floodable park shows positive long-term benefit–cost ratios. Recreational opportunities and environmental revitalisation activities generate value that extends beyond mere damage reduction. This perspective, in turn, addresses the broader needs of a territory in which water management faces increasing climate-related threats.

From a technical perspective, the park's effectiveness is supported by two core design features: (i) retention capacity for controlled inundations, especially during peak flow events, and (ii) vegetated surfaces along the Oiartzun River corridor to attenuate runoff velocities. Hydraulic modelling suggests meaningful decreases in average water depth and velocity downstream of the park, translating into a significant reduction in flood damage costs. Although final estimates vary depending on the recurrence intervals analysed, avoided damage consistently surpasses the annualised maintenance costs within the standard 42-year evaluation horizon. Sensitivity analyses of discount rates (e.g., 1% to 5%) and climate change scenarios (RCP 4.5 and 8.5) highlight that the floodable park continues to yield net economic benefits even under more extreme climatic conditions and higher discount factors.

In parallel, literature review further evidence that the ecosystem-based approaches like the park foster local biodiversity, enhance microclimatic conditions, and improve quality of life in the surrounding community. These additional ecosystem services—though not always straightforward to monetize—reinforce the role of floodable parks as cost-effective, multifunctional green infrastructures. Notably, the “Bakea” park avoids other potential downsides associated with “grey” infrastructure, such as channelised flows that can exacerbate downstream flooding, while also delivering intangible benefits related to recreation, aesthetics, and community engagement with nature.

As climate change intensifies the need for robust flood defences, the “Bakea” park offers persuasive evidence that green infrastructure can effectively balance urban development, environmental conservation, and economic viability. Although the current evaluation of the “Bakea” park highlights the importance of nature-based solutions for urban flood risk management, further methodological refinements could help clarify its broader societal value. In particular, a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches would more effectively capture intangible benefits—such as recreation, carbon sequestration, and enhanced quality of life—offering a more complete understanding of the park's overall contribution.

7.2.2. Restoration of an intermittent river in Vilanova i la Geltrú

The proposed restoration of the intermittent river of Torrent de la Piera in Vilanova i la Geltrú has showed to be a cost-efficient adaptation strategy, as demonstrated by the strong positive NPV results. The consideration of earthen embankments, either alone or in combination with riverbed reprofiling, was primarily aimed at reducing flood risk by improving flood conveyance capacity. With the aim of preserving the natural functions of the intermittent river and its connection with the coastal area, the assessed interventions substantially lowered flood exposure and economic losses, particularly for buildings and infrastructure. They demonstrated economic efficiency under both moderate (RCP4.5) and extreme (RCP8.5) climate scenarios over an analysis spanning from 2024 to 2065, when compared to the business-as-usual (BAU) scenario (no adaptation). In economic terms, this involved comparing the implementation and maintenance costs with the benefits, defined as the reduction in average annual losses (AAL) from flood damage to buildings, as well as road and railway networks following the adaptation measures.

The analysis focused on the primary direct benefit identified for climate change adaptation, not accounting for additional benefits worth mentioning, such as biodiversity conservation and enhancement, carbon capture sequestration, and improved landscape aesthetics, among others. These broader benefits were identified by local stakeholders during the MCA workshop held in March 2023, which helped prioritise EBA interventions in this intermittent river in Vilanova i la Geltrú (D7.3; Campos Rodrigues et al. 2023). Additionally, the analysis did not consider indirect impacts from the flooding scenarios, such as traffic disruptions and rerouting due to closed streets, or the potential closure of businesses, among other factors.

When comparing the costs of the proposed interventions with those of similar hard-based measures, potential costs savings can be inferred, although more detailed cost estimates are needed for a more accurate comparison. Taking

the example of the earthen embankment in Zone 5 (see Table 6 and Table 7), the cost per meter of length with a 2-meter elevation ranges from €549.41 to €921.79. In comparison, the construction of a concrete or brick-based vertical floodwall (or T-wall) with a similar 2-meter height is estimated to range between approximately €1,967 and €2,624 per meter of length (Keating et al., 2015)¹⁴.

This study concludes that river protection and restoration practices based on nature-based solutions (NBS) have the potential to be an economically efficient approach, while also offering additional co-benefits that may not be achievable through engineering-based solutions. Nevertheless, it is important to highlight the limitations posed by the lack of available space for intervention adjacent to rivers and streams in many urban areas, due to urban expansion and reduction of permeable soil. Moreover, effective water management and climate change adaptation at the local level, particularly in terms of flood risk mitigation, require a hybrid approach, combining EBA with both hard (e.g., sewage systems, channelised river sections) and soft (e.g., deployment of water monitoring sensors, prevention plans) approaches.

Future research could benefit from several improvements, including a more detailed topographic characterisation of the territory and the inclusion of additional benefits and costs for a comprehensive social CBA approach. Moreover, a better understanding of the hydrological effects of raising dykes in the study area – such as potential downstream and lateral flood risks, as well as the resistance to extreme events – is important, particularly given the area's proximity to residential and commercial zones. These improvements could help reduce the uncertainty surrounding climate change impact and adaptation, favouring the integration of EBA into the overall adaptation approach.

7.2.3. Restoration of historic water cisterns in Piran

The primary objective of the suggested project is to repurpose the historic cisterns of Piran to alleviate pressure on municipal water supplies, enhance local resilience to water scarcity, and promote awareness of water conservation practices. The performed cost-benefit analysis (CBA) focused on three key cisterns: 1st of May Square Cistern, Lighthouse on Punta Cistern, and Old Kindergarten Parish Cistern. These cisterns, originally designed to capture and store rainwater for non-potable uses, offer both functional as well as cultural value in the present-day context of climate change adaptation and water resource management.

The analysis, which was conducted for a 42-year period starting in 2025, compared the implementation and maintenance costs of cistern restoration with the expected direct and indirect benefits. The findings underscore the significance of considering broader socio-economic and environmental benefits beyond direct financial returns. Direct benefits, in Year 2024 values, included an estimated €35,394 in water savings, €2,124 in energy savings, €84,272 in reduced surface runoff, and €50,563 in erosion control, contributing to a total of €172,354. Indirect benefits, particularly the revenue from increased tourism (€1,057,133), played a critical role in determining the project's overall economic sustainability.

Hence, the CBA showed that the restoration of historic water cisterns in Piran has good potential as a cost-effective adaptation strategy, particularly when considering the integration of cultural heritage conservation and sustainable water management. The CBA results indicate that when tourism revenue is included in the expected restoration benefits, the project is economically viable, with a positive net present value (NPV) of €626,388. However, when excluding tourism benefits, the project exhibits a negative NPV of -€339,823, highlighting the limited economic feasibility of cistern restoration when viewed solely from a water savings perspective.

¹⁴ Keating et al. (2015) presents estimates in Pounds at the 2025 price level. The conversion and adjustment to Euros for 2024 were carried out using the following sources:

https://www.ecb.europa.eu/stats/policy_and_exchange_rates/euro_reference_exchange_rates/html/eurofxref-graph-gbp.en.html;
<https://www.ceicdata.com/en/european-union/esa-2010-eurostat-gdp-deflator-current-price/gdp-deflator-eu-28>.

Despite the positive findings when tourism benefits are considered, the study highlights key challenges that may hinder the widespread adoption of this approach. These include high fixed costs for pre-treatment, water quality monitoring, and infrastructure maintenance, which, as discussed earlier, may not be justified purely by water savings alone. Indeed, the limited water capacity of the cisterns and the high initial investment costs pose constraints to the project's sustainability from a pure financial standpoint.

While the water storage capacity of the cisterns is relatively limited due to their shallow depth and small surface area, their potential role in flood control and urban cooling remains relevant. Additionally, the comparison between water transportation via tanker trucks and the use of restored cisterns suggests that the latter represents a more cost-effective and environmentally sustainable solution for non-potable water applications such as street cleaning and irrigation.

A hybrid approach integrating cistern restoration with complementary adaptation measures, such as advanced water recycling systems and sustainable urban drainage solutions, could enhance the resilience of Piran's water management framework. Additionally, future research should explore improved methods for quantifying indirect benefits, particularly cultural and environmental co-benefits, which were not fully accounted for in this analysis.

In conclusion, while the restoration of historic water cisterns presents a valuable opportunity to address water scarcity challenges in Piran, its success is heavily dependent on external factors, such as tourism revenues and broader sustainability initiatives. Ensuring long-term viability requires strategic investment, stakeholder engagement, and integration with wider climate resilience and urban development policies.

7.2.4. Renovation of degraded areas into green spaces in Piran

The primary objective of the suggested project is to assess the economic viability and desirability for the transformation of degraded urban areas into open access green spaces and pocket parks in Piran. Towards this, a cost-benefit analysis (CBA) was performed with the use of the Green Infrastructure Valuation Toolkit (GI-Val), considering four specific sites: the Kindergarten Park, Dog Park, Maritime Museum Park, and Olive Trees Park. These areas were selected based on their potential to provide multifunctional benefits, such as improving air quality, mitigating urban heat, enhancing biodiversity, and promoting social cohesion. Furthermore, these four areas are distributed across town, each with different tourism visitation patterns; hence, differences in their uses (especially in tourism) were considered. The economic analysis compared the costs of land acquisition, development, and maintenance with key benefits, including increased property values, healthcare savings, stormwater management improvements, and tourism revenue.

The suggested interventions have proven to be a viable and beneficial climate adaptation strategy. The performed CBA indicates positive net present values (NPVs) for a 42-year project, demonstrating both economic feasibility and broader environmental and social gains. The suggested interventions also align with EU policies on urban greening, biodiversity conservation, and climate resilience, while also enhancing the well-being of local communities.

The results of the CBA indicate substantial economic benefits across all sites. The Kindergarten Park and Olive Trees Park, in particular, showed high NPVs of €1.8 million and €3.1 million, respectively, largely due to their capacity to attract visitors and enhance urban biodiversity. The Dog Park and Maritime Museum Park also demonstrated positive NPVs of €676,513 and €210,763, confirming the financial viability of their development. A sensitivity analysis considering different discount rates and disaster scenarios further reinforced the resilience of these investments, indicating that even in the event of a complete park reconstruction because of a disaster event in the middle of the considered 42-year period, the benefits outweigh the costs.

Beyond economic returns, these green spaces contribute significantly to environmental sustainability. They are expected to reduce urban heat by up to 0.96°C, sequester approximately 289,000 kg of CO₂-equivalent, and divert significant amounts of stormwater from drainage systems. The social benefits include increased recreational opportunities, enhanced community engagement, and improved mental and physical health. The project is also estimated to generate new employment opportunities, with several Full-Time Equivalent (FTE) jobs expected to be created annually.

Despite the positive outlook, the study highlights key challenges such as relatively high initial capital costs, continuous maintenance requirements, and potential land-use conflicts. The success of these green spaces will depend on effective long-term planning, stakeholder engagement, and integration with broader urban development strategies. Additionally, while tourism revenue plays a crucial role in the economic viability of these projects, reliance on external visitors introduces an element of uncertainty that should be addressed through diversified funding strategies.

In conclusion, the renovation of degraded areas into green spaces in Piran presents a compelling case for urban sustainability and resilience. These pre-feasibility study findings support investment in nature-based solutions as a means to enhance climate adaptation, improve public health, and foster socio-economic development, also by providing local jobs for the maintenance of green spaces. Future research could focus on refining valuation methodologies for non-monetary benefits and exploring financing mechanisms to ensure the most efficient implementation and the long-term success of the suggested urban greening initiatives.

7.2.5. Beach and dunes valuation and management in the context of coastal erosion in Sligo

Sand dune management is becoming increasingly important across Ireland, in order to not only prevent coastal erosion, but also offer a range of ecosystem services. As this study indicates, the economic and non-economic value of coastal/beach ecosystem is highly substantial, and better dune restoration and management can offer significant coastal protection. Our results suggest that dune management has the potential to deliver significant economic benefits relative to its management costs. Additionally, healthy dunes enable more resilient beaches, which are better equipped to withstand coastal hazards and sea level rise, as the coastal ecosystem is interconnected.

Numerous management practices can support the development of healthy dune systems. For example, human impact on dunes can be reduced by diverting visitor traffic through use of signage and creation of pedestrian pathways. The impact of climate change – such as sea level rise, storms, floods, and erosion – can be reduced by identifying priority-areas to implement dune management interventions on the beaches, as well as monitoring the efficacy of dune management practices like fencing, sand-trapping, vegetation, etc. Additionally, addressing beach geo-morphology through practices like dune nourishment and increasing beach width can support resilient dunes and maximise coastal protection.

It is equally important to monitor and understand the role of any grey engineering-based infrastructure, both alone and in connection with EBA practices, in terms of their potential to mitigate or exacerbate erosion in certain areas of the beach as found in our case study. Growing scientific evidence suggests that the socioeconomic and environmental co-benefits of EBAs, such as sand dune management, may be larger than the co-benefits of grey infrastructure. Despite this, undervaluation of co-benefits has affected the uptake of EBAs in policy. Policy changes including greater stakeholder engagement, improved local knowledge and public awareness, increased monitoring and accessibility to reliable data, and multidisciplinary solutions can address this.

The analysis conducted on Sligo County's beaches – Enniscrone, Streedagh, and Strandhill – focused on some of the key benefits of dunes identified, including coastal protection, support of recreation, and carbon sequestration. These

benefits were selected due to some availability of data, stakeholder responses, and the perceived significance of these ecosystem services. The study did not account for additional benefits like biodiversity conservation, water quality improvement, job creation, social cohesion, among others. These broader benefits were identified by local stakeholders during the MCA workshop held in March 2023, which helped prioritise sand dune management as an EBA strategy in Sligo County (Tiwari et al., 2024).

Furthermore, while the analysis focused on shoreline evolution under sea level rise, other impacts outside of its scope are also worth mentioning, such as the effects of coastal storms on dunes and the surrounding areas. Effective dune management could help mitigate the infrastructural damage costs of climate change, by offering coastal protection to housing properties, roads and transportation networks, agricultural farms, recreational sites, and other areas. Evidence also indicates that sand dunes could move and grow in response to geomorphological activity on the beach, naturally adapting to rising sea level levels. Nevertheless, there is still uncertainty regarding the adaptation of dunes to high-intensity storms and how these systems – particularly the various stages of dune succession – might evolve over time with climate change and other anthropogenic impacts.

Finally, it is pivotal to engage in dune management practices that do not negatively impact the local ecosystem or cause maladaptation. For instance, introducing invasive species of vegetation to fix dunes could create soil that is susceptible to eventual inundation. Incorrect fencing or too much fencing can hinder the effective movement of sand, thus reducing the effectiveness of the dune system. It is equally important to combine local knowledge with scientific evidence to engage residents and communities to understand dune dynamics comprehensively. This local knowledge can be incorporated into policy, based on the living lab principles of co-creation and co-design. Whilst this study offers important data and insights, it also highlights significant knowledge gaps relating to the availability of shoreline erosion data, coastal elevation models and monetary valuation of ecosystem services in the northwest region of Ireland. This data is based on assumptions and proxies, and whilst these values can be used as a reference, improvements in data quality in this region can further increase our understanding of the contributions of local natural resources.

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APPENDIX SECTION

ANNEX 1. SPECIFIC ASSUMPTIONS ASSOCIATED WITH THE CASE STUDY “RENOVATION OF DEGRADED AREAS INTO GREEN SPACES IN PIRAN”

“Project area (After)”: “69.2” ha (Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia, 2024) for all parks. This is the wider project settlement area affected by the investment.

“Total area of greenspace (Before)”: “0” ha for all parks due to the general assumptions.

“Total area of greenspace (After)”: “0.20129” ha (Kindergarten), “0.04427” ha (Dog Park), “0.02700” ha (Maritime Museum), and “0.88180” ha (Olive Trees) (

Table A 1).

“New green space created by the project (After)”: Same as the total area of greenspace (after) due to the general assumptions.

“Pre-existing area of greenspace enhanced by the project (After)”: “0.00000” ha for all due to the general assumptions.

“Tree cover (Before)”: “0.00000” ha for all due to the general assumptions.

“Tree cover (After)”: Same as the total area of greenspace (after) due to the general assumptions.

“Total area of green roofs (Before & After)”: “0.00000” ha for all due to general knowledge of the area and the general assumptions.

“Cycle routes (Before & After)”: “0” km for all due to general knowledge of the area and the fact that the areas are too small to create cycle routes.

“Current cycle routes upgraded”: “0” km for all, as there are no cycle routes.

“Footpaths (Before)”: “0” km for all due to general knowledge of the area and the general assumptions.

“Footpaths (After)”: “0.050” km (Kindergarten), “0.025” ha (Dog Park), “0.025” ha (Maritime Museum), and “0.100” ha (Olive Trees). The assumptions derive from general knowledge of the area and

Table A 1.

“Footpaths upgraded (After)”: “0” km for all, as there are no footpaths.

“Number of households within 300m and 1200m (Before)”: “67” and “1,076” respectively for all. These assumptions were derived from the fact that as of January 1, 2022, the Municipality of Piran, Slovenia, had approximately 10,493 dwellings, which typically corresponds to a household, in an area of 44 km² (Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia, 2022). These result in 238 households per km², 67 households in an area of 0.283 km² (<300 m radius), and 1,076 households in an area of 4.524 km² (<1,200 m radius).

“Number of businesses within 300m and 1200m (Before)”: “13” and “206” respectively for all. These assumptions were derived from the fact that, according to the Slovenian Business Register, Piran hosts approximately 2,000 registered businesses (Agency of the Republic of Slovenia for Public Legal Records and Related Services, n.d.) and the respective calculations as previously.

“Number of residents within 300m and 1200m (Before)”: “117” and “1,877” respectively for all. These assumptions were derived from the fact that, as of mid-2022, the Municipality of Piran had a population of approximately 18,259 residents (Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia, 2022) and the respective calculations as previously.

“Number of households within 300m, 1200m and 450m (After)”: “70” (<300 m radius), “1,086” (<1,200 m radius), and “157” (<450 m radius) (Kindergarten), “68” (<300 m radius), “1,078” (<1,200 m radius), and “152” (<450 m radius) (Dog Park), “67” (<300 m radius), “1,120” (<1,200 m radius), and “177” (<450 m radius) (Maritime Museum), and “80” (<300 m radius), “1,086” (<1,200 m radius), and “157” (<450 m radius) (Olive Trees). The initial assumptions were that a park like the Kindergarten park would increase the households in the area by a factor of 5% (in <300 m radius), 3% (in 300 m<x<450 m radius), and 1% in total for <1,200 m radius. The values for the other parks were calculated using linear interpolation of the differences with respect to the areas. The results were discussed with the SCORE consortium and local stakeholders and found to be reasonable.

“Number of businesses within 300m and 1200m (After)”: “14” and “208” respectively (Kindergarten), “13” and “206” respectively (Dog Park), “13” and “206” respectively (Maritime Museum), and “17” and “215” respectively (Olive Trees). The initial assumptions were that a park like the Kindergarten park would increase the businesses in the area by a factor of 5% (in <300 m radius) and 1% in total for <1,200 m radius. The values for the other parks were calculated using linear interpolation of the differences with respect to the areas. The results were discussed with the SCORE consortium and local stakeholders and found to be reasonable.

“Number of residents within 300m and 1200m (After)”: “123” and “1,896” respectively (Kindergarten), “118” and “1,881” respectively (Dog Park), “118” and “1,880” respectively (Maritime Museum), and “143” and “1,960” respectively (Olive Trees). The initial assumptions were that a park like the Kindergarten park would increase the residents in the area by a factor of 5% (in <300 m radius) and 1% in total for <1,200 m radius. The values for the other parks were calculated using linear interpolation of the differences with respect to the areas. The results were discussed with the SCORE consortium and local stakeholders and found to be reasonable.

“Number of community groups involved (Before & After)”: “1” and “5” respectively (Kindergarten), “1” and “2” respectively (Dog Park), “1” and “2” respectively (Maritime Museum), and “1” and “10” respectively (Olive Trees). Initially, it was assumed that a park like the Kindergarten park could motivate from five (5) to ten (10) new community groups involved. Nevertheless, after discussions within the SCORE consortium and local stakeholders, the lower value was used for the Kindergarten park, and the highest value was used for the much larger Olive Trees park to be on the safe side. The other “after” values were calculated using linear interpolation of the differences with respect to the areas. The “before” values for all the parks were estimated to be one (1), representing the residents who may help with the management of the areas. The results were discussed with the SCORE consortium and local stakeholders and found to be reasonable.

“Total number of users per year (Before)”: “0” for all the parks due to the general assumptions.

“Total number of users per year (After)”: “119,215” (Kindergarten), “79,477” (Dog Park), “39,738” (Maritime Museum), and “158,953” (Olive Trees), calculated as the sums of the “after” values of the following two subcategories “Of which number of visits from local visitors (recreation) (After)” and “Of which number of visits from tourist visitors (tourism) (After)”.

“Of which number of visits from local visitors (recreation) (Before)”: “0” for all the parks due to the general assumptions.

“Of which number of visits from local visitors (recreation) (After)”: “43,821” (Kindergarten), “29,214” (Dog Park), “14,607” (Maritime Museum), and “58,428” (Olive Trees). As of mid-2022, the Municipality of Piran had a population of approximately 18,259 residents (Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia, 2022). From general knowledge of the area, it was assumed that 40% of residents visit a park annually around eight (8) times. This results in 58,428, which is quite a big number for a park like the Kindergarten park but reasonable for the largest park, i.e., the Olive Trees park, for which it was used. The values for the Kindergarten park, the Dog Park, and the Maritime Museum park were calculated by multiplying 58,428 by a factor of 0.75, 0.50, and 0.25, considering their importance in terms of their area and location. The results were discussed with the SCORE consortium and local stakeholders and found to be reasonable.

“Of which number of visits from tourist visitors (tourism) (Before)”: “0” for all the parks due to the general assumptions.

“Of which number of visits from tourist visitors (tourism) (After)”: “75,394” (Kindergarten), “50,263” (Dog Park), “25,131” (Maritime Museum), and “100,525” (Olive Trees). In 2023, the number of overnight tourists in Piran, Slovenia, was 591,326 (Statista, n.d.), of which 15% are estimated to visit the largest park (i.e., Olive Trees). A 40% increase should be added to the number of overnight tourists in order to include non-overnight visitors, of which 5% are estimated to visit the largest park (i.e., Olive Trees). These resulted in 88,699 visits from overnight tourists and 11,826 visits from non-overnight tourists, totalling 100,525 visits. These assumptions were made based on general knowledge of the area and discussions with the local stakeholders. The values for the Kindergarten park, the Dog Park, and the Maritime Museum park were calculated using the same factors of 0.75, 0.50, and 0.25 as previously. The results were discussed with the SCORE consortium and local stakeholders and found to be reasonable.

“Estimate of working population (Before)”: “5,334” for all (Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia, 2022).

“Estimate of working population (After)”: “75,394” (Kindergarten), “50,263” (Dog Park), “25,131” (Maritime Museum), and “100,525” (Olive Trees). The creation of a new park, such as the largest Olive Trees park in Piran, may indirectly contribute to an increase in the working population by enhancing the area’s liveability and attractiveness. Improved green spaces lead to more tourism, local businesses, and services, which in turn generate employment opportunities. However, the actual increase in the working population depends on the scale and economic impact of the park. If the employment growth is moderate for a medium park, e.g., 3-5%, for the largest park, i.e., Olive Trees, it can be assumed that there will be a 5% increase in employment opportunities due to tourism, hospitality, and maintenance services. Therefore, the estimated working population for the Olive Trees park could increase from 5,334 to approximately 5,600 individuals. The values for the Kindergarten park, the Dog Park, and the Maritime Museum park were calculated by multiplying the difference by a factor of 0.75, 0.50, and 0.25 and adding the result to the respective before values, considering their importance in terms of their area and location. The results were discussed with the SCORE consortium and local stakeholders and found to be reasonable, but a detailed economic impact analysis would be required for a more precise projection.

“Number of residential properties at flood risk (Before)”: “75” for all. Given the frequency of reported flooding incidents (Kralj et al., 2023), it is reasonable to estimate that approximately 75 residential properties in Piran’s historic centre are at risk of flooding.

“Number of residential properties at flood risk (After)”: “63” (Kindergarten), “74” (Dog Park), “74” (Maritime Museum), and “49” (Olive Trees). The implementation of flood-mitigation features like Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems (SUDS) in a park, like the Kindergarten park, could reduce localised flooding risks by 10–30%, potentially protecting a significant portion of at-risk properties. Reducing 75 by 15% leads to 63. The values for the other parks were calculated using linear interpolation of the differences with respect to the areas and by multiplying with a factor of 0.5, taking into account that the other parks are next to the sea, so there are residents only at one-half side of theirs.

“Number of commercial, business, industrial premises at flood risk (Before)”: “75” for all. Given the frequency of reported flooding incidents (Kralj et al., 2023), it is reasonable to estimate that approximately 30 commercial, business, and industrial premises in Piran’s historic center are at risk of flooding.

“Number of commercial, business, industrial premises at flood risk (After)”: “26” (Kindergarten), “30” (Dog Park), “30” (Maritime Museum), and “21” (Olive Trees). The implementation of flood-mitigation features like Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems (SUDS) in a park, like the Kindergarten park, could reduce localised flooding risks by 10–30%, potentially protecting a significant portion of at-risk properties. Reducing 30 by 15% leads to 26. The values for the other parks were calculated using linear interpolation of the differences with respect to the areas and by multiplying with a factor of 0.5, taking into account that the other parks are next to the sea, so there are commercial, business, industrial premises only at one-half side of theirs.

“Amount of SUDS storage (Before)”: “100” m³ for all, as the minimum capacity of unused land according to the general assumptions.

“Amount of SUDS storage (After)”: “1,250” m³ (Kindergarten), “275” m³ (Dog Park), “168” m³ (Maritime Museum), and “5,476” m³ (Olive Trees). A well-designed green park, like the Kindergarten park, could add 500–2,000 m³ of SUDS storage, depending on the park’s size and features like retention basins, permeable surfaces, and rain gardens. The mean value of that is 1,250 m³. The values for the other parks were calculated using linear interpolation of the differences with respect to the areas.

“Length of watercourse (Before)”: “0” km for all, after discussions with local stakeholders and the general assumptions.

“Length of watercourse improved/restored (After)”: “0,075” km (Kindergarten), “0,016” km (Dog Park), “0,010” km (Maritime Museum), and “0,329” km (Olive Trees). New features like bioswales or small artificial streams might add 50–100 meters of new watercourse features within a park, like the Kindergarten park. The mean value of that is 0.075 km. The values for the other parks were calculated using linear interpolation of the differences with respect to the areas.

“Is the area serviced by a combined sewer system? If 'Yes' please enter 1”: “1” after discussions with local stakeholders.

“Area designated for nature and wildlife conservation (local designation) (Before & After)”: “0” ha and “0” ha, respectively, for all parks, as there are no local designations and no foreseen ones for such small parks.

“Area designated for nature and wildlife conservation (national designation) (Before & After)”: “0” ha and “0” ha, respectively, for all parks, as there is no national designation and no foreseen ones for such small parks.

“Area of woodland w/biodiversity value not captured above (i.e., not protected through local or national designation) (Before)”: “0” ha, for all parks, due to common knowledge of the area and the general assumptions.

“Area of woodland w/biodiversity value not captured above (i.e., not protected through local or national designation) (After)”: “0.20000” ha (Kindergarten), “0.04399” ha (Dog Park), “0.02683” ha (Maritime Museum), and “0.87615” ha (Olive Trees). These are the whole areas of the parks, reduced by the “Area of wetland w/biodiversity value not captured above (After)”. Initially, after discussion within the SCORE consortium, it was estimated that a small area of 0.00129 ha would probably be an area of wetland with biodiversity value, leaving 0.20000 ha as an area of woodland with biodiversity value in Kindergarten park, and the rest of the values both for the wetlands and the woodlands were calculated accordingly using linear interpolation with respect to the areas.

“Area of wetland w/biodiversity value not captured above (i.e., not protected through local or national designation) (Before)”: “0” ha, for all parks, due to common knowledge of the area and the general assumptions.

“Area of wetland w/biodiversity value not captured above (i.e., not protected through local or national designation) (After)”: “0.00129” ha (Kindergarten), “0.00028” ha (Dog Park), “0.00017” ha (Maritime Museum), and “0.00565” ha (Olive Trees). These are the whole areas of the parks, reduced by the “Area of woodland w/biodiversity value not captured above (ie: not protected through local or national designation) (After)”. Initially, after discussion within the SCORE consortium, it was estimated that a small area of 0.00129 ha would probably be an area of wetland with biodiversity value, leaving 0.20000 ha as an area of woodland with biodiversity value in Kindergarten park, and the rest of the values both for the wetlands and the woodlands were calculated accordingly using linear interpolation with respect to the areas.

“Number of construction jobs created as a result of scheme delivery (After)”: “10” ha (Kindergarten), “5” ha (Dog Park), “5” ha (Maritime Museum), and “15” ha (Olive Trees). It is estimated that five (5) to 15 construction jobs will be needed, depending on the scale and duration of the project, i.e., on the area of each park. The lowest values were selected for the two smallest parks, the highest for the largest Olive Trees park, and the mean value for the Kindergarten park, according to their areas.

“Number of jobs created/safeguarded for management/maintenance of site (After)”: “2” ha (Kindergarten), “1” ha (Dog Park), “1” ha (Maritime Museum), and “3” ha (Olive Trees). It is estimated that one (1) to three (3) jobs for management and maintenance will be needed, depending on the area of each park. The lowest values were selected for the two smallest parks, the highest for the largest Olive Trees park, and the mean value for the Kindergarten park, according to their areas.

“Average residential property price in the area (Before)”: “£333,333”. As of November 2024, the average residential property price in Piran, Slovenia, varies based on property type, location, and amenities. According to listings on Properstar, apartments in Piran are priced between approximately \$161,000 and \$553,000, depending on size and features (Properstar, 2024). Additionally, Tranio reports that real estate prices in Piran range from €150,000 to €12,000,000, reflecting a broad spectrum that includes both modest apartments and luxury villas (Tranio, 2024). Given this wide range, a mid-range apartment in Piran is estimated to cost between €300,000 and €500,000. The mean value is €400,000, i.e., £333,333, with a conversion rate of 1.2 from British pounds to Euros due to the general assumptions.

The SCORE Consortium partners and local stakeholders reviewed all the input values and found them reasonable.

Specific assumptions for benefits per category

Climate change adaptation and mitigation.

“Additional residential buildings with large trees < 10m”: “0” for all parks, as there are no additional residential buildings with large trees in an area of less than 10 m.

“% building(s) air conditioned”: “50%” for all parks. While in Slovenia, the prevalence of air-conditioning systems was around 37% per building in 2014 (Building and Civil Engineering Institute, 2014), it can be safely assumed that in 2024, in Piran, Slovenia, which is a highly touristic destination, it should be around 50%, as a rough estimate.

“Yearly air conditioning use”: “500” Hrs/yr for all, assuming air conditioning is used for around four (4) hours per day in the summer months from May to August, which is also the default value.

“Broadleaf (No thinning)”: “0.20129” ha (Kindergarten), “0.04427” ha (Dog Park), “0.02700” ha (Maritime Museum), and “0.88180” ha (Olive Trees). The default value is tree cover “after” minus tree cover “before”, all counted as broadleaf with no thinning, according to the GI-Val toolkit and due to the general assumptions.

“Broadleaf (Thinned)”: “0” ha for all, due to the previous assumptions.

“Conifer (No thinning)”: “0” ha for all, due to the previous assumptions.

“Conifer (Thinned)”: “0” ha for all, due to the previous assumptions.

“Land converted from improved grassland or other land use to semi-natural grassland”: “0” ha for all, due to the general assumptions.

“Land converted from arable to wetland”: “0” ha for all, due to the general assumptions.

“Land converted from grassland to wetland”: “0” ha for all, due to the general assumptions.

The SCORE Consortium partners and local stakeholders reviewed all the input values and found them reasonable.

Flood alleviation and water management.

“Annual rainfall”: “958” mm/yr for all. This is the mean value of the nearest meteorological station at the airport of Portorož (7 km away) (Environmental Agency of the Republic of Slovenia, n.d.).

“Self-sufficient properties for surface drainage”: “0” for all, due to common knowledge of the area and discussions with local stakeholders.

“Self-sufficient properties for surface drainage”: “0” for all, due to common knowledge of the area and discussions with local stakeholders.

“Developed area 1”: “0” for all, due to common knowledge of the area and discussions with local stakeholders (the same applies for all rows about developed areas).

The SCORE Consortium partners and local stakeholders reviewed all the input values and found them reasonable.

Place and communities.

“Percentage of local households with a view of green space (Existing): “33%” for all, i.e., one-third of households in less than 300 m radius. This is a rough estimate derived from common knowledge of the area and discussions with local stakeholders, considering also the general assumptions that the areas are unused lands.

“Percentage of local households with a view of green space (Proposed): “58%” (Kindergarten), “50%” (Dog Park), “42%” (Maritime Museum), and “67%” (Olive Trees). This is also a rough estimation, assuming that the percentage would double for the biggest park, i.e., Olive Trees park. The values for the Kindergarten park, the Dog Park, and the Maritime Museum park were calculated by multiplying the difference of the proposed to the existing value of the Olive Trees park by a factor of 0.75, 0.50, and 0.25 and by adding the result to the existing value of each, considering their importance in terms of their area and location.

“Number of volunteers (Existing & Proposed)”: “3” and “15” (Kindergarten), “3” and “6” (Dog Park), “3” and “6” (Maritime Museum), and “3” and “30” (Olive Trees). The values were calculated assuming that each local community group mentioned is composed of three (3) people.

“Number of volunteers (Existing & Proposed)”: “3” and “15” No/yr (Kindergarten), “3” and “6” No/yr (Dog Park), “3” and “6” No/yr (Maritime Museum), and “3” and “30” No/yr (Olive Trees). The values were calculated assuming that each local community group mentioned is composed of three (3) people.

“Average number of hours worked per volunteer (Existing & Proposed)”: “24” and “24” for all, after the conservative assumption that a volunteer offers around two (2) hours of voluntary work per month.

The SCORE Consortium partners and local stakeholders reviewed all the input values and found them reasonable.

Health and wellbeing.

“Number of local residents beyond 1200m (Before & After)”: “16,382” and “16,363” (Kindergarten), “16,382” and “16,378” (Dog Park), “16,382” and “16,379” (Maritime Museum), and “16382” and “16299” (Olive Trees). The values were calculated by subtracting the population in less than 300 m and between 300 and 1,200 m radius of each park from the total population of 18,259 (Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia, 2022).

“Residents within 300m: Average No of trips per year (Before & After)”: “83” and “100” for all. The default values were used based on the literature (Grahn & Stigsdotter, 2003) since there is no local survey data.

“Residents 301m - 1200m: Average No of trips per year (Before & After)”: “39” and “47” for all. The default values were used based on the literature (Grahn & Stigsdotter, 2003) since there is no local survey data.

“Residents beyond 1200m: Average No of trips per year (Before & After)”: “0” and “0” for all. The default values were used based on the literature (Grahn & Stigsdotter, 2003) since there is no local survey data.

“Residents beyond 1200m: Total trips per year (Before & After)”: “0” and “0” for all. The default values were used based on the literature (Grahn & Stigsdotter, 2003) since there is no local survey data.

"Residents > 1200m: Total distance travelled per year by all pedestrians = X km (Before & After)": "0" and "0" for all. The default values were used based on the literature (Grahn & Stigsdotter, 2003) since there is no local survey data.

"Number of local residents (other - beyond 1200m) (Before & After)": "0" and "0" for all. The default values were used based on the literature (Grahn & Stigsdotter, 2003) since there is no local survey data.

"Proportion of non-users within the local population (Before & After)": "38%" and "38%" for all. The default values were used (English Heritage et al., 2004) since there is no local survey data.

"Proportion of green infrastructure users using the asset for cycling (Before & After)": "10%" and "10%" for all. The default values were used (Greenspace, 2007) since there is no local survey data.

"Proportion of green infrastructure users using the asset for cycling (Before & After)": "10%" and "10%" for all. The default values were used (Greenspace, 2007) since there is no local survey data.

"Residents within 300m: Average trips per year (Before & After)": "83" and "100" for all. The default values were used based on the literature (Grahn & Stigsdotter, 2003) since there is no local survey data.

"Residents 301m - 1200m: Average trips per year (Before & After)": "39" and "47" for all. The default values were used based on the literature (Grahn & Stigsdotter, 2003) since there is no local survey data.

"Residents beyond 1200m: Average trips per year (Before & After)": "0" and "0" for all. The default values were used based on the literature (Grahn & Stigsdotter, 2003) since there is no local survey data.

"Residents beyond 1200m: Total trips per year (Before & After)": "0" and "0" for all. The default values were used based on the literature (Grahn & Stigsdotter, 2003) since there is no local survey data.

"Residents Other - beyond 1200m: Total distance travelled per year (Before & After)": "0" and "0" for all. The default values were used based on the literature (Grahn & Stigsdotter, 2003) since there is no local survey data.

"What type of location is the project in?": "Urban" "Roadside" for all, due to common knowledge of the area.

"Percentage evergreen (before)": "0%" for all, due to general assumptions.

"Percentage evergreen (new planting)": "100%" for all, due to general assumptions.

"Leaf-on date (average last frost date)": "15 March", for all. The estimated leaf-on date (average last frost date) for Piran, Slovenia is between March 11 and March 20, with a mean value of March 15 (PlantMaps, n.d.a).

"Leaf-off date (average first frost date)": "15 December", for all. The estimated leaf-off date (average first frost date) for Piran, Slovenia is between December 11 and December 20, with a mean value of December 15 (PlantMaps, n.d.b).

"Factor to account for night-time": "0.5" for all. The default values were used. Gases are not absorbed during the night as stomata are closed.

"Factor to account for periods of precipitation": "0.5" for all. The default values were used. Dry deposition does not occur during periods of precipitation.

The SCORE Consortium partners and local stakeholders reviewed all the input values and found them reasonable.

Land and property values.

"New green space created: Of which high quality 'city park'": "0.100645" Ha (Kindergarten), "0.022135" Ha (Dog Park), "0.013500" Ha (Maritime Museum), and "0.440900" Ha (Olive Trees). The values are half of the total park areas. Since there is no implementation study to know what kind of park they would be or what percentage of them will be one kind of park or another, the best approach is to assume that half of the parks will be high-quality "city parks" and half "local parks".

"New green space created: Of which quality 'local park'": "0.100645" Ha (Kindergarten), "0.022135" Ha (Dog Park), "0.013500" Ha (Maritime Museum), and "0.440900" Ha (Olive Trees). The values are half of the total park areas. Since there is no implementation study to know what kind of park they would be or what percentage of them will be one kind of park or another, the best approach is to assume that half of the parks will be high-quality "city parks" and half "local parks".

"Green space enhanced: Of which high quality 'city park'": "0" Ha for all, due to the general assumptions.

"Green space enhanced: Of which quality 'local park'": "0" Ha for all, due to the general assumptions.

"% of properties with green space <450m currently and benefiting": "60%" for all. It is not clear if this refers to privately owned green spaces or closeness or access to green spaces; therefore, the default value was used.

The SCORE Consortium partners and local stakeholders reviewed all the input values and found them reasonable.

Investment.

There are no input values required in that tool.

Labour productivity.

“Number of workers encouraged to walk or cycle to work by green infrastructure scheme”: “21%” for all. The default value is 10%. Nevertheless, in Slovenia, 20.9% walk or cycle at least 30 min per day (Eurostat, 2022); therefore, it is safe to use this value rounded to zero decimal digits. Apart from that, the cell C15 of the Sheet “7 Lab Prod” was corrected from “=('Project Data'!E48)*D15” to “=('Project Data'!E48-'Project Data'!D48)*D15” in order to include only the new workers.

“Average hours worked per day (Census average)”: “7.5” for all. This is the default value for the United Kingdom, and for Slovenia, the same will be used as both countries have the same average hours worked per worker per week (Marian, n.d.).

“Average gross daily wage of walker / cyclist”: “£91.93” for all. The average gross monthly wages in Slovenia stand at €2,427 as of 2023 (My Dolce Casa, 2024). Divided by 22 (for the working days of the month) and 1.20 (the assumed conversion rate from Euros to British pounds from the general assumptions), the result is £91.93.

“Benefit discount. WHO research used is based on 30 min exercise 5 days per week. The assumption being made here is that people walk 4 out of 5 days/week.”: “77%” for all. The assumed default value was used.

The SCORE Consortium partners and local stakeholders reviewed all the input values and found them reasonable.

Tourism.

“Total estimated number of tourists visiting the site”: “4,524” (Kindergarten), “1,508” (Dog Park), “503” (Maritime Museum), and 10,053” (Olive Trees). The default way that the toolkit counts that number is by subtracting the “Before” tourist visitors from the “After” tourist visitors. In this specific case, due to the general assumptions, the “Before” visitors are “0” and, thus, all the visitors would be found to be new visitors due to the creation of the parks, which is not correct. Therefore, a new approach was used. For Piran, Slovenia, where tourism is already strong, green open parks and pocket parks could increase tourist numbers by 2-5% proportionally for smaller parks and up to 5-10% for larger, well-designed parks integrated into the town’s cultural and natural landscape, as the positive correlation of tourist attraction and green open parks and pocket parks is well documented (Terkenli et al., 2017). While these numbers may seem high enough, they will be used only for those who would visit the parks, which are much smaller than the whole number of tourists because Piran is an already touristically developed area, and the aim is to find the number of new tourists that would visit Piran due to the parks. Therefore, the formula that was used was the following: “=('Project Data'!E46-'Project Data'!D46)*Factor” where the increasing factor is as follows: “6%” (Kindergarten), “3%” Ha (Dog Park), “2%” Ha (Maritime Museum), and “10%” (Olive Trees).

“Of which day visits”: “1,809” (Kindergarten), “603” (Dog Park), “201” (Maritime Museum), and “4,021” (Olive Trees). The values were calculated as previously by the totals multiplied by a factor of 40% for day visitors.

“Of which overnight visits”: “2,714” (Kindergarten), “905” (Dog Park), “302” (Maritime Museum), and “6,032” (Olive Trees). The values were calculated as previously by the totals multiplied by a factor of 60% for day visitors.

“Average expenditure per visitor day: Day visitors”: “£16.7” for all. According to interviews with local stakeholders, day visitors spend around €20. To British pounds, that is £16.7 with a conversion rate of 1.2

“Average expenditure per visitor day: Overnight visitors”: “£33.3” for all. According to interviews with local stakeholders, overnight visitors spend around €40. To British pounds that is £33.3 with a conversion rate of 1.

There are a couple of yellow cells in the following tool, “8.2 Employment supported by tourism,” but all these are auto-calculation cells, and the default values of the libraries will be used.

The SCORE Consortium partners and local stakeholders reviewed all the input values and found them reasonable.

Recreation and leisure.

“Of which (specify breakdown if known)”: “0” for all different activities for all parks. This is the default value for not known breakdowns, as in such a pre-feasibility study, due to the general assumptions.

Biodiversity.

All cells are auto-calculation cells.

Land management.

All cells are auto-calculation cells.

The SCORE Consortium partners and local stakeholders reviewed all the input values and found them reasonable.

Specific assumptions for capital costs

The capital costs were divided in the following categories: “Trees”, “Equipment”, “Construction”, “Labor”, “Studies”, and “Miscellaneous”.

“Capital costs: Trees”: “£20,129” (Kindergarten), “£5,000” (Dog Park), “£3,000” (Maritime Museum), and “£88,000” (Olive Trees), assuming 10 trees per 100 m² £100 per evergreen tree (Noel, 2024).

“Capital costs: Equipment”: “£17,500” (Kindergarten), “£1,000” (Dog Park), “£500” (Maritime Museum), and “£41,000” (Olive Trees). Assuming that a park like the Kindergarten park will need around five (5) benches and one (1) playground, the Dog Park, and the Maritime Museum park will need two (2) and one (1) bench, respectively, but no playground, due to their much smaller size, and the Olive Trees park will need 22 benches and two (2) playgrounds. The final costs were calculated assuming that a bench costs £500 and a playground “£15,000”.

“Capital costs: Construction”: “£130,839” (Kindergarten), “£28,776” (Dog Park), “£17,550” (Maritime Museum), and “£573,170” (Olive Trees), assuming that the construction cost of a high-quality city park is £80/m² and of a local park £50/m².

“Capital costs: Labor”: “£60,000” (Kindergarten), “£30,000” (Dog Park), “£30,000” (Maritime Museum), and “£180,000” (Olive Trees). The costs were estimated with the following assumptions: 10 workers for three (3) months (Kindergarten), five (5) workers for three (3) months (Dog Park), five (5) workers for three (3) months (Maritime Museum), and 15 workers for six (6) months (Olive Trees), for an average salary of £2,000/month per construction worker. The number of workers was estimated above, and the duration has been doubled for the largest Olive Trees park.

“Capital costs: Studies and surveys”: “£11,423” (Kindergarten), “£3,210” (Dog Park), “£2,538” (Maritime Museum), and “£44,118” (Olive Trees). These costs were calculated as 5% of all the previous costs (Trees, Equipment, Construction, and Labor), according to the literature and practice (Infrastructure and Projects Authority, 2021).

“Capital costs: Overheads and miscellaneous”: “£23,989” (Kindergarten), “£6,741” (Dog Park), “£5,329” (Maritime Museum), and “£92,647” (Olive Trees). These costs were calculated as 10% of all the previous costs (Trees, Equipment, Construction, Labor, and Studies and surveys), according to the literature and practice (De Bonis, 2024).

The SCORE Consortium partners and local stakeholders reviewed all the input values and found them reasonable.

Specific assumptions for maintenance costs

“Management and maintenance costs: Horticultural maintenance”: “£1,241” (Kindergarten), “£273” (Dog Park), “£166” (Maritime Museum), and “£5,436” (Olive Trees), all per year from the second year up to the 42nd year. Urban gardens in Ljubljana, Slovenia, have a horticultural maintenance cost of 1.48 €/m² (Glavan et al., 2016). Evergreen tree parks have less horticultural maintenance costs than urban gardens; therefore, a factor of 0.75 and 0.25 was applied for high-quality city park areas and for local park areas, respectively. Finally, the conversion rate of 1.20 from British pounds to Euros was applied.

“Management and maintenance costs: Labor”: “£48,000” (Kindergarten), “£24,000” (Dog Park), “£24,000” (Maritime Museum), and “£72,000” (Olive Trees), all per year from the second year up to the 42nd year. Labor costs were calculated by multiplying the number of maintenance workers by the number of months per year, i.e., 12, and by an average salary of £2,000/month per maintenance worker.

“Management and maintenance costs: Utilities”: “£48,000” (Kindergarten), “£24,000” (Dog Park), “£24,000” (Maritime Museum), and “£72,000” (Olive Trees), all per year from the second year up to the 42nd year. The average utility costs for an 85m² apartment in Slovenia is €175 per month, i.e., €2,100 per year, and €24.71 per year/m². Given that the utility cost for parks per m² is much lower, a factor of 10% was applied for high-quality city park areas and 5% for local park areas. Finally, the conversion rate of 1.20 from British pounds to Euros was applied.

“Management and maintenance costs: Utilities”: “£3,100” (Kindergarten), “£682” (Dog Park), “£416” (Maritime Museum), and “£13,580” (Olive Trees), all per year from the second year up to the 42nd year. The average utility costs for an 85m² apartment in Slovenia is €175 per month, i.e., €2,100 per year, and €24.71 per year/m². Given that the utility cost for parks per m² is much lower, a factor of 10% was applied for high-quality city park areas and 5% for local park areas. Finally, the conversion rate of 1.20 from British pounds to Euros was applied.

“Management and maintenance costs: Equipment replacement”: “£3,100” (Kindergarten), “£682” (Dog Park), “£416” (Maritime Museum), and “£13,580” (Olive Trees), all per year from the second year up to the 42nd year. Timber benches typically last 5 to 15 years (Tudor Environmental, n.d.), with a mean value of 10 years, meaning that 0.1 benches should be replaced per year, i.e., £50 per year is required to

replace one bench in time. The lifespan of playground equipment will differ from supplier to supplier but will generally last up to 10 years (Huck Nets, 2014), i.e., £1,500 per year is required to replace one playground in time.

“Management and maintenance costs: Cleaning”: “£1,590” (Kindergarten), “£350” (Dog Park), “£213” (Maritime Museum), and “£6,966” (Olive Trees), all per year from the second year up to the 42nd year. The average maintenance cost for parks in Italy is €1.10 per m² per year (Tempesta, 2015). This was adjusted by a factor of 0.86 due to different labour costs in Slovenia (25.5) and Italy (29.8) in 2023 (Eurostat, 2024). Finally, the conversion rate of 1.20 from British pounds to Euros was applied. The result is €0.79 per m² per year.

The SCORE Consortium partners and local stakeholders reviewed all the input values and found them reasonable.

Finally, the cells of the toolkit were examined, and all the needed modifications were made to agree with the assumptions. For example, the default discount rate was changed from 3.5% to 3% everywhere it was found; the calculations were made for 42 years, assuming that in the first year, the construction works will take place and in the following years, the maintenance costs will run, and the benefits will be derived, etc.

To be better understood, all the aforementioned assumptions should be read in parallel with the GI-Val Toolkit (The Mersey Forest et al., 2010) and its User’s Guide (The Mersey Forest et al., 2011).

Table A 1: Indicative NPV benefits of the GI-Val toolkit (The Mersey Forest et al., 2010) for Kindergarten park

No.	Benefits groups	Tools	Functions	GVA value	Land and property value	Other economic value	Qualitative benefits
1	1. Climate Change Adaptation & Mitigation	1.1 Reduced building energy consumption for heating	Shelter from wind	0.00 €	n.a.	n.a.	0 kWh/yr energy saved
		1.2 Avoided carbon emissions from building energy saving for heating		n.a.	n.a.	0.00 €	0 kgCO ₂ /yr not emitted
		1.3 Avoided damage from wind and storms		Tool not yet functional	n.a.	n.a.	Tool not yet functional
		1.4 Reduced peak summer surface temperatures	Reduction of urban heat island effect	Tool not yet functional	n.a.	n.a.	0.2°C in surf. temperature reduction
		1.5 Reduced building energy consumption for cooling	Cooling through shading and evapotranspiration	0.00 €	n.a.	n.a.	0 kWh/yr energy saved
		1.6 Avoided carbon emissions from building energy saving for cooling	Carbon storage and sequestration	n.a.	n.a.	0.00 €	0 kgCO ₂ not emitted
		1.7 Carbon sequestered by trees		n.a.	n.a.	2,347.20 €	66,067 kgCO ₂ e sequestered
		1.8 Carbon sequestered through other land use change		n.a.	n.a.	0.00 €	0 kgCO ₂ e sequestered
Sub-total				0.00 €	n.a.	2,347.20 €	-
2	2. Water management & Flood Alleviation	2.1 Energy and carbon emissions savings from reduced stormwater volume entering combined sewers	Interception, storage and infiltration of rainwater	63.54 €	n.a.	n.a.	46,691 L/yr water diverted from sewers
		2.2 Reduced wastewater treatment costs for domestic and commercial water customers		0.00 €	n.a.	n.a.	Tool not yet functional
		2.3 Avoided costs of traditional water drainage infrastructure		Tool not yet functional	n.a.	n.a.	Tool not yet functional
Sub-total				63.54 €	n.a.	n.a.	-
3	3. Place & communities	3.1 Willingness to pay for a view of urban green space	Catalyst for community cohesion and pride	n.a.	n.a.	26,752.93 €	18 more households with a view of green space
		3.2 Increase in volunteering		125,010.98 €	n.a.	n.a.	12 new volunteers
Sub-total				125,010.98 €	n.a.	26,752.93 €	-
4	4. Health & Well-being	4.1 Health costs savings from increase in physical activity	Provision of attractive opportunities for exercise	Tool not yet functional	n.a.	n.a.	Tool not yet functional
		4.2 Reduced mortality from increased walking and cycling		n.a.	n.a.	1,098,466.41 €	0.0 lives saved per yr
		4.3 Health cost savings from reduction in mental health disorders	Stress and mental illness alleviation	Tool not yet functional	n.a.	n.a.	Tool not yet functional
		4.4 Health cost savings from reduced in-patient stays	Healing time reduction	Tool not yet functional	n.a.	n.a.	Tool not yet functional
		4.5 Reduced mortality from respiratory illnesses	Air pollution removal	Tool not yet functional	n.a.	n.a.	Tool not yet functional
		4.6 Reduced air pollution		19,917.51 €	n.a.	n.a.	0.00 t/yr of NO ₂ removed 0.00 t/yr of O ₃ removed 0.00 t/yr of SO ₂ removed 0.01 t/yr of PM2.5 removed
Sub-total				19,917.51 €	n.a.	1,098,466.41 €	-
5		5.1 Residential land and property values uplift		n.a.	2,233,250.05 €	n.a.	n.a.

No.	Benefits groups	Tools	Functions	GVA value	Land and property value	Other economic value	Qualitative benefits
	5. Land & Property Values	5.2 Commercial land and property values uplift	Setting for higher value residential and commercial properties	n.a.	Tool not yet functional	n.a.	n.a.
	Sub-total			n.a.	2,233,250.05 €	n.a.	-
6	6. Investment	6.1 Private sector investment levered	Setting for inward investment	Tool not yet functional	n.a.	n.a.	Tool not yet functional
		6.2 Employment creation		Tool not yet functional	n.a.	n.a.	Tool not yet functional
		6.3 Image enhancement		n.a.	n.a.	Tool not yet functional	Tool not yet functional
	Sub-total			n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	-
7	7. Labour Productivity	7.1 Savings from reduced employee turnover	Reduction of 111bsenteeism from work	Tool not yet functional	n.a.	n.a.	Tool not yet functional
		7.2 Increase in labour productivity	Labor productivity improvement	Tool not yet functional	n.a.	n.a.	Tool not yet functional
		7.3 Savings from reduced 111bsenteeism from work	Attraction and retention of high quality staff	96,992.68 €	n.a.	n.a.	Between 16 and 87 work days lost avoided per yr
	Sub-total			96,992.68 €	n.a.	n.a.	-
8	8. Tourism	8.1 Tourism expenditure	Tourism attraction	2,033,407.13 €	n.a.	n.a.	4,524 Visitor days
		8.2 Employment supported by tourism		2,094,409.34 €	n.a.	n.a.	4 FTE jobs
	Sub-total (only the highest value counts)			2,094,409.34 €	n.a.	n.a.	-
9	9. Recreation & leisure	9.1 Recreational value for use by local population	Provision of recreation opportunities	n.a.	n.a.	587,872.09 €	43,821 Local users
	Sub-total			n.a.	n.a.	587,872.09 €	-
10	10. Biodiversity	10.1 Willingness to pay for protection or enhancement of biodiversity	Provision of recreation opportunities	n.a.	n.a.	0.17 €	0 Ha of land w/ biodiversity value added
	Sub-total			n.a.	n.a.	0.17 €	-
11	11. Land management	11.1 Market value of land products	Production of food, timber & industrial crops	Tool not yet functional	n.a.	n.a.	Tool not yet functional
		11.2 Employment supported by land management	Land management	1,404,744.00 €	n.a.	n.a.	2 FTE jobs
	Sub-total			1,404,744.00 €	n.a.	n.a.	-
Total economic NPV of benefits				3,741,138.06 €	2,233,250.05 €	1,127,566.70 €	-

ANNEX 2. LITERATURE ANALYSED FOR THE CASE STUDY “BEACH AND DUNES VALUATION AND MANAGEMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF COASTAL EROSION IN SLIGO”

Table A 2: Studies associated with the valuation of coastal protection

Type of Coastal Protection	Value of Coastal Protection	Study Site	Reference
Residual value of flood protection infrastructure	30,133 euros	Netherlands	IISD (2021)
Replacement costs of dune foot nourishments were used to value coastal safety maintenance against erosion- without fresh sand soil develops, marram degenerates	5,600 euros per ha/yr.	Belgium	Van der Biest et al. (2017)
Dune foot nourishment- corresponds to cost of maintaining dyke	16 euros/m ³	Netherlands	Deltafact (2012)
Sea dike maintenance costs	For Netherlands, estimated costs of \$19.3–27.2 million/km per meter of dike raised, and for Vietnam at \$0.9–1.6 million/km per meter of dike raised. Raising sea dikes in European cities costed \$21.8–31.2 million/km per meter of dike raised. Maintenance is estimated at \$0.15 million/km and \$0.03 million/m for sea dikes in Netherlands and Vietnam.	Netherlands, Vietnam, European cities	Aerts (2018)
Economic losses from erosion, future projections	16.28 (x10 ⁶ €) by 2030; 60.73 by 2050, 152.15 by 2100 (all under SSP3).	Aveiro, Portugal	Pais-Barbosa et al. (2023)
Economic losses from erosion, future projections	7-34 million AUD by 2050, 553-800 million by 2100 (worst case scenario).	Sydney, Australia	Toimil et al. (2023)
Considering all the nourishment operations (sediments dredging, transport, and deposition), this value was defined based on unitary costs of sand transposition studies carried out for the Portuguese west coast	2 euros/m ³	Portugal	Coelho et al. (2022)
Economic losses from erosion, future projections	Estimated annual damage of 2.8 million euros by 2050 and 32.3 million euros by 2100. With interventions (Parco del Mare project), damages reduce to 10,000 euros.	Italy	Amadio et al. (2022)
Valuing increase in property values from one metre of beach erosion prevention	In New Hampshire and Maine, a coastal erosion program that preserves five miles of beach is estimated to have net benefits of \$4.45/household. One-meter increase in beach width, or equivalently, the prevention of one meter of beach erosion, increased oceanfront and inlet-front property values by \$233 in Georgia.	USA	Barbier et al. (2011)
Average cost of beach re-nourishment along Texas coast	13.48USD (2013) based on average of 13 beaches.	USA	Feagin et al. (2014)
Loss of dune stabilisation because of biodiversity/species loss	Annual loss of stabilisation process at 7.325 million Israeli New Shekel, calculated based on willingness to pay	Israel	Bar et al. (2016)
Economic losses from lack of habitat restoration	Potential residential property damage from one extreme event could reach nearly 9 million euros. On the other hand, value of residential property damage could reach 115 million euros, representing a residential property damage cost prevention difference of 105 million euros.	Portugal	Cunha et al. (2021)
Cost of beach nourishment for eroded volume of sand	Price of sand: 6USD/m ³ /yr and total equals 81,790 annually	Morocco	Flayou et al. (2021)
Erosion control across Europe	Currently valued at 41.8 billion euros for coastlines across Europe; 1.7 billion euros lost by 2050 and 3.3-4.1 billion euros lost by 2100 due to coastal erosion.	33 European countries	Paprotny et al. (2018)
Cost of dune reconstruction	16.67 euros/m ³	Adriatic region, Italy	Fernandez-Montblanc et al. (2020)
Annual loss in land cover value due to coastal erosion	-1.1 million euros/yr.	Portugal	Roebeling et al. (2018)

Table A 3: Studies associated with the valuation of carbon sequestration

Dune Type	Value (Carbon/Ecosystem Service)	Type of Carbon Sequestration	Reference	Site
Embryonic/dynamic dunes	154 euros per ha/yr	Carbon sequestration was quantified using empirical study on field measurements in northern Belgium. Carbon stored in the upper first meter of soil was estimated based on soil profile characteristics and land use type. Yearly additional sequestration was calculated by dividing the amount of stored carbon by 100, assuming that soils reach their equilibrium concentration after 100 years.	Van der Biest et al. (2017)	Belgium
Semi fixed dunes	233 euros per ha/yr			
Fixed dunes	223 euros per ha/yr			
Embryonic/dynamic dunes	350 euros/hm/a	The value of the adjustment of atmospheric balance (exchange between carbon and oxygen) was determined using the opportunity cost method, carbon tax method and industrial oxygen method.	Yang and Tang (2019)	China
Semi fixed dunes	460 euros/hm/a			
Fixed dunes	2,255 euros/hm/a			
Overall sand dunes	22-54 euros/ha/yr	Mean sequestration rates are estimated at $58.2 \pm 26.2 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in dry dune grasslands and $73.0 \pm 26.2 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in wet dune slack habitats. Based on the area of dry dune and dune slack habitats (91% and 9% of UK dune area respectively) a proportional average sequestration rate for dune habitats of $59.5 \pm 25.8 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ was calculated. Carbon stock in sand dunes was calculated for carbon stored in above-ground and below-ground plant biomass, and for soil (to 15 cm).	Beuamont et al. (2014)	UK
Semi fixed dunes	215.4 tonnes			
Fixed dunes	512.3 tonnes			
Embryonic/dynamic dunes	5.72 +- 2.28 (g m ⁻² yr ⁻¹)	Soil carbon density and bulk density were computed from fresh soil weight, percentage of moisture and core volume. Carbon stocks per unit area at sample depth were computed. Carbonate content was measured on a subset of oven-dried samples from bare sand and wooded dunes, using the gravimetric method. Rates of long-term sequestration were estimated from a study on land cover change. Mean carbon stock and sequestration values were scaled up to cover the extent of coastal dunes, by multiplying the average per hectare carbon values and their standard deviations by the total habitat extents.	Drius et al. (2016)	Adriatic Region, Italy
Semi fixed dunes	5.57 +- 3.10 (g m ⁻² yr ⁻¹)			
Fixed dunes	7.49 +- 2.56 (g m ⁻² yr ⁻¹)			
Overall sand dunes (across Ireland)	26,400 tonnes, valued at 0.5 million euros; area 12,013 ha	-	Jones et al. (2008)	Ireland
Overall sand dunes	1,457 euros/yr – 7km stretch of dunes	Carbon storage in the area amounts to 45,000 tonnes. Many crops grown in North Holland have a low tolerance for salt water, and the area depend on fresh surface water for agriculture. Thus, an increase in salinity due to sea level rise can damage crops in this region. Thus, we assume that without a sufficient coastal defence system, agricultural land would be converted to bare land or water. As a result, carbon stored in crops would be released into the atmosphere. Similarly, coastal vegetation is vulnerable to saltwater intrusion and flooding. Although specific impacts depend on local species and vegetation, we assume that without constructing protective dunes, all the carbon in the area would be emitted.	IISD (2021)	Netherlands
Overall sand dunes	30.30-75.5USD/ha/yr	-	Ramesh et al. (2020)	India
Overall coastlines	19.2 billion euros	Currently valued at 19.2 billion euros for coastlines across Europe; 0.5 billion euros lost by 2050 and 1 billion euros lost by 2100 due to coastal erosion.	Paprotny et al. (2021)	33 European countries

Table A 4: Studies associated with the valuation of recreation

Study Site	Monetary Value	Recreational Services	No. of Visitors/Trips	Welfare Value	Reference
Strandhill	11.5 million euros annually	Camping, Surfing, Accommodation	Not specified	Not specified	SCC (2016)
Glenville walking trail, Galway	642,063 euros annually	Walking	210 survey respondents; 65 average trips annually; 6eur cost per trip (indicates mostly locals)	Willingness to pay per trip- 17euros; consumer surplus- 11euros	Hynes et al. (2022)
Dingle Peninsula, Kerry	9 million euros expenditure annually	Food, accommodation, transport, recreational bookings	Local communities in Maharees and Castlegregory	Consumer surplus value of 3 euros per person	Carr (2020)
Ireland (all marine recreational services)	1,69,037,814 euros	Fishing, swimming/diving, windsurfing, kayaking/sailing, snorkelling, birdwatching, walking, boating, surfing, family visit, dolphin watching, etc.	96,946,069	Not specified	Norton et al. (2018)
Belgium (Recreation from different dune categories)	Embryonic- 16,992 euros/ha/yr; semi-fixed- 30,976 euros/ha/yr; fixed- 3,033 euros/ha/yr	Based on attractiveness of landscape, recreational infrastructure, population proximity, tourism data/preferences in Flanders	300,000-500,000	4.5 euros average consumer surplus per visit, ranging between 3-9 euros.	Van der Biest et al. (2017)
Netherlands (Hondsbochhe dunes)	103,074 euros/yr- 7km stretch of dunes	Overall tourism revenue	Not applicable	Not applicable	IISD (2021)
South Korea (Shinduri dunes)	22 euros/ha/yr	Overall tourism revenue	Not applicable	Not applicable	You et al. (2018)
One-day data on visitors from Sligo County beaches (Ireland)	Not specified	Many types of activities detailed extensively for all sites	Streedagh (2021- 156 visitors); Mullaghmore (year 2015: 308 visitors)	Not applicable	Faite Ireland (2019)
Recreational value of beaches around world (Greece, Australia, Ecuador)	Costs were \$10 per beach trip for residents around Great Barrier Reef. Cost of Gold Coast is \$19.47 per person. Cost per visit for locals in Ecuador is \$13.60. And the cost per visit ranges from 10-35euros depending on age and proximity to beach across Greece.	Not specified	Not applicable	Not specified	Stamatiadou et al. (2024)
Australia (Sydney)	65-596 million AUD by 2050; 355-2120 million AUD by 2100	Recreational value of beaches	Not specified	Not applicable	Toimil et al. (2023)
India	12,585-37,445USD ha/yr	Recreational value of dunes	Not specified	Not specified	Ramesh et al. (2020)
USA (North Carolina)	Improving beach width by 100 feet increases number of trips from 11 to 14, with beachgoers willing to pay \$166/trip or \$1574 per visiting household.	Recreational value from increasing beach width	Not applicable	Widening beach width increases the consumer surplus of visitors by \$7/trip	Barbier et al. (2011)
Australia (Gold Coast)	Not applicable	Walking, swimming, surfing, enjoying nature, fishing etc.	40 million for locals, 7 million for outside tourists per year	19.5-25.7 AUD	Zhang et al. (2015)
Australia (Sydney)	Generic cost of trip to the beach was \$24.87 for Sydney residents and \$12.78 for non-residents.	Walking, swimming, surfing, enjoying nature, fishing, etc.	Not applicable, but study includes table with estimates of similar studies from across Australia	Base consumer surplus value of just visiting beach was \$10.09. Visiting a beach for swimming, followed by a walk was \$25.29/trip. Fishing and surfing provided the greatest	Pascoe et al. (2019)

Study Site	Monetary Value	Recreational Services	No. of Visitors/Trips	Welfare Value	Reference
				benefits at 22.5\$ and 11.3\$.	
Europe	52.9 billion euros per annum currently; 0.8 billion euros lost by 2050 and 1.4-1.8 billion euros lost by 2100	Recreational value from coastlines across Europe, and projections of future losses	Not applicable	33 European countries	Paprotny et al. (2021)
Morocco	17,496,082.81 USD	Recreational loss from beach retreat between 2016-2035	Not applicable	Not applicable	Flayou et al. (2021)

